

M.Sc. Thesis

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Cloud Condensation Nuclei Properties
of Organic Aerosol Particles:
Effects of Acid Dissociation and
Surfactant Partitioning

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Abstract

Aerosol particles are crucial to the formation of clouds in the atmosphere, and clouds in turn play an important role in determining global climate. The ability of aerosol particles to condense water vapor from the air and thus form cloud droplets depends on both their sizes and chemical compositions. Whereas the cloud formation properties of inorganic aerosol components are reasonably well-characterized, the significance of organic compounds has been recognized fairly recently. Organics display complex and widely varying chemical properties in activating droplet solutions and the resulting influence of organic constituents on the ability of aerosol particles to form cloud droplets still needs to be properly quantified.

In this work, the cloud condensation nuclei properties of organic aerosol components have been investigated with focus on the effects of dissociation of polyfunctional acids and partitioning of surface active agents in the growing droplets. The cloud droplet activation of aerosol particles containing citric and malic acid, sodium dodecyl sulfate and *cis*-pinonic acid has been measured in laboratory experiments using a static thermal-gradient diffusion chamber cloud condensation nucleus counter (CCNC) and predicted theoretically using model and other calculations based on Köhler theory. Citric, malic and *cis*-pinonic acid are atmospherically relevant compounds, whereas sodium dodecyl sulfate has been studied to test model predictions for a compound with well-known properties.

The effects of acid dissociation on cloud condensation nuclei properties were studied in terms of citric and malic acid containing particles. Activation properties of these particles have been calculated with application of water activity parameterizations based on acid van't Hoff factors, osmolality and direct electrodynamic balance and bulk water activity measurements. Both citric and malic acid were found to dissociate to some degree in the activating droplets, thus affecting the droplet solution water activities and the critical supersaturations of the citric and malic acid containing particles. For droplets originating from dry particles of a given composition, the degree of acid dissociation at the point of activation was seen to increase with particle size due to increasing extent of droplet dilution. A water activity parameterization employing a single constant acid van't Hoff factor could therefore not fully describe the activation properties observed for a collection of particles with a given composition and different sizes. The empirically based osmolality and bulk water activity parameterizations on the other hand captured the effects of changing acid dissociation on droplet solution water activity and activation well and are promising for future application to predicting cloud droplet activation

properties of atmospheric aerosol samples.

Surfactant partitioning and the effects on cloud condensation nuclei properties was studied for sodium dodecyl sulfate and *cis*-pinonic acid containing particles. Comparing experimental and model results clearly showed, that including partitioning in the evaluation of droplet solution surface tension was essential for a proper description of the activation behavior observed for sodium dodecyl sulfate containing particles, and that the best prediction of experiments was obtained when partitioning of sodium dodecyl sulfate was considered in determining both Kelvin and Raoult terms of the Köhler equation, as achieved by the Kuopio model. Unfortunately, these findings could not be conveyed to the investigated *cis*-pinonic acid containing particles, most likely due to inexpedient experimental conditions concerning generation of the *cis*-pinonic acid containing particles in the laboratory, which were not taken properly into account in the interpretation of the results. As *cis*-pinonic acid is a compound of great atmospheric relevance, a number of future investigations are contemplated to improve control and understanding of the laboratory experiments involving *cis*-pinonic acid containing particles and resolve the potentially important influence of *cis*-pinonic acid surfactant properties and partitioning on cloud droplet activation.

The four organic compounds investigated all proved to be efficient sources of aerosol particle cloud condensation nuclei properties, albeit not as distinctly as the inorganic salts.

Preface

This thesis describes the work I have done during my M.Sc. studies at the University of Copenhagen from September 2005 to September 2006. The project concerns the experimental measurement and theoretical description of cloud droplet activation for aerosol particles containing organic compounds and focuses on the effects of acid dissociation and surfactant partitioning on the cloud condensation nuclei properties of organic aerosol particles. Comparatively simple atmospherically relevant particle components and compositions were investigated to facilitate the comparison of theory and experiments.

The thesis consists of 6 chapters: A short introduction is given to aerosols and their role in cloud formation and global climate. Then the fundamental theory for determining cloud droplet nucleating properties of aerosol particles is described; to the uninitiated, this proved to be a rather intricate task, due in particular to unlike notation and the different approaches adopted by the various texts on the topics in question. The theory chapter is therefore somewhat more comprehensive than usual. The experimental chapter gives an account of the experimental setup and laboratory and data treatment procedures involved in obtaining the experimental results. A chapter is then devoted to each of the main topics. Chapter 4 deals with acid dissociation and the effects for the water activity of activating droplets and investigates the use of different water activity parameterizations in predicting cloud droplet activation. Chapter 5 deals with surfactant partitioning and the effects for the surface tension of activating droplets and investigates different ways of accounting for surfactant partitioning and surface tension in evaluation of cloud droplet activation. In chapter 6, a short summary and outlook is given.

The majority of the work described in this thesis has been carried out at the University of Copenhagen and all experiments were performed in the laboratory of the Aerosol Group, which is a part of the Aerosol, Physical and Organic Chemistry Group (APOC) at the Department of Chemistry, University of Copenhagen. I spent the period from January 8 to February 11, 2006, in Kuopio, Finland, visiting the group of Professor Ari Laaksonen at the Department of Physics, University of Kuopio, where I studied their unique model accounting for surfactant partitioning in the evaluation of cloud droplet activation properties of organic aerosols. In addition, I have participated in the summer school "Aerosol Formation and Growth" and the field course "Physics and Chemistry of Air Pollution and Their Effects", both at the Hyytiälä forest field station in Hyytiälä, Finland.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

The aim of this study has been to investigate the influence of organic component chemical properties on the ability of aerosol particles to form cloud droplets, with focus on the effects of dissociation of polyfunctional acids and partitioning of surface active agents in the growing droplets. This was accomplished through comparing laboratory measurements with model and other theoretical calculations of the cloud droplet formation properties for simple aerosol particles containing selected organic compounds.

1.1 Atmospheric Aerosols

{This and the following section are based on Seinfeld and Pandis [92] and Finlayson-Pitts and J.N. Pitts [30].}

An aerosol is defined as a suspension of solid or liquid particles in a gas [45, pp.3]; in an atmospheric aerosol, the particles are suspended in ambient air. Aerosol particles are ubiquitous in the atmosphere, from polluted industrial areas to the pristine arctic regions, but the particle numbers, sizes and compositions vary greatly on both spatial and temporal scales due to diverse sources and processes of transport and removal.

Sources of atmospheric aerosols may be natural or anthropogenic in origin, comprising both direct emissions and formation in the atmosphere by gas-to-particle conversion: Particles may for example be emitted directly to the atmosphere from sea spray, volcanos or automobile exhaust and are then called primary. Secondary particles form by either nucleation or condensation onto preexisting particles of gas-phase species in the atmosphere; these gaseous compounds are similarly emitted from both natural or anthropogenic sources, like photosynthesizing plants and trees, industrial processes or fires, or formed from such precursors by chemical reactions in the atmosphere.

Particles can be removed from the atmosphere by sedimentation, adsorption on surfaces or rain-out; the time scales involved in the various removal processes determine the residence times of particles in the atmosphere. The longer the aerosol particles remain suspended in the atmosphere, the farther they may be transported from their point of origin and the greater the number of atmospheric processes they may participate in.

1.2 Cloud Formation

Aerosol particles are crucial to the formation of clouds in the atmosphere; in the absence of aerosols, an atmospheric water content several times greater than the present would be required for cloud droplets to begin to form [109] and all naturally occurring cloud droplets therefore emerge by condensing of water onto airborne particles [84]. Particles that are able to nucleate formation of cloud droplets are accordingly called cloud condensation nuclei: This ability depends on both the physical and chemical properties given by the sizes and compositions of atmospheric aerosol particles and on the atmospheric conditions of temperature and water content.

Figure 1.1: Schematic representation of a typical size distribution with some formation and removal processes of atmospheric aerosol particles. Particles relevant for cloud formation appear in the accumulation mode of the fine particle fraction. Adapted from http://www.defra.gov.uk/ENVIRONMENT/airquality/aqs/air_measure/03.htm#fig2 (last accessed 18-09-2006).

To be relevant for cloud formation, aerosol particles must be large enough to act as cloud condensation nuclei and small enough to remain suspended in the atmosphere for sufficiently long to participate in the droplet forming processes. Such particles have diameters of roughly 10 nm to 1 μm and fall within the so-called accumulation mode of the atmospheric fine particle fraction (see fig. 1.1).

The chemical compositions of aerosol particles governing cloud condensation nuclei properties are far more complex to determine. Inorganic constituents like sea salt and

sulfates readily dissolve and dissociate in water condensing onto an aerosol particle and their role in cloud droplet formation is therefore reasonably well understood. On the other hand, the significance of organic aerosol components for cloud condensation nuclei properties has only been recognized fairly recently. The water solubilities of these organics vary widely, and upon dissolution in a droplet the compounds display diverse and often concentration dependent dissociation behavior as well as other solution effects, like lowering of the droplet surface tension. Such solution phenomena will affect the possibility of subsequent growth to form a cloud droplet, following the initial condensation of water by an aerosol particle. Overall, the influence of organic component chemical properties on various solution effects and droplet formation ability of organic aerosol particles is still not well-quantified and an area of exiting ongoing research.

1.3 Climate

{This section is based on Lohmann and Feichter [69] and Andreae et al. [9].}

Global climate is determined by the radiative balance of incoming solar and outgoing terrestrial radiation and the distribution of energy within the Earth system resulting from this equilibrium. Aerosols affect climate by scattering and absorption of both light and heat radiation, which is called the direct aerosol climate effect, and through the formation of clouds by acting as cloud condensation nuclei.

Clouds cover approximately 60% of the Earth at any given time and play an important role in regulating the radiation balance by scattering and absorbing incoming solar and outgoing terrestrial radiation, and in the distribution of water and heat in the Earth system through the hydrological cycle. Small changes in cloud micro- and macro-physical properties like the droplet size and the extent of cloud cover may thus have significant effects on climate.

Changes in aerosol properties have been found to alter clouds in a number of ways, perhaps most importantly through an increase in the number of cloud condensation nuclei. For a given cloud water content, the corresponding increase in cloud droplet number entails smaller individual droplets, which enhances reflection efficiency of solar radiation and suppresses formation of large rain drops and precipitation, thereby increasing cloud lifetime. These mechanisms are called the 1st and 2nd indirect aerosol climate effects, or the Twomey and Albrecht effects, respectively. The Twomey effect has been observed in ship tracks (see fig. 1.2) where particles in ship exhaust clearly enhance the reflectivity of clouds over the ocean by increasing the number of cloud condensation nuclei and droplets in the clouds.

Both the Twomey and Albrecht effects enhance the Earth albedo and thus decrease the amount of solar energy received; agreement exists on the assertion that this causes a net cooling effect on climate. The magnitude of the cooling effect due to changed cloud properties by aerosols and the resolution of contributions from different mechanisms is however highly uncertain, owing in particular to insufficient knowledge of

aerosol numbers and abilities to form cloud droplets resulting from compositions and chemical properties.

Figure 1.2: Ship tracks showing the Twomey or 1st indirect aerosol climate effect. The cloud reflectivity is enhanced due to an increased number of cloud droplets formed by the particles emitted in ship exhaust. Adapted from <http://www-das.uwyo.edu/~geerts/cwx/notes/-chap08/contrail.html> (last accessed 17-09-2006).

The IPCC Third Assessment Report [46] suggests, that the climate cooling effect from changes in cloud properties caused by anthropogenic aerosol emissions may potentially be of equal magnitude, but in opposing direction, as the warming effect from increased levels of greenhouse gases since preindustrial times (see fig. 1.3). However, the uncertainty involved with estimating the magnitude of the aerosol indirect effect is equally large. Reviewing modeling and estimates of global indirect aerosol effects, Lohmann and Feichter [69] conclude that "linking aerosol particles to cloud droplets is probably the weakest point in estimates of the indirect aerosol effects". Thus, the effect of aerosols on cloud formation and properties represent a major uncertainty in determining present anthropogenic perturbations to global climate.

Figure 1.3: The estimated magnitudes, the so-called climate forcings, and uncertainties of different mechanisms affecting global climate in a warmer or cooler direction. The cooling effect of changed cloud properties due to anthropogenic aerosol emissions, the aerosol indirect climate effect, is potentially of equal magnitude as the warming caused by increased greenhouse gas levels (far left), but highly uncertain. Adapted from Houghton et al. [46, pp.8].

The uncertainty in the magnitude of the combined anthropogenic influences on climate entails a corresponding uncertainty in the climate sensitivity, which is a measure of "how strongly Earth's climate system responds to a given perturbation" [9]. This in turn affects the projections of climate change resulting from a change in the relative contributions of the effects of different climate affecting mechanisms. The anthropogenic aerosol emissions are expected to decline in the future due to regulatory efforts following the recognition of serious aerosol effects on human health, which will affect the relative magnitudes of climate perturbations from aerosols and greenhouse gases due to the much longer atmospheric residence time of the greenhouse gases compared to aerosol particles. Andreae et al. [9] then point out, that any present cooling effect from aerosols will mask the true climate warming potential of the increased greenhouse gas levels, and that if the present magnitude of aerosol cooling is sufficiently large, future climate change may exceed the current upper estimates of the IPCC Third Assessment Report.

An understanding of the cloud forming properties of atmospheric aerosols is therefore essential for understanding the present magnitude of the anthropogenic indirect aerosol climate effect and for making more precise projections of future climate change, which is highly relevant in respect to the current national and international debate concerning the needs for taking appropriate measures to avoid dramatic future changes of climate

and human living conditions. An improved characterization aerosol cloud forming abilities in turn requires increased knowledge of aerosol chemical properties, in particular pertaining to organic components, which pose the greatest uncertainty in determining the cloud condensation nuclei properties of atmospheric aerosol particles.

Chapter 2

Theory

In this chapter, the central theoretical concepts and some of their interrelations utilized for this work are presented within the underlying framework of thermodynamics.

2.1 Basic Concepts

The fundamental thermodynamic concepts in this work are those of phase, equilibrium, chemical potential and vapor pressure of a substance, which shall be introduced here.

2.1.1 Phase

The thermodynamic properties of matter can be discerned as extensive properties like volume and energy, which depend on the amount of matter present, and intensive properties like pressure and temperature that are independent of the size of a system [104, pp.20]. A phase can then be defined as a region of space where all the intensive properties of matter varies continuously, and which is bound by a surface of discontinuity in at least one of these variables or its derivatives [13, pp.547]. The phases encountered in this work are those of solid, liquid, vapor and aqueous solution; the latter can be regarded as comprising a bulk and a surface phase, respectively [80, pp.12.1].

A phase transition is a process that brings a substance from one phase to another [13, pp.547]. The distribution of a substance between its attainable phases is referred to as partitioning [92, pp.736]. Here, partitioning is primarily used to describe the distribution of a surfactant between the bulk and surface phases of an aqueous solution droplet [97].

2.1.2 Chemical Potential

The chemical potential μ_i of a substance i in a single phase mixture is defined as the partial molar Gibbs free energy of the mixture with respect to that particular substance [11, pp.166],[86, pp.24]

$$\mu_i \equiv \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial n_i} \right)_{p, T, n_{j \neq i}} \quad (2.1)$$

where G is the Gibbs free energy of the mixture, n_i is the amount in moles of substance i and the partial derivative is taken for the pressure p and temperature T of the system, as well as the amounts in moles of all other substances in the mixture $n_{j \neq i}$, kept constant. Thus, the chemical potential μ_i gives the composition dependency of the Gibbs free energy G of the mixture in terms of substance i .

The relation between the chemical potentials μ_i, μ_j, \dots of the different components i, j, \dots in a system is given by the Gibbs-Duhem equation [104, pp.148], [11, pp.168] which for constant temperature and pressure states

$$\sum_k n_k d\mu_k = 0 \quad (2.2)$$

2.1.3 Equilibrium

Equilibrium conditions for a system can be derived [13, pp.682-684], [92, pp.495-498], [83, pp.103], [11, pp.105,145,216] from the Second Law of thermodynamics, which implies that for a spontaneous change taking place in an isolated system, the corresponding change in the entropy S of the system must be $(\delta S)_{U,V,n_i} \geq 0$. For a system comprising components i, j, \dots distributed on phases α, β, \dots this leads to the following constraints on temperature T , pressure p and composition n_i, n_j, \dots

$$T^\alpha = T^\beta \quad (2.3)$$

$$p^\alpha = p^\beta \quad (2.4)$$

$$\mu_i^\alpha = \mu_i^\beta \quad (2.5)$$

$$\sum_k \nu_k \mu_k = 0 \quad (2.6)$$

for thermal, mechanical, chemical phase and chemical reaction equilibrium, respectively. 2.6 refers to a single reaction between species i, j, \dots with stoichiometric coefficients ν_i, ν_j, \dots .

This work deals with equilibrium properties and changes taking place at equilibrium conditions of the systems in question; therefore, the conditions 2.3, 2.4, 2.5 and 2.6 are generally assumed to be met. The various systems are all studied at ambient conditions, so that thermal and mechanical equilibrium is implied and considerations focus on the consequences of chemical equilibrium.

2.1.4 Vapor Pressure

When a single component gas exists in equilibrium with its corresponding liquid, the pressure p of the two phases must be the same according to 2.4, and this pressure is known as the vapor pressure of the substance [11, pp.142]. Sometimes the equilibrium condition is emphasized by referring to the equilibrium [112, pp.804] or saturation [83, pp.110], [92, pp.546] vapor pressure, but these equivalent designations are implied in

the definition of the vapor pressure p .

For a mixture of gases present at pressure p , the partial pressure p_i of component i can be defined [11, pp.22], [49, pp.652] as

$$p_i \equiv y_i p \quad (2.7)$$

where y_i is the mole fraction of component i in the gas phase, the ratio of the amount in moles n_i of component i to the total amount in moles of substance in the gas mixture

$$y_i \equiv \frac{n_i}{\sum_j n_j} \quad (2.8)$$

If the gas phase is thus a mixture of components, the partial pressure p_i of the component i in equilibrium with its liquid phase is accordingly the partial vapor pressure of the particular substance [11, pp.148]. Often, the designation "partial" is omitted, since at atmospheric conditions the gas phase is always a mixture of compounds.

The vapor pressure p of a single component system is a function only of temperature, with the temperature dependence given by the Clausius-Clapeyron equation [13, pp.866]. On the other hand, the partial vapor pressure p_i of a component i in a gas phase mixture in equilibrium with its corresponding liquid depends on the overall pressure p according to the Poynting equation [13, pp.831], as well as on the temperature.

2.2 Aqueous Solutions

Cloud droplets are essentially aqueous solution systems formed in the atmosphere. An aqueous solution can be considered a liquid mixture of components formally discerned as water (w) and solute (s). Besides the solution bulk, both water and solute may be present in other phases too, such as the vapor phase, the droplet surface phase or a solid phase imbedded in the droplet solution. For the greater part of this work, the solutes studied are assumed to have negligible vapor pressures and sufficiently high water solubilities that they are found in neither the vapor nor the solid phase. However, in chapter 5 limited water solubility will need to be considered. As experiments were carried out in a laboratory at ambient temperatures around 298 K, water is only considered present in its liquid and vapor phases. Considerations are therefore confined to the partitioning of water between the liquid droplet and vapor phases and how this is affected by the behavior of the solute in the droplet solution as well as its partitioning between the solid, droplet bulk and surface phases. Water is denoted by w and v in its liquid and vapor form, and emphasis on the nature of liquid and gas phases themselves is given by superscripts l and g .

2.2.1 Water

Being the solvent, water in an aqueous solution is present in excess, and the solution composition is thus most conveniently expressed in terms of water using its mole fraction

$$x_w \equiv \frac{n_w}{n_w + n_s} \quad (2.9)$$

Here, n_w and n_s are the amounts in moles of water w and solute s , respectively.

The chemical potential of water in a solution at given conditions of temperature T , pressure p and composition x_w can be formulated as [81, pp.508], [13, pp.905]

$$\mu_w^l(T, p, x_w) = \mu_w^{l,0}(T, p) + RT \ln(a_w(x_w)) \quad (2.10)$$

where $\mu_w^{l,0}(T, p)$ is the chemical potential of pure liquid (indicated by the superscript 0) water at the same temperature and pressure. 2.10 defines the (rational) activity $a_w(x_w)$ of water in the solution, which can be expressed as an explicit function of composition by the mole fraction x_w

$$a_w(x_w) = \gamma_w(x_w)x_w \quad (2.11)$$

This relation defines the (rational) activity coefficient $\gamma_w(x_w)$ of water in the solution [83, pp.109], [86, pp.27]. It is evident that both the water activity a_w and the water activity coefficient γ_w are functions of the solution composition through the water mole fraction x_w . The term "rational" refers to the specific use of the mole fraction scale for expressing the amount of water in solution.

For pure water $x_w = 1$ and $\mu_w^l(T, p, x_w = 1) = \mu_w^{l,0}(T, p)$ by definition, so from 2.10, this entails

$$a_w(x_w = 1) = 1, \gamma_w(x_w = 1) = 1 \quad (2.12)$$

The definition of the water chemical potential is such that for water in an actual solution [104, pp.362], [11, pp.183], [92, pp.504]

$$\begin{aligned} a_w(x_w) &\longrightarrow x_w & \text{for } x_w &\longrightarrow 1 \\ \gamma_w(x_w) &\longrightarrow 1 & \text{for } x_w &\longrightarrow 1 \end{aligned} \quad (2.13)$$

Due to this limiting behavior, a_w and γ_w must be dimensionless quantities like x_w .

2.2.2 Solute

Water is an ionizing solvent [86, pp.1], whence solutes in aqueous solutions can be divided into electrolytes and non-electrolytes, respectively.

Electrolytes MX dissociate into ions upon dissolution

Here, ν_M and ν_X denote the number of positively and negatively charged ions in one formula unit of MX , just as z_M and z_X give the charge numbers of the positive and negative ions, respectively.

Non-electrolytes AB remain in assembly when dissolved in water

The amount of solute present in solution is commonly expressed on several different concentration scales. For a single non-electrolyte solute component s , the amount in moles of solute in solution n_s relative to the total amount in moles of substance present is given by the solute mole fraction

$$x_s \equiv \frac{n_s}{n_w + n_s} \quad (2.16)$$

From 2.9 and 2.16, $x_s + x_w = 1$ by definition. In the case of an electrolyte, n_s is replaced by $\nu_s n_s$ in both 2.9 and 2.16 [86, pp.31-32], [81, pp.518,519]

$$x_s \equiv \frac{\nu_s n_s}{n_w + \nu_s n_s}, \quad x_w \equiv \frac{n_w}{n_w + \nu_s n_s} \quad (2.17)$$

where n_s denotes the original amount in moles of solute before dissociation and ν_s is the overall number of species generated in solution per formula unit of solute s upon dissolution, comprising the total of ions as well as any remaining undissociated compound; if the dissociation is complete according to 2.14, $\nu_s = \nu_M + \nu_X$, else $\nu_s < \nu_M + \nu_X$. From the definition 2.17, the relation $x_s + x_w = 1$ is retained. In the general case of several electrolyte solutes s_i, s_j, \dots present in solution, the mole fractions of water and each solute become

$$x_{s_i} \equiv \frac{\nu_{s_i} n_{s_i}}{n_w + \sum_k \nu_{s_k} n_{s_k}}, \quad x_w \equiv \frac{n_w}{n_w + \sum_k \nu_{s_k} n_{s_k}}, \quad x_w + \sum_k x_{s_k} = 1 \quad (2.18)$$

when the respective solutes dissociate to each produce an overall of $\nu_{s_i}, \nu_{s_j}, \dots$ species in solution.

The molal concentration of solute b_s gives the amount of solute in moles n_s per 1000 g of solvent, and the molar concentration c_s is the amount of solute in moles n_s per 1 dm³ of solution [81, pp.509]. Again, for electrolytes, $\nu_s n_s$ is used in place of n_s when dissociation is considered, so the total concentration in solution becomes $\nu_s b_s$ and $\nu_s c_s$ for the respective concentrations b_s and c_s of the electrolyte as a whole [104, pp.509]. For multiple solute species s_i, s_j, \dots , the molar c_{s_i}, c_{s_j}, \dots and molal b_{s_i}, b_{s_j}, \dots concentrations are attributed to each solute accordingly.

In expressing the chemical potential $\mu_s^l(T, p, [s])$ of the solute at specific conditions of temperature T , pressure p and solution composition in terms of solute $[s]$, any of the above concentration scales can be used for $[s]$ [86, pp.26]

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_s^l(T, p, [s]) &= \mu_s^{l,\dagger}(T, p, x^\dagger) + RT \ln(a_s^x(x_s)) \\ &= \mu_s^{l,\dagger}(T, p, b^\dagger) + RT \ln(a_s^b(b_s)) \\ &= \mu_s^{l,\dagger}(T, p, c^\dagger) + RT \ln(a_s^c(c_s)) \end{aligned} \quad (2.19)$$

2.19 define three different activities of the solute in solution, the rational $a_s^x(x_s)$, the molal $a_s^b(b_s)$ and the molar $a_s^c(c_s)$ activity [86, pp.27]. The solute activities can be expressed as explicit functions of solution composition on the respective solute concentration scales by

$$a_s^x(x_s) = \gamma_s^x(x_s) x_s \quad (2.20)$$

$$a_s^b(b_s) = \gamma_s^b(b_s)b_s \quad (2.21)$$

$$a_s^c(c_s) = \gamma_s^c(c_s)c_s \quad (2.22)$$

These relations define the rational $\gamma_s^x(x_s)$, molal $\gamma_s^b(b_s)$ and molar $\gamma_s^c(c_s)$ activity coefficients of the solute [86, pp.27].

The chemical potential $\mu_s^l(T, p, [s])$ of the solute in a given actual solution state is unique [86, pp.26], but has in 2.19 been resolved on the basis of different reference states $\mu_s^{l,\ddagger}(T, p, x^\ddagger)$, $\mu_s^{l,\ddagger}(T, p, b^\ddagger)$ and $\mu_s^{l,\ddagger}(T, p, c^\ddagger)$. These reference states are solutions of standard unity concentration [81, pp.509-510], [11, pp.185]

$$x^\ddagger = 1, b^\ddagger = 1 \text{ mol/kg}, c^\ddagger = 1 \text{ mol/dm}^3 \quad (2.23)$$

defined, such that for the actual solutions at all temperatures and pressures [86, pp.28], [81, pp.509-510], [11, pp.184,186]

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_s^x(x_s) &\longrightarrow 1, a_s^x(x_s) \longrightarrow x_s && \text{for } x_s \longrightarrow 0 \\ \gamma_s^b(b_s) &\longrightarrow 1, a_s^b(b_s) \longrightarrow b_s && \text{for } b_s \longrightarrow 0 \\ \gamma_s^c(c_s) &\longrightarrow 1, a_s^c(c_s) \longrightarrow c_s && \text{for } c_s \longrightarrow 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2.24)$$

By definition then, in either reference state [86, pp.28-29], [81, pp.510]

$$\begin{aligned} a_s^x(x_s = 1) &= a_s^b(b_s = 1) = a_s^c(c_s = 1) = 1 \\ \gamma_s^x(x_s = 1) &= \gamma_s^b(b_s = 1) = \gamma_s^c(c_s = 1) = 1 \end{aligned} \quad (2.25)$$

Physically, the reference states can be perceived of as hypothetical solutions in which all molecular interactions experienced by the solute are equal to those between the solute and the solvent [13, pp.906-907], and with a chemical composition corresponding to unity solute concentration on the respective scales. The solute reference state chemical potentials $\mu_s^{l,\ddagger}(T, p, x^\ddagger)$, $\mu_s^{l,\ddagger}(T, p, b^\ddagger)$ and $\mu_s^{l,\ddagger}(T, p, c^\ddagger)$ consequently depend on the nature of both the solute and the solvent, in this case water, [13, pp.906], [81, pp.509] and must have different values for a given solute due to the different solution compositions. This means that the numerical values of the solute activities and activity coefficients will differ as well for a given actual solution state [81, pp.510], [49, pp.659].

The different solute activities and activity coefficients depend on the solution composition through the solute concentration given on the different scales. From 2.24, the activities a_s^b and a_s^c have dimensions mol/kg and mol/dm³, whereas a_s^x and the activity coefficients γ_s^x , γ_s^b and γ_s^c are dimensionless. Therefore, to avoid the problems of using dimensional quantities as argument in the logarithms in 2.19, the molal and molar solute activities can be interpreted as reduced by the corresponding reference unity concentration b^\ddagger and c^\ddagger . This practice follows that of [11, pp.185-186].

The reference states need not be physically realizable, only to have well-defined properties [81, pp.510]. The reason for resolving the chemical potential in contributions from a reference and the actual state is that the equation of state is not formally known for

the condensed phases [13, pp. 902].

A rigid treatment of electrolyte solutes require some modifications to the above in order to preserve similar limiting properties and retain experimental grounding of the quantities in question [81, pp.513-516], [86, pp.26-29], [13, pp. 972-974]. Imposing the condition of electroneutrality [81, pp.513] on the electrolyte solution, mean ionic quantities $b_{\pm}, a_{\pm}, \gamma_{\pm}$ for a fully dissociated electrolyte according to 2.14 can be defined [81, pp.514]. The chemical potentials for fully dissociated electrolytes can then be formulated in terms of these mean ionic quantities with reference states of unity individual ionic concentrations $\nu_M b_{MX} = \nu_X b_{MX} = 1$ [86, pp.27], [81, pp.513], assuring that for real solutions [81, pp.516]

$$\gamma_{\pm}^b \longrightarrow 1, a_{\pm}^b \longrightarrow b_{\pm} \quad \text{for} \quad b_{\pm} \longrightarrow 0 \quad (2.26)$$

2.2.3 Ideal and Real Solutions

An ideal solution is defined such that the activity coefficient $\gamma_i = 1$ for all solution components i [81, pp.219], [92, pp.504]. This entails for an ideal aqueous solution

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_w &= \gamma_s^x = \gamma_s^b = \gamma_s^c = 1 \\ a_w &= x_w, a_s^x = x_s, a_s^b = b_s, a_s^c = c_s \end{aligned} \quad (2.27)$$

Solution ideality thus depends on the choice of reference states for the chemical potentials of solvent and solute [81, pp.214], and with the definitions in 2.10 and 2.19 a solution with the properties 2.27 is denoted ideal-dilute [81, pp.222], [11, pp.173]. The ideal solution can be perceived as an idealized system in which solvent and solute are both subject to interactions identical to those of their respective reference states [13, pp.902-903].

The chemical potentials of water and solute in an ideal aqueous solution are consequently

$$\mu_w^l(T, p, x_w) = \mu_w^{l,0}(T, p) + RT \ln(x_w) \quad (2.28)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_s^l(T, p, [s]) &= \mu_s^{l,\ddagger}(T, p, x^{\ddagger}) + RT \ln(x_s) \\ &= \mu_s^{l,\dagger}(T, p, b^{\dagger}) + RT \ln(b_s) \\ &= \mu_s^{l,\dagger}(T, p, c^{\dagger}) + RT \ln(c_s) \end{aligned} \quad (2.29)$$

The expressions for the chemical potentials given by 2.28 and 2.29 can conversely be employed to define solution ideality [11, pp.172-173], [49, pp.658].

In real solutions, intermolecular interactions deviate from the idealized behavior of the solvent and solute reference states. The chemical potentials for water and solute in a real aqueous solution can be expressed according to 2.11, 2.20, 2.21 and 2.22 as

$$\mu_w^l(T, p, x_w) = \mu_w^{l,0}(T, p) + RT \ln(x_w) + RT \ln(\gamma_w) \quad (2.30)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mu_s^l(T, p, [s]) &= \mu_s^{l,\ddagger}(T, p, x^\ddagger) + RT \ln(x_s) + RT \ln(\gamma_s^x) \\
&= \mu_s^{l,\ddagger}(T, p, b^\ddagger) + RT \ln(b_s) + RT \ln(\gamma_s^b) \\
&= \mu_s^{l,\ddagger}(T, p, c^\ddagger) + RT \ln(c_s) + RT \ln(\gamma_s^c)
\end{aligned}
\tag{2.31}$$

Comparison of 2.28, 2.29, 2.30 and 2.31 show, that all deviations from ideal behavior in a real aqueous solution are expressed through the activity coefficients [11, pp.184]. Real solutions approach ideal behavior $\gamma_w, \gamma_s^x, \gamma_s^b, \gamma_s^c \rightarrow 1$ as $x_w \rightarrow 1$ and $x_s, b_s, c_s \rightarrow 0$ by definition. Non-ideality can generally result in activity coefficients both larger or smaller than unity [81, pp.515].

Accounting for the intermolecular interactions leading to solution non-ideality, and thereby predicting activity coefficients for water and solute analytically, is rather complicated and is treated for electrolytes by [86]. For water, contributions to non-ideal interactions arise from differences between water and solute molecular energy levels, sizes, shapes, permanent electrical dipole and quadrupole moments, polarizabilities, van der Waals interactions and hydrogen bonding properties. In solutions of finite dilution there is moreover a finite separation of solute molecules, so in real solutions the solute molecules will interact with each other as well as with water molecules, which causes deviations on behalf of the solute from ideal solution behavior. This is particularly the case for electrolyte solutions, since the Coulomb fields set up by the ionic charges have very long ranges compared to other intermolecular interactions.

In dilute electrolyte solutions, of solute molalities less than about 0.1 mol/kg, the variation of the mean ionic activity coefficient γ_{\pm} with solute concentration can be evaluated from the extended Debye-Hückel law [11, pp.253],[104, pp.525]. Alternatively, the activity coefficients can be regarded as empirical quantities to be determined from experiments [49, pp.658].

This work concerns the properties of water in aqueous solution droplets and so the focus is mainly the activity of water a_w in terms of how this quantity is affected by the presence of the solute, contrary to explicitly describing the actual state of the solute in solution. However, the activities and activity coefficients of water and solute are interrelated through the Gibbs-Duhem equation 2.2 [81, pp.222].

2.2.4 The Raoult Effect

Like liquids, gases can also be discerned as either real or ideal. Here, an ideal gas is defined as one that obeys the ideal gas law [11, pp.19]

$$pV = nRT \tag{2.32}$$

for the relation between the pressure p and temperature T of the gas and its volume V for a given amount of substance n . If the gas is a mixture, each component i must obey the ideal gas law individually

$$p_i V = n_i R T \tag{2.33}$$

The chemical potential of water vapor v can be given as [13, pp.751], [11, 133]

$$\mu_v^g(T, p, y_v) = \mu_v^{g,*}(T, p^*) + RT \ln \left(\frac{f_v(y_v)}{p^*} \right) \quad (2.34)$$

The quantity $f_v(y_v)$ is the fugacity of the water vapor, which has dimensions of pressure and is related to the water vapor pressure p_v by the property [13, pp.751], [11, 134]

$$f_v(y_v) \longrightarrow p_v(y_v) \quad \text{for } p \longrightarrow 0 \quad (2.35)$$

A functional form of the fugacity is given in Berry et al. [13, pp.750]. As reference state for the water vapor chemical potential $\mu_v^{g,*}(T, p^*)$ is chosen that of pure water vapor $y_v = 1$ behaving ideally according to 2.32 at standard pressure $p^* = 1$ bar (denoted by *).

For water vapor v in equilibrium with liquid water w in an aqueous solution, condition 2.5 yields

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_v^g(T, p, y_v) = \mu_w^l(T, p, x_w) &\Rightarrow \\ \mu_v^{g,*}(T, p^*) + RT \ln \left(\frac{f_v(y_v)}{p^*} \right) &= \mu_w^{l,0}(T, p) + RT \ln(a_w(x_w)) \end{aligned} \quad (2.36)$$

Comparing this expression with the corresponding one for water vapor in equilibrium with pure water, obtained by noting that $a_w = x_w = 1$ and substituting the relevant fugacity $f_v^0(y_v^0)$, one can derive [83, pp.109-110], [13, 910-911]

$$a_w = \frac{f_v}{f_v^0} \quad (2.37)$$

Arguing that the vapor pressures p_v and p_v^0 of water in solution and pure form, respectively, are of comparable size and therefore require similar correction factors to obtain the corresponding fugacities f_v and f_v^0 2.37 can be approximated [86, pp.25], [92, pp.783]

$$a_w = \frac{p_v}{p_v^0} \quad (2.38)$$

Alternatively, one can argue that at ambient conditions, pressures are sufficiently low that the vapor behaves ideally $f \simeq p$ [13, 911], [83, 107]. Relation 2.38 states the water activity of an aqueous solution a_w in terms of the fractional relation between the water vapor pressures over the solution p_v and over pure liquid water p_v^0 . On the other hand, equation 2.38 gives the reduction in water vapor pressure p_v due to the presence of the solute in the aqueous phase relative to the water vapor pressure of pure liquid water p_v^0 as the value of the aqueous solution water activity a_w .

If water behaves ideally, the aqueous solution water activity equals the mole fraction of water $a_w = x_w$ and Raoult's law [83, pp.110], [13, pp.911] is recovered from 2.38

$$x_w = \frac{p_v}{p_v^0} \quad (2.39)$$

Thus, equation 2.38 gives the extension of Raoult's law for real aqueous solutions; reduction of the solution water vapor pressure due to presence of the solute is therefore called the Raoult effect.

The fractional relation of the equilibrium water vapor pressure p_v to that of pure water p_v^0 defines the water saturation ratio [92, pp.545]

$$s \equiv \frac{p_v}{p_v^0}, S \equiv \frac{p_v}{p_v^0} \cdot 100\% \quad (2.40)$$

For water vapor, the saturation percentage S is called the relative humidity [92, pp.20]

$$RH = \frac{p_v}{p_v^0} \cdot 100\% \quad (2.41)$$

When $p_v = p_v^0 \Rightarrow RH = 100\%$ the gas phase is saturated with water vapor; correspondingly, the relative humidity ranges $RH < 100\%$ and $RH > 100\%$ are referred to as sub- and supersaturated conditions [92, pp.546], respectively.

2.2.5 Parameterizations of Water Activity

The reduction in solvent vapor pressure of a solution due to the presence of a non-volatile solute, as expressed for water in 2.38, causes the observed phenomena of freezing point depression, boiling point elevation and osmotic pressure [112, pp.844], [49, pp.661], [13, pp.924]. These are collectively called the colligative properties of the solution because, in their limiting form for ideal and dilute non-electrolyte solutions, their observed magnitudes depend only on the amount of solute present in solution, not on the specific nature of the solute, and the various phenomena can therefore be grouped together on this basis. More precisely, the solvent vapor pressure reduction is a manifestation of a reduction in solvent chemical potential, or activity, by the presence of the solute, which is the fundamental thermodynamic cause of the observed properties. Thus, the colligative properties of an aqueous solution can be used as measures of the solution water activity [101, pp.210,213].

Osmotic Pressure

By far the most sensitive [49, pp.667], [101, pp.211], [86, pp.206] of the colligative properties to variations in the amount of solute is the osmotic pressure π [106, pp.540-543], which can be explained as the hydrostatic or externally applied pressure difference of a solution, needed to equilibrate the solvent in the solution when in contact with its pure phase over a semipermeable membrane, across which only the solvent can pass (an ideal semipermeable membrane [59]).

The condition for equilibrium between water w in an aqueous solution (sol) and its pure form (pur) is from 2.5

$$\mu_w^{sol}(T^{sol}, p^{sol}) = \mu_w^{pur}(T^{pur}, p^{pur}) \quad (2.42)$$

If the water activity in solution $a_w^{sol} \neq 1$, the chemical potentials μ_w^{sol} and μ_w^{pur} cannot be equal at the same temperature and pressure, according to 2.10. A temperature difference cannot be sustained across the membrane [106, pp.541], so thermal equilibrium of water in the solution and pure phase gives $T^{sol} = T^{pure} = T$. If the membrane can support a pressure difference, mechanical equilibrium can be achieved at $p_w(p + \pi) = p_w^0(p)$, where $p_w(p + \pi)$ is the partial vapor pressure of water over the solution at pressure $p^{sol} = p + \pi$ and $p_w^0(p)$ is the partial vapor pressure of pure water at pressure $p^{pur} = p$. An additional pressure π must thus be applied to the solution, to increase the partial vapor pressure of water according to the Poynting equation [13, pp.831] in response to the water vapor pressure reduction due to the solute as given by 2.38. Re-formulation of 2.42 [101, pp.213], [81, pp.511], [59] yields

$$\begin{aligned}
\mu_w^{sol}(T, p + \pi) &= \mu_w^{pur}(T, p) \Rightarrow \\
\mu_w^{sol}(T, p) + \int_p^{p+\pi} \left(\frac{\partial \mu_w^{sol}(T, p')}{\partial p'} \right)_T dp' &= \mu_w^0(T, p) \Rightarrow \\
\mu_w^{sol}(T, p) + \int_p^{p+\pi} v_w dp' &= \mu_w^0(T, p) \Rightarrow \tag{2.43} \\
\mu_w^0(T, p) + RT \ln(a_w) + v_w \pi &= \mu_w^0(T, p) \Rightarrow \\
\pi &= \frac{-RT}{v_w} \ln(a_w)
\end{aligned}$$

Here, the relation $\mu_w^{sol}(T, p) = \mu_w^0(T, p) + RT \ln(a_w)$ given by definition 2.10 has been substituted, where $\mu_w^0(T, p)$ is the chemical potential of pure water at conditions T and p and a_w is the solution water activity. The pressure variation of the water chemical potential in the solution is substituted, assuming the derivative is invariant with the order of differentiation, by [106, pp.541]

$$\left(\frac{\partial \mu_w(T, p)}{\partial p} \right)_T = \frac{\partial}{\partial p} \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial n_w} \right)_{T, p, n_s} = \frac{\partial}{\partial n_w} \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial p} \right)_{T, n_s, n_w} = \frac{\partial}{\partial n_w} V = v_w \tag{2.44}$$

where

$$\left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial p} \right)_{T, n_s, n_w} = V \tag{2.45}$$

yields the solution volume V [11, pp.128], and the derivative

$$\left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial n_w} \right)_{T, p, n_s} = v_w \tag{2.46}$$

is by definition the partial molar volume of water v_w in the solution [13, pp.909]. It has been assumed in 2.43 that v_w is constant over the pressure range of integration. Equation 2.43 shows explicitly, how the osmotic pressure π of an aqueous solution is a direct measure of the solution water activity a_w [101, pp.213].

For an ideal solution $a_w = x_w = 1 - x_s$, and 2.43 can be approximated for a non-electrolyte solute as [49, pp.666], [112, pp.848], [81, pp.98]

$$\pi = \frac{-RT}{v_w} \ln(1 - x_s) \simeq \frac{-RT}{v_w} (-x_s) = \frac{RT n_s}{v_w (n_s + n_w)} \simeq \frac{RT n_s}{v_w n_w} \simeq c_s RT \tag{2.47}$$

assuming the solution is very dilute, so that $x_s \ll 1 \Rightarrow \ln(1 - x_s) \simeq -x_s$, $n_s + n_w \simeq n_w$ and the solution volume $V = V_w = v_w n_w$, whereby the solute molar concentration $c_s = n_s/V$ is recovered. Equation 2.47 is the van't Hoff limiting law for the osmotic pressure [101, pp.214] and states that for an ideal and dilute solution, the osmotic pressure of the solution depends only on the solute concentration c_s at a given temperature T . If in 2.47 the mass m_w and mass density ρ_w of water is used, where $m_w \rho_w = v_w n_w$, an expression in the molal solute concentration $b_s = n_s/m_w$ is obtained

$$\pi = \frac{b_s}{\rho_w} RT \quad (2.48)$$

For ideal and dilute electrolyte solutions, van't Hoff's equation is obtained by identical arguments, assuming $\nu_s n_s + n_w \simeq n_w$, as

$$\pi = \nu_s c_s RT = \frac{\nu_s b_s}{\rho_w} RT \quad (2.49)$$

where ν_s is the overall number of solute species in solution generated by dissociation for each formula unit of the original solute s ; for infinite dilution, the dissociation is complete and $\nu_s = \nu_M + \nu_X$ in 2.14.

The van't Hoff Factor

In solutions of finite dilution, the dissociation of electrolytes proceeds to a finite extent, which depends on the electrolyte concentration. To account for the concentration dependent extent of dissociation, along with classical electrostatic effects of ion pairing in solution [112, pp.852], the van't Hoff factor i_s of the solute was introduced into the expression for the osmotic pressure [83, pp.110], [112, pp.853]

$$\pi = i_s c_s RT = \frac{i_s b_s}{\rho_w} RT \quad (2.50)$$

Zumdahl [112, pp.852] expresses the van't Hoff factor i_s as the ratio of the amount in moles of solute species actually in solution to the amount in moles of solute originally dissolved. This can be realized by comparison of 2.47, 2.48, 2.49 and 2.50. In an ideal solution with no electrostatic interactions between ions, $i_s = \nu_s$, and in an ideal and infinitely dilute solution with complete dissociation $i_s = \nu_s = \nu_M + \nu_X$.

McDonald [72] apply the van't Hoff factor i_s for an electrolyte s in an extension of Raoult's law 2.39 to real electrolyte solutions

$$\frac{p_w - p_w^0}{p_w^0} = -\frac{i_s n_s}{n_w + i_s n_s} \quad (2.51)$$

where p_w and p_w^0 are the vapor pressures of water over the solution and pure water, respectively, and n_w and n_s are the amount in moles of water and originally dissolved electrolyte in solution. Like this, the righthand side of 2.51 can be interpreted as (the

negative of) an effective mole fraction for the electrolyte, and rearranging yields [83, pp.110], [61], [89]

$$\frac{p_w}{p_w^0} - 1 = -\frac{i_s n_s}{n_w + i_s n_s} \Rightarrow \frac{p_w}{p_w^0} = 1 - \frac{i_s n_s}{n_w + i_s n_s} \stackrel{(2.38)}{\Rightarrow} a_w = \frac{n_w}{n_w + i_s n_s} \quad (2.52)$$

The water activity a_w of a real solution has thus been expressed as an effective mole fraction of water in the solution, parameterized in terms of the van't Hoff factor of the solute. In this context, the van't Hoff factor i_s can therefore be regarded as accounting for all non-ideal solution effects; due to the connection between the water and solute properties through the Gibbs-Duhem equation 2.2, it does not seem unreasonable to incorporate all deviations from ideality into a property attributed solely to the solute. This interpretation of the van't Hoff factor is adopted in this work, in agreement with the application of the van't Hoff factor as a fitting parameter for the water activity in the description of experimentally determined quantities, which innately reflect the actual state of solutions.

An extension of 2.52 to a solution with several solutes $s_i, s_j, ..$ would according to 2.18 and 2.51 be

$$a_w = \frac{n_w}{n_w + \sum_k i_{s_k} n_{s_k}} \quad (2.53)$$

where $i_{s_i}, i_{s_j}, ..$ are the van't Hoff factors attributed to each of the originally undissolved solute species.

Osmolality

The osmolarity and the corresponding osmolality of a solution are defined as the concentrations obtained from an empirically determined osmotic pressure using the van't Hoff limiting law for a non-electrolyte with molar (2.47) and molal (2.48) solute concentration, respectively [49, pp.667]. Since all the colligative properties share a mutual thermodynamic basis and are thus used to measure each other [59], osmolarity and osmolality can more generally be defined as the molarity or molality of an ideal aqueous non-electrolyte solution with the same magnitude of a particular colligative property as observed for the actual solution [59].

The dimensions of osmolarity and osmolality are osmoles [Osm] per solution volume in dm^3 and solvent mass in kg, respectively [96, pp. 474]. The osmole [96, pp.474] is a non-SI unit, and can from the definitions of osmolarity and osmolality be interpreted as measure of the number n_s^{osm} of osmotically active (i.e. "contributing to the osmotic pressure") species present in solution [57].

In this work only the osmolality scale b_{osm} is used.

The empirical definition of the osmolality has important consequences: Through 2.43, the osmotic pressure of an aqueous solution is an equivalent expression of the solution water activity. However, the measured osmotic pressure only accounts for the effect of

those solute species that cannot cross the semipermeable membrane between the solution and pure water [101, pp.216], [59]. Osmolalities used here are assumed to reflect osmotic pressures comprising all solute species present in solution and therefore relate directly to the solution water activity a_w . Because osmolality relates the actual state of a real solution to that of an ideal and dilute non-electrolyte solution, both the extent of dissociation and all non-ideal interactions are accounted for [57], and the osmolality concept is equally applicable to solutions of electrolytes and non-electrolytes alike. All solution effects are related solely to the solute molality b_s ; since the measured osmotic pressure is related to an expression for a single ideal solute, the solution osmolality provide a collective measure of the overall effect of the total solute concentration $b_{s_i} + b_{s_j} + \dots$ when several solutes s_i, s_j, \dots are present in the solution.

Considering the water activity of a real aqueous solution as an effective mole fraction of water in solution, analogously to 2.52, Kiss and Hansson [57] approximate the solution water activity a_w by a parameterization in the solution osmolality b_{osm} , probably by an argument like the following

$$a_w \simeq \frac{n_w}{n_w + n_s^{osm}} = \frac{\frac{n_w}{m_w}}{\frac{n_w}{m_w} + \frac{n_s^{osm}}{m_w}} = \frac{M_w^{-1}}{M_w^{-1} + b_{osm}} \quad (2.54)$$

m_w and M_w are the water mass and molar weight, and n_s^{osm} gives the number in osmoles of osmotically active species in solution.

Osmotic Coefficients

The ratio of the magnitude of a colligative property observed for a real solution (*real*) to that of an ideal solution (*ideal*) of the same solute concentration $[s]$ defines the osmotic coefficient [49, pp.659], [81, pp.512]

$$\phi \equiv \frac{\pi^{real}([s])}{\pi^{ideal}([s])} \stackrel{(2.43)}{=} \frac{\ln(a_w^{real}([s]))}{\ln(a_w^{ideal}([s]))} \quad (2.55)$$

The water activity in a real solution a_w^{real} is uniquely defined in 2.10. However, for an ideal solution, the value of the water activity a_w^{ideal} depends on the concentration scale used for the solute through the connection between water and solute chemical potentials in 2.2, since the reference states for the solute chemical potential employed for each concentration scale in 2.19 entail different definitions of solution ideality. The value of the osmotic coefficient ϕ thus depends on the concentration scale used for expressing the solution composition $[s]$.

In an ideal solution $a_w^{ideal} \stackrel{(2.27)}{=} x_w$, and the rational osmotic coefficient is thereby defined as [86, pp.29], [104, pp.510]

$$\phi^x = \frac{\ln(a_w^{real})}{\ln(a_w^{ideal})} = \frac{\ln(a_w)}{\ln(x_w)} \quad (2.56)$$

Through the Gibbs-Duhem equation, the water activity can be related to the solute

molal concentration b_s at constant temperature and pressure [81, pp.511] in a way that for an ideal solution, where the solute activity coefficient $\gamma_s^b = 1$, gives

$$\ln(a_w^{b \text{ ideal}}) = -\frac{M_w}{1000} b_s \quad (2.57)$$

The molal, or practical, osmotic coefficient is consequently defined as [86, pp.29], [83, pp.111], [104, pp.509]

$$\phi^b = \frac{\ln(a_w^{real})}{\ln(a_w^{b \text{ ideal}})} = \frac{\ln(a_w)}{-\frac{M_w}{1000} b_s} = -\frac{1000}{M_w b_s} \ln(a_w) \quad (2.58)$$

Here, M_w is the molar weight of water, given with the usual dimensions [g/mol].

For an ideal electrolyte solution, where n_s moles of dissolved solute dissociate into a total of $\nu_s n_s$ species in solution, the osmotic coefficients become [81, pp.516-517], [86, pp.29,31]

$$\phi^x = \frac{\ln(a_w)}{\ln(x_w)} \text{ with } x_w = \frac{n_w}{n_w + \nu_s n_s} \quad (2.59)$$

$$\phi^b = -\frac{1000}{M_w \nu_s b_s} \ln(a_w) \text{ with } \ln(a_w^{b \text{ ideal}}) = -\frac{M_w}{1000} \nu_s b_s \quad (2.60)$$

The extensions to solutions with several electrolytes s_i, s_j, \dots , dissociating into $\nu_{s_i}, \nu_{s_j}, \dots$ species, is achieved by applying 2.18 in 2.59 for the rational osmotic coefficient ϕ^x , and for the molal osmotic coefficient by [104, pp.509]

$$\phi^b = -\frac{1000}{M_w \sum_k \nu_{s_k} b_{s_k}} \ln(a_w) \quad (2.61)$$

Expression of solution deviation from ideality in terms of the osmotic coefficients ϕ^x and ϕ^b is completely equivalent to employing the activity coefficients [13, pp.929]. When the focus is on solvent properties in solution, the osmotic coefficients have the advantage that their numerical values are much more sensitive to variation in solute concentration than the value of the solvent activity coefficient [81, pp.512,519].

The osmotic coefficients can help visualize the empirical concepts of the solute van't Hoff factor i_s and the solution osmolality b_{osm} within the theoretical framework. For a solution with original concentration b_s of electrolyte s , which dissociates into $\nu_s n_s$ solute species, the solution osmolality $b_{osm}(b_s)$ can be related to the molal osmotic coefficient ϕ^b by

$$\phi^b \equiv \frac{\pi^{real}(b_s)}{\pi^{ideal}(b_s)} \stackrel{(2.48,2.49)}{=} \frac{b_{osm}(b_s)RT}{\nu_s b_s RT} \Rightarrow b_{osm}(b_s) = \phi^b \nu_s b_s \quad (2.62)$$

The van't Hoff factor i_s of the solute can be related to the rational osmotic coefficient ϕ^x as follows

$$\phi^x \equiv \frac{\ln(a_w^{x \text{ real}})}{\ln(a_w^{x \text{ ideal}})} \stackrel{(2.52,2.17)}{=} \frac{\ln\left(\frac{n_w}{n_w + i_s n_s}\right)}{\ln\left(\frac{n_w}{n_w + \nu_s n_s}\right)} = \frac{\ln\left(1 + \frac{i_s n_s}{n_w}\right)}{\ln\left(1 + \frac{\nu_s n_s}{n_w}\right)} \simeq \frac{i_s n_s}{\nu_s n_s} \Rightarrow i_s \simeq \phi^x \nu_s \quad (2.63)$$

Kreidenweis et al. [61] similarly relates the van't Hoff factor $i_s \simeq \phi^b \nu_s$, since the two osmotic coefficients have the same value to a first order approximation [86, pp.33].

For solutions of several solutes s_i, s_j, \dots with concentrations b_{s_i}, b_{s_j}, \dots , using 2.61 in 2.62 gives an expression for the osmolality as $b_{osm}(\sum_k b_{s_k}) = \phi^b \sum_k \nu_{s_k} b_{s_k}$. This works because both the osmotic coefficient and the osmolality are properties of the solution. Since the van't Hoff factors i_{s_i}, i_{s_j}, \dots are properties attributed to the individual solutes, a similar extension of 2.63 makes little sense.

2.2.6 Organic Acids

This study deals with both inorganic and organic solutes; the inorganic solutes, as well as one of the organics, are salts and thus strong electrolytes. The rest of the organic solutes contain one or more carboxylic acid groups $-COOH$, which may protolyze in aqueous solution. The stepwise protolysis of a general polyprotic acid H_nA can be described by the equilibria

with the corresponding acid (a) constants for each step given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 K_{a1} &= \frac{[H_{n-1}A^-]_{eq}[H_3O^+]_{eq}}{[H_nA]_{eq}} \\
 K_{a2} &= \frac{[H_{n-2}A^{2-}]_{eq}[H_3O^+]_{eq}}{[H_{n-1}A^-]_{eq}} \\
 K_{a3} &= \frac{[H_{n-3}A^{3-}]_{eq}[H_3O^+]_{eq}}{[H_{n-2}A^{2-}]_{eq}} \\
 &\dots \\
 K_{an} &= \frac{[A^{n-}]_{eq}[H_3O^+]_{eq}}{[HA^{(n-1)-}]_{eq}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.65}$$

Strictly, the acid dissociation equilibrium constants should be expressed in terms of the activities of the involved species; here, activities have been replaced with concentrations in anticipation of the following application for equations 2.65. This corresponds to an implicit assumption of solution ideality.

The protolysis of the carboxylic acid groups can be viewed as a dissociation of the organic acid in aqueous solution. The acids concerned in this work are weak and will thus only protolyze, or dissociate, partly; the degree of dissociation α_a can then be defined as the difference between the amount of acid initially dissolved in solution $[H_nA]_{in}$

and the amount undissociated acid present at equilibrium $[H_nA]_{eq}$, normalized by the original amount

$$\alpha_a \equiv \frac{[H_nA]_{in} - [H_nA]_{eq}}{[H_nA]_{in}} \quad (2.66)$$

The dissociation degree α_a can be determined from the acid constants K_{an} , as noted by Kumar et al. [62], by considering the dissociation steps as

where $X_{n'}$ is the amount of $H_{n-(n'-1)}A^{(n'-1)-}$ that dissociates to form $H_{n-n'}A^{n'-}$. This gives the equilibrium conditions as

$$\begin{aligned}
 [H_nA]_{eq} &= [H_nA]_{in} - X_1 \\
 [H_{n-1}A^-]_{eq} &= X_1 - X_2 \\
 [H_{n-2}A^{2-}]_{eq} &= X_2 - X_3 \\
 &\dots \\
 [A^{n-}]_{eq} &= X_n \\
 [H_3O^+]_{eq} &= X_1 + X_2 + \dots + X_n
 \end{aligned} \quad (2.67)$$

For a known initial concentration of dissolved acid $[H_nA]_{in}$, equations 2.67 can be solved numerically using equations 2.65 with known acids constants K_{an} , to yield the equilibrium acid concentration $[H_nA]_{eq}$ in solution, from which the acid dissociation degree α_a can be calculated by equation 2.66.

The dissociation degree α_a can be related to the acid van't Hoff factor i_a [44] by the following argument: Interpreting the acid van't Hoff factor i_a as the overall number of species generated upon dissolution from each acid molecule [112, pp.852], an initial

amount of dissolved acid $[H_nA]_{in}$ will dissociate to generate a total amount of dissolved species at equilibrium

$$\begin{aligned} i_a[H_nA]_{in} &= [H_nA]_{eq} + N_a X = ([H_nA]_{in} - X) + N_a X \Rightarrow \\ X &= \frac{(i_a - 1)}{(N_a - 1)} [H_nA]_{in} \end{aligned} \quad (2.68)$$

$[H_nA]_{eq}$ is the equilibrium amount of undissociated acid, X is the amount of acid that does dissociate and N_a is the number of ions generated from each molecule that dissociates. From equation 2.68, the acid dissociation degree α_a can then be deduced

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_a &= \frac{[H_nA]_{in} - [H_nA]_{eq}}{[H_nA]_{in}} \\ &= \frac{[H_nA]_{in} - ([H_nA]_{in} - X)}{[H_nA]_{in}} \\ &= \frac{[H_nA]_{in} - \left([H_nA]_{in} - \left(\frac{i_a - 1}{N_a - 1} \right) [H_nA]_{in} \right)}{[H_nA]_{in}} \\ &= \frac{i_a - 1}{N_a - 1} \end{aligned} \quad (2.69)$$

Carboxylic acids have a tendency to dimerize in solution due to hydrogen bond formation between the carboxylic groups [79, pp.503], [31, pp.664]. This is just one manifestation of association processes between species in solution, another is pairing of ions due to electrostatic interactions [112, pp.852]. Both dissociation and association will affect the water activity a_w of aqueous solutions [101, pp.214] by increasing and decreasing the effective number of dissolved solute species, respectively. Relation 2.69 is valid under the assumption that dissociation dominates association in the solution.

All of the organic acids studied in this work contain other functional groups besides carboxylic groups, for instance hydroxyl groups $-OH$ or carbonyl groups $=C=O$. As opposed to polyprotic acids that contain multiple carboxylic groups, the compounds with different functional groups will be referred to as polyfunctional organics.

2.3 Droplets

A droplet can be defined as a small volume of liquid at equilibrium with its surrounding vapor and air [11, pp.155]. In the atmosphere, aqueous solution droplets can form by condensation of water vapor from ambient air onto solid aerosol particles comprising water soluble species, which subsequently dissolve in the liquid water [45, pp.289]. This occurs, when formation of the solution droplet is energetically favored over the particle remaining in its solid state, that is when the phase transformation involves a decrease in the Gibbs free energy of the system [92, pp.508]. Due to the relation given by equations 2.10, 2.34 and 2.5 between the water vapor pressure and the liquid water chemical potential (the partial molar Gibbs free energy) in the system, the tendency of solid particles to take up water and form solution droplets depends on the relative humidity.

Some chemical species condense and evaporate water continuously with changing relative humidity and are thus called hygroscopic [92, pp.508], while others do not begin to take up water before a definite so-called deliquescence relative humidity (*DRH*) is attained [92, pp.509-510]. The subsequent equilibrium behavior of the formed solution droplets and possible growth into cloud droplets is described by Köhler theory [55], to be expounded in the following.

In this work, the term "particle" designates a dry solid particle, and once the particle has taken up water it is referred to as a "droplet". Properties of dry particles are denoted by upper-case letters with subscript p , whereas droplet properties are denoted with lower-case letters and no subscript.

2.3.1 Surface Tension

A surface is more precisely an interface between two bulk phases with distinct properties; across the surface, a rapid change of corresponding properties thus occurs [64, pp.97],[8, pp.58], which can be idealized as discontinuous, making the surface a two-dimensional entity [47, pp.49-50]. The surface can be regarded as a separate phase and thus assigned properties which are distinct from those of either interfacing bulk phase [80, pp.12.1] but nevertheless depend on the characteristics of both of these [64, pp.97], [8, pp.1]. Here, the concern is specifically the interface between an aqueous solution and air, which is referred to as the aqueous solution surface.

A unique surface property is that of surface tension σ . The surface tension $\sigma(P)$ in a point P on a given surface is equivalently defined as the magnitude of the force $dF_\sigma(P)$ pr. unit length dl of a line segment through P acting in P tangential to the surface and orthogonal to the line segment [64, pp.98], [47, pp.49]

$$\sigma(P) = \frac{dF_\sigma(P)}{dl} \quad (2.70)$$

or the surface Gibbs free energy $dG_\sigma(P)$ pr. unit area dA in P for constant temperature and pressure [80, pp.12.1], [8, pp.48]

$$\sigma(P) = \frac{dG_\sigma(P)}{dA} \quad (2.71)$$

The second definition strictly pertains to the surfaces of pure liquids [8, pp.77]. If both interfacing bulk phases are homogeneous and isotropic, that is their properties are independent of position and direction, the surface tension $\sigma(P) = \sigma$ is constant throughout the surface phase and is the surface tension of the surface in question [64, pp.98], [47, pp.49]. The dimension of surface tension is force pr. length or energy pr. area, and the units are correspondingly [N/m] or [J/m²] [64, pp.98], [8, pp.4].

Generally, the surface tension depends on temperature T , pressure p and the composition of the interfacing bulk phases [80, pp.12.11-12], [8, pp.50,55,65]. For single component systems, the surface tension is often observed to decrease nearly linearly

with increasing temperature and is expected increase with increasing pressure. A similar behavior applies to mixtures. Since this work is concerned with properties of aqueous solutions surrounded by air at ambient conditions, the surface tension temperature and pressure dependencies of these systems are not considered further, whereas the surface tension variation with aqueous solution composition is addressed below.

The surface tension σ arises due to the rapid change of intermolecular forces across an interface separating two distinct bulk phases. The unbalanced forces in the interface generates a tension or an increased molecular interaction energy; since the interface is only arbitrarily assigned as surface of either bulk phase, this tension or change in molecular interaction energy, that is the surface tension, can always be regarded as positive when the two separate phases can coexist. A positive surface tension causes a tendency for the surface to contract and thereby minimize the surface area, since decreasing the surface area will decrease the additional force or the surface Gibbs free energy [8, pp.1,5,8,51-53,56,61], [80, pp.12.1], [64, pp.97-98]. In the absence of additional forces such as gravity, fluid systems such as those comprising only a liquid droplet solution and air will therefore attain spherical interfaces [47, pp.53], [64, pp.98-99], for which the surface area is minimal for a given contained volume. The effect of gravity on droplet shape can be disregarded for aqueous droplets with radii smaller than so-called capillary length $r < R_c = 2.7$ mm [64, pp.99]; In this study, droplets are therefore assumed to spherical.

For systems in mechanical equilibrium, contraction of the surface is balanced by the resulting increase in pressure of the enclosed bulk phase. The pressure difference Δp sustained across a surface of arbitrary shape is given by the Young-Laplace equation [8, pp.8], [64, pp.99], which for the special case of a spherical surface with surface tension σ and curvature radius r yields the pressure difference between the convex (outer) p_{out} and the concave (inner) p_{in} side of the interface as [8, pp.11], [64, pp.98], [47, pp.52-53]

$$\Delta p = p_{in} - p_{out} = \frac{2\sigma}{r} \quad (2.72)$$

As a consequence of the Young-Laplace equation, the pressure is always greater by an amount $2\sigma/r$ on the concave (inner) than on the convex (outer) side of a spherical interface [8, pp.8], [64, pp.99], [47, pp.53] and the pressure difference Δp increases with increasing surface tension σ and decreasing radius r of curvature. Furthermore, since a plane can be idealized as a sphere with infinite radius of curvature $r = \infty$, no pressure difference $\Delta p = 0$ can be sustained across a flat surface [47, pp.53].

The aqueous solution droplets in ambient air of concern for this study attain sizes in the diameter range 10 nm and 1 μ m; therefore the effect of gravity on the droplet shape can reasonably be disregarded [64, pp.99], just as the actual dependence of the surface tension on droplet curvature, which becomes evident for systems of very small scale $r < 2$ nm can be ignored [8, pp.55].

2.3.2 The Kelvin Effect

The effect of the pressure difference Δp existing across a spherical droplet surface on the equilibrium partial vapor pressure p_i of substance i in a liquid droplet can be rationalized as follows: By definition of the Gibbs free energy of a system with composition $\sum_k n_k$ [92, pp.493], its partial derivative with respect to pressure p is [92, pp.499] [11, pp.128]

$$\left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial p}\right)_{T,n_k} = V \quad (2.73)$$

Assuming the order of differentiation is immaterial, the partial derivative of the chemical potential μ_i of substance i with respect to pressure p yields the partial molar volume v_i of the substance [11, pp.147], [13, pp.830]

$$\left(\frac{\partial \mu_i}{\partial p}\right)_{T,n_i,n_{j \neq i}} \stackrel{2.1}{=} \frac{\partial}{\partial p} \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial n_i}\right)_{T,p,n_{j \neq i}} = \frac{\partial}{\partial n_i} \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial p}\right)_{T,n_i,n_{j \neq i}} \stackrel{2.73}{=} \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial n_i}\right)_{T,n_{j \neq i}} \equiv v_i \quad (2.74)$$

When substance i is present in both liquid (l) and gas (g) phase, the equilibrium condition 2.5 for its chemical potential μ_i in the respective phases gives

$$\mu^l = \mu^g \quad (2.75)$$

The variation of the liquid phase chemical potential of substance i with the pressure of the system p is given by

$$\frac{\partial \mu_i^l}{\partial p} \stackrel{2.74}{=} v_i^l(T, p) \quad (2.76)$$

If substance i behaves ideally in the gas phase, the fugacity f_i can be replaced by the corresponding partial pressure p_i in expression 2.34 for the gas phase chemical potential, and the variation herein with the partial vapor pressure p_i of substance i then becomes

$$\frac{\partial \mu_i^g}{\partial p_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial p_i} (\mu_i^{g,*}(T, p^*) + RT \ln(p_i/p^*)) = \frac{RT}{p_i} \quad (2.77)$$

A change in the pressure of the system Δp will cause a change Δp_i in the equilibrium vapor pressure of substance i . For equilibrium to be maintained, the chemical potentials of the liquid and gas phase of substance i must remain equal $d\mu_i^l = d\mu_i^g$; assuming that only component i in the mixture experience a change in vapor pressure p_i from the pressure change Δp and that the resulting pressure $p + \Delta p$ in return is virtually unaffected by the change Δp_i , the change in vapor pressure $\Delta p_i = p_i(p + \Delta p) - p_i(p)$

can be determined as [11, pp.148-149]

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial \mu_i^l}{\partial p} dp &= \frac{\partial \mu_i^g}{\partial p_i} dp_i \stackrel{2.76, 2.77}{\Rightarrow} \\
v_i^l(T, p) dp &= \frac{RT}{p_i} dp_i \Rightarrow \\
\int_p^{p+\Delta p} v_i^l(T, p') dp' &= RT \int_{p_i(p)}^{p_i(p+\Delta p)} \frac{1}{p_i'} dp_i' \Rightarrow \\
v_i^l \Delta p &= \ln \left(\frac{p_i(p+\Delta p)}{p_i(p)} \right) \Rightarrow \\
p_i(p+\Delta p) &= p_i(p) \exp \left(\frac{v_i^l \Delta p}{RT} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{2.78}$$

In the integration, the partial molar volume of substance i in the liquid phase is assumed to be constant $v_i^l(T, p) = v_i^l$ over integrated pressure interval $[p; p + \Delta p]$, which seems reasonable for liquid water at ambient pressures. Equation 2.78 is equivalent to the Poynting equation [13, pp.831], giving the dependence of the partial pressure on total pressure as mentioned in section 2.1.4.

Since no pressure difference can be sustained across a flat surface $\Delta p = 0$ according to the Young-Laplace equation 2.72, the water vapor pressure over a flat surface of pure water will only depend on temperature T and ambient pressure p , that is $p_w^{0,flat} = p_w^0(T, p)$, where the notation from section 2.2.4 has been changed in order to emphasize the role of the liquid phase. However, for a spherical droplet of pure water the increased pressure on the liquid due to the curved droplet surface $\Delta p = 2\sigma_w/r$ (where σ_w is the surface tension of pure water in air and r is the droplet curvature radius) increases the equilibrium vapor pressure of water in the droplet $p_w^{0,drop}$ above that given for pure water by the temperature and ambient pressure $p_w^0(T, p)$ by an amount according to equations 2.72 and 2.78

$$p_w^{0,drop} = p_w^0(T, p) \exp \left(\frac{v_w^0 \Delta p}{RT} \right) = p_w^0(T, p) \exp \left(\frac{v_w^0 2\sigma_w}{RT r} \right) \tag{2.79}$$

Here, the partial molar volume of pure water $v_w^0 = M_w/\rho_w$ has appropriately been applied. Equation 2.79 is called the Kelvin equation [11, pp.156], [92, pp.521], [8, pp.54] and states that the equilibrium water vapor pressure is greater over a droplet than over a flat surface of pure liquid water. This phenomenon is accordingly called the Kelvin effect.

For water in an aqueous solution where the dissolved solute exerts no vapor pressure, the derivation of equation 2.78 is still as valid. Applying the partial molar volume of water in solution v_w^{sol} and the solution/air surface tension σ_{sol} , the Kelvin equation for the water vapor pressure over a spherical aqueous solution droplet $p_w^{sol,drop}$ at ambient temperature T and pressure p becomes

$$p_w^{sol,drop} = p_w^{sol}(T, p) \exp \left(\frac{v_w^{sol} 2\sigma_{sol}}{RT r} \right) \simeq p_w^{sol}(T, p) \exp \left(\frac{2M_w \sigma_{sol}}{RT \rho_w r} \right) \tag{2.80}$$

where $p_w^{sol}(T, p)$ is the water vapor pressure over a flat surface of the corresponding aqueous solution. In the last step, the partial molar volume of water in solution has been approximated with the partial molar volume of pure water $v_w^{sol} \simeq v_w^0 = M_w/\rho_w$. This corresponds to an assumption of volume additivity of the solution components, or equivalently to solution ideality [16], [17], [61] but is approximately attained for dilute solution [92, pp.786].

2.3.3 The Köhler Equation

The water vapor pressure of a solution of non-volatile solute is reduced from the pure water value $p_w^{sol} = a_w p_w^0$ due to the Raoult effect as given by equation 2.38. Substituting this expression into the Kelvin equation 2.80 for a spherical aqueous solution droplet thus yields

$$p_w^{sol,drop} = p_w^{sol}(T, p) \exp\left(\frac{2M_w\sigma_{sol}}{RT\rho_w r}\right) = p_w^0(T, p) a_w \exp\left(\frac{2M_w\sigma_{sol}}{RT\rho_w r}\right) \quad (2.81)$$

The saturation ratio for the droplet solution is according to equation 2.40 the fractional relation of equilibrium water vapor pressures over the aqueous solution droplet and a flat surface of pure water, respectively, $s \equiv p_w^{sol,drop}/p_w^0$. Omitting the superscripts on the aqueous solution droplet water vapor pressure p_w , the saturation ratio s is given by the Köhler equation [55] in the form [92, pp.785], [57], [16], [17], [61], [100]

$$s = \frac{p_w}{p_w^0} = a_w \exp\left(\frac{4M_w\sigma}{RT\rho_w d}\right) \quad (2.82)$$

where M_w and ρ_w are the water molar mass and mass density, σ is the droplet solution/air surface tension and $d = 2r$ is the diameter of the growing spherical droplet. Often, equation 2.82 is stated deploying the droplet solution density ρ instead of ρ_w [89], [62], [40], [41], [84]; however the resulting difference in saturation ratio thus obtained should be negligible [61], [16].

The supersaturation ratio is defined according to the saturation ratio s , given by equation 2.40, as

$$ss \equiv s - 1, \quad SS \equiv S - 100\% \quad (2.83)$$

Here, SS is the corresponding supersaturation in units of [%] [61]. In terms of the supersaturation ratio ss , the Köhler equation then becomes

$$ss = \frac{p_w}{p_w^0} - 1 = a_w \exp\left(\frac{4M_w\sigma}{RT\rho_w d}\right) - 1 \quad (2.84)$$

The Köhler equation states the relation between the equilibrium saturation s or supersaturation ss ratio and the diameter d of the solution droplet formed on a given dry particle and thus describes the equilibrium growth of the droplet by condensation of water from the vapor phase. Here, the dry particle is assumed to be spherical and can therefore be described in terms of its diameter D_p .

As the water activity term a_w gives the influence of the Raoult effect on the droplet equilibrium (super) saturation ratio, while the exponential term gives the dependence on the Kelvin effect, these individual terms are correspondingly called the Raoult and the Kelvin term of the Köhler equation, respectively. A small value of the droplet solution water activity a_w results from a large Raoult effect, and a small droplet diameter d or a large droplet solution surface tension σ entails a large exponential term and a large Kelvin effect. Since the droplet solution water activity implicitly depends on the droplet diameter owing to the dilution resulting from droplet growth, the Kelvin and Raoult effects exert opposing influences on the magnitude of the equilibrium (super) saturation ratio of a droplet.

A plot of the Köhler equation in either of its forms is called a Köhler curve; fig. 2.1 shows the Raoult and Kelvin terms together with the Köhler curve resulting from their combination, for the equilibrium growth of a droplet formed on a particle consisting of ammonium sulfate with a diameter of 20 nm in its original dry form.

Figure 2.1: Example of a Köhler curve with resolved Raoult and Kelvin terms, here for the equilibrium growth of the droplet formed on a 20 nm dry ammonium sulfate particle.

The Köhler curve maximum value resulting from combining the opposing effects of the Raoult and Kelvin terms is called the critical (super) saturation ratio, denoted s_c or ss_c , and defines the corresponding critical droplet diameter d_c . For droplets smaller than the critical diameter, the Köhler curve slope is positive $ds/dd > 0$ and the equilibrium given by the Köhler equation is stable, as small perturbations in either droplet size or

(super) saturation ratio will cause the system to attain a new equilibrium position in the immediate vicinity of the previous. On the contrary, droplets larger than the critical diameter are in unstable equilibrium according to the Köhler equation with respect to the surrounding water vapor, since the Köhler curve slope is negative $ds/dd < 0$; a small decrease in droplet size or (super) saturation ratio will make water evaporate from the droplet until the corresponding equilibrium Köhler curve position for droplet sizes smaller than the critical diameter is reached, while a small increase in droplet size or (super) saturation ratio will cause the droplet to grow only limited by the availability of condensing water vapor controlled by diffusion. This is the principle of formation of cloud droplets in the atmosphere and is called cloud droplet activation of either the original dry particle or of the corresponding droplet formed from it. A droplet that has grown beyond the critical diameter is therefore said to be activated [92, pp.809].

Figure 2.2: Example of the variation in critical saturation ratio s_c with dry particle diameter D_p for particles of a given chemical composition, here 20-110 nm ammonium sulfate particles.

For particles of a given chemical composition, the larger particles activate for lower critical saturation ratios than the smaller particles. The Kelvin effect is innately smaller from the onset of droplet growth for larger dry particles, since at the point of droplet formation the droplet diameter equals the dry particle diameter $d = D_p$. In addition, a larger Raoult effect is attained at a given droplet diameter d from dissolution of the larger amount in moles of solute contained within the larger dry particles, which result in comparatively smaller water mole fractions in the droplets. Consequently, for any droplet diameter d , the equilibrium saturation ratio s is lower for droplets formed on

larger dry particles. It can therefore be reasoned, that when the Köhler curves for droplets formed on larger dry particles have lower values s at any point d than the Köhler curves for droplets formed on smaller dry particles, then the corresponding values of the Köhler curve maxima, the critical saturation ratios s_c , must also be smaller for droplets formed on larger dry particles than for droplets formed on smaller dry particles. Fig. 2.2 shows the variation of critical saturation ratio s_c as function of dry particle diameter D_p for droplets formed on ammonium sulfate particles with diameters between 20 and 110 nm.

On the other hand, for dry particles of a given diameter D_p with different chemical compositions, the critical saturation ratios s_c of the corresponding droplets formed will depend on the water activities a_w and surface tensions σ attained by the droplet solutions from dissolution of the respective dry particle constituents; the lower the water activity a_w or surface tension σ attained for a resulting solution droplet at a given diameter d , the greater the Raoult effect or the smaller the Kelvin effect, and thus the lower the critical saturation ratio s_c of the droplet.

The magnitude of the Raoult effect will depend on the resulting mole fraction of water and the nature of the intermolecular interactions in a solution droplet formed; the water mole fraction at any droplet size is determined by the amount in moles of solute contained within the dry particle and the subsequent dissociation behavior of this solute upon dissolution as the droplet is formed. The water activity a_w decreases and the Raoult effect increases, when the effective amount in moles of dissolved solute in a droplet solution increases.

The amount in moles of solute in particles of a given dry diameter D_p is related to the molar mass to mass density ratio of the constituents which for the simple case of single component solid particles gives

$$n_s = \frac{m_s}{M_s} = \frac{\rho_s V_s}{M_s} \propto \frac{\rho_s}{M_s} D_p^3 \quad (2.85)$$

where n_s , m_s , M_s , ρ_s and V_s are the amount in moles, mass, molar mass, mass density and volume of solute s in a dry particle of diameter D_p comprising pure s . The molar mass to mass density ratio of dry particle components is invoked several places in this work for a qualitative estimate of the expected relative activation order of particles with different compositions.

Conditions pertaining to the droplet solution surface tension is treated in section 2.3.4 below.

Particles that activate at a given saturation ratio are called cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) [92, pp.809]. Equivalently, the saturation ratio s_c necessary for a given dry particle or solution droplet to activate is referred to as the cloud condensation nucleus, or activation, property of the particle or droplet in question.

In literature on particle hygroscopic growth and cloud droplet activation, the water vapor pressures p_w and p_w^0 are often referred to as the vapor pressure and saturation vapor pressure of water, respectively. Strictly, they are the equilibrium (or saturation) partial vapor pressures of water over the droplet solution and over a flat surface of pure water, respectively.

2.3.4 Surfactants and Partitioning

As mentioned in section 2.3.1, the surface tension of a liquid mixture depends on the composition, but often not linearly due to non-ideality of the mixture. Furthermore, there is a tendency for the component with the lower surface tension in its pure form to preferentially concentrate in the surface phase; the surface tension of the mixture is therefore lowered relatively more than expected from the mixing ratio and individual pure form surface tensions of the solution components. The difference in composition of the surface and bulk phases arises as the lower surface tension thus attained is energetically favorable [80, pp.12.12,12.20]. In addition, contrary to pure liquids where the surface Gibbs free energy density and the surface tension are identical, the composition difference between surface and bulk for mixtures introduces a lowering of the surface Gibbs free energy density from the value of the surface tension [8, pp.77]. Preferential concentration in the surface is also referred to as surface adsorption of the component in question [8, pp.67], [66].

For aqueous solutions of organic solutes with molecular structure containing both polar functional groups and non-polar hydrocarbon parts, surface adsorption of the organic can be very pronounced and the surface tension lowered considerably by comparatively small amounts of solute [80, pp.12.17], [8, pp.69]. Organic compounds with a polar and non-polar structure are also called surfactants, as in surface active agents [8, pp.69], [66]. Surfactants preferentially concentrate in the aqueous solution surface to minimize the unfavorable interactions between polar water molecules and the non-polar regions of the surfactant molecules. In the surface, the hydrophobic hydrocarbon parts of the surfactant molecules are excluded from the solution, pointing out towards the gas phase, and thus mutually interact via van der Waals forces, whereas the hydrophilic ends form hydrogen bonds with water molecules. Since both interactions are weaker than the hydrogen bonding in water, the strength of molecular interactions in the surface phase and thus the surface tension decrease compared to pure water and the magnitude of the surface tension lowering increases with the amount of surfactant in the surface (private communication, Ari Laaksonen).

In Gibbs surface thermodynamics, the surface region is quantified by a two-dimensional entity called the Gibbs dividing surface, which resolves the system into a bulk (B) phase of volume V^B enclosed by a surface (S) phase of area A^S , and the surfactant (*sft*) preferential surface adsorption is then described in terms of the surfactant surface excess n_{sft}^S , providing the excess amount in moles of surfactant present in the area of the Gibbs dividing surface [8, pp.71-75], [97]. The value of the surfactant surface excess n_{sft}^S depends on the position chosen for the idealized Gibbs dividing surface of the

system [66], [97] but either way reaches a maximum value N_{sft}^S when the surface phase is saturated with surfactant [8, pp.78].

The surfactant surface area and bulk volume concentrations can be defined as

$$c_{sft}^S = \frac{n_{sft}^S}{A^S}, c_{sft}^B = \frac{n_{sft}^B}{V^B} \quad (2.86)$$

where n_{sft}^S and n_{sft}^B are the respective amounts in moles of surfactant in the surface and bulk phases and A^S and V^B the surface area and bulk volume. The total amount in moles of surfactant in the system is $n_{sft}^T = n_{sft}^S + n_{sft}^B$ and until surface saturation is reached, the resulting surfactant equilibrium distribution between solution surface and bulk must be expressible by a surface adsorption equilibrium like

$$K_{ads} = \frac{c_{sft}^S}{c_{sft}^B} \quad (2.87)$$

Since the surfactant surface and bulk concentrations innately depend on the surface area A^S and bulk volume V^B magnitudes, the equilibrium distribution of surfactant solute between the bulk and surface phases due to preferential surfactant surface adsorption thus depends on the ratio of surface area to bulk volume A^S/V^B : For small droplets in particular, the surface area to bulk volume ratio is large and, at equilibrium, the amount in moles of surfactant in the surface phase n_{sft}^S is not negligible compared to the bulk amount n_{sft}^B . The droplet bulk phase is thus notably depleted in surfactant solute and from relation 2.87 the decreased bulk concentration c_{sft}^B affects the surfactant equilibrium distribution between surface and bulk phases such that the surface concentration c_{sft}^S decreases accordingly. A smaller surfactant surface concentration entails that the surfactant covers the larger surface area less efficiently and consequently lowers the surface tension less for a given total amount of surfactant n_{sft}^T , when the surface area to bulk volume ratio is large [66].

Generally, for a given total amount of surfactant, the corresponding equilibrium surface and bulk concentrations will both be smaller and the surface tension lowering by the surfactant less efficient, the larger the surface area to bulk volume ratio. This effect on the magnitude of the surface tension reduction of the surfactant distribution between surface and bulk is referred to as the effect of surfactant partitioning [66], [97]. The presence of salts in the aqueous solution affects this effect of partitioning by further promoting the preferential surfactant surface adsorption and thus enhancing the surface tension lowering attained from a given total amount of surfactant in solution [66].

Surfactant partitioning in aqueous solution droplets entails two different consequences for the corresponding cloud droplet activation properties. For smaller droplets, due to partitioning, a given initial surfactant concentration lowers the droplet solution surface tension less compared to pure water [66] and according to the Kelvin effect (equation 2.80), activation is thus comparatively less facilitated by the presence of the surfactant in the droplet. Furthermore, smaller droplets attain a smaller Raoult effect (equation

2.38) for a given initial surfactant concentration as a consequence of the resulting decrease in surfactant solute bulk concentration when the droplet bulk is increasingly depleted in surfactant solute due to surface adsorption onto relatively larger surface areas [97]. This is the basis for the Koupio model described in chapter 5, taking surfactant partitioning into account in both the Kelvin and the Raoult term when evaluating cloud droplet activation properties of surfactant containing particles from Köhler theory.

Chapter 3

Experimental

This chapter describes the equipment, setup and procedures used for the laboratory experiments in this work, the data fitting and calibration methods subsequently applied for obtaining the final experimental results and the principles by which estimates of the experimental errors have been made.

3.1 Conduction of Experiments

All experiments performed for this study are conducted in the aerosol laboratory at the University of Copenhagen. The objective of the laboratory experiments is to measure cloud droplet activation properties of aerosol particles with different sizes and chemical compositions produced for this purpose. In this section, a review is given of the experimental setup and procedures applied for particle activation measurements in this work.

3.1.1 The Experimental Setup

Particles are generated in the laboratory by atomization of an aqueous solution of the compounds and their relative mass ratios of interest. This produces an aqueous solution aerosol, which is subsequently dried by passing through a set of diffusion driers, leaving the dissolved solute as a polydisperse aerosol of solid dry particles. The dry aerosol is supplied with a known equilibrium charge distribution in bipolar chargers and a narrow distribution of sizes is then selected based on the electrical mobility of the charged particles using a differential mobility analyzer (DMA).

The resulting quasi-monodisperse dry aerosol flow is diluted by purified dry air and split between a condensation particle counter (CPC) and a cloud condensation nucleus counter (CCNC); The CPC measures the total number concentration of aerosol particles in the flow, whereas the CCNC exposes the aerosol to a given supersaturation and determines the number concentration of particles that activate under the given conditions. The quantity measured in the experiments is the activated fraction, defined as the ratio of the number concentration of activated particles to the total particle number concentration in the aerosol flow, as function of supersaturation for each particle size

and chemical composition.

A schematic representation of the experimental setup is shown in fig. 3.1 and the central components can be seen in fig. 3.2; the basic properties of these components and details of the experimental procedure are given in the following.

Figure 3.1: Schematic representation of the experimental setup for laboratory activation measurements. A quasi-monodisperse dry aerosol is generated by atomization of an aqueous solution followed by drying, charging and size selection of the resulting aerosol. The measured total and activated number concentrations of aerosol particles in the flow yields the activated fraction of particles at a given supersaturation. Adapted from Rosenørn [88].

Figure 3.2: Main features of the experimental setup for laboratory activation measurements. An aqueous solution aerosol is generated in the atomizer and dried to produce a polydisperse solid particle aerosol flow by passage through the diffusion driers. After dilution of the flow, a quasi-monodisperse dry aerosol flow is selected in the differential mobility analyzer (DMA) and the flow is split between the condensation particle counter (CPC) and the cloud condensation nucleus counter (CCNC) for measurements of the number concentrations of total and activated particles in the flow, respectively.

The DMA

The differential mobility analyzer (DMA) is part of TSI Series 3080 electrostatic classifier [7] and enables selection of a narrow size fraction from a polydisperse aerosol by separation based on electrical mobility.

Before entering the DMA, the dry polydisperse aerosol is conveyed to attain an equilibrium bipolar (positive and negative) charge distribution, slightly different from the Boltzmann equilibrium charge level, by passing through two bipolar chargers, a TSI Model 3077 and a TSI Model 3012 Aerosol neutralizer, in series [4, pp.2-1], [3, pp.2-1].

The DMA contains two concentric metal cylinders (see fig. 3.3), of which the inner

is negatively charged and the outer is electrically grounded, thus generating an electric field E between the cylinders. The bipolar charged polydisperse aerosol enters the DMA between the two cylinders, where an electric force $F_E = Ene$ is exerted on the aerosol charges ne and thereby deflecting the aerosol flow. The electrical mobility Z_p of a particle gives a measure its ability to move in an electric field and is defined as [7, pp.B-12]

$$Z_p = \frac{n\epsilon C}{3\pi\eta D_p^{EM}} \quad (3.1)$$

where n is the particle charge number, e is the elementary charge, C is the so-called Cunningham slip correction factor, η is the aerosol carrier gas viscosity and D_p^{EM} is the particle electrical mobility diameter.

Equation 3.1 stems from equating the electric force F_E to the corresponding drag force F_D exerted on a particle by the aerosol flow carrier gas, as particles are assumed to move at terminal velocities v^{TE} in the electric field through DMA. For particle sizes in the transition regime [45, pp.51], the drag force is reduced from the value given by Stokes' law [45, pp.45] by the Cunningham slip correction factor, which depends on the particle size $C = C(D_p) \geq 1$ [45, pp.49]

$$F_D = \frac{3\pi\eta v^T D_p^M}{C} \quad (3.2)$$

Here, v^T and D_p^M denote the particle terminal velocity and mobility diameter for a general applied force.

In the DMA, positively charged particles will move towards the negatively charged inner cylinder (see fig. 3.3) and given the right electrical mobility Z_p exit the DMA through a narrow slit at the bottom of the inner cylinder, whereby a selection of particles with a narrow range of electrical mobilities is obtained. The actual width of the electrical mobility distribution depends on the aerosol flow rates and properties of the DMA [7, pp.B-13].

As the electrical mobility Z_p given by equation 3.1 depends on both particle size and charge, the quasi-monodisperse electrical mobility distribution exiting the DMA does not necessarily entail a monodisperse distribution of electrical mobility diameter D_p^{EM} . Thus, the aerosol selected by the DMA will contain a fraction of larger multiply charged particles with the same electrical mobility as the majority of smaller, singly charged particles. As will be seen later, this has consequences for the outcome of activation experiments, as larger particles of a given composition activate more easily than smaller particles (see section 2.3.3). The precise fraction of particles with different multiple charges $n > 1$ for a given particle size can be seen from the tabulated bipolar equilibrium charge distribution [7, pp.B-10].

Figure 5. A schematic drawing of a DMA column.

Figure 3.3: A schematic representation of the DMA. A polydisperse aerosol enters the DMA in the electric field between two concentric metal cylinders and positively charged particles are deflected towards the inner cylinder as shown. Particles with the appropriate electrical mobility Z_p exit the DMA as a quasi-monodisperse aerosol flow the bottom of the inner cylinder. Adapted from Rosenørn [88].

Stokes' law assumes spherical particles; therefore, the electrical mobility diameter D_p^{EM} defined by equation 3.1 must be interpreted as the diameter of a spherical particle with a given electrical mobility Z_p . In the interpretation of the experimental results, particles are generally assumed to be spherical and the geometric diameter consequently equated to the electrical mobility diameter $D_p^G = D_p^{EM}$ and referred to simply as the particle diameter D_p . For non-spherical particles, the dynamic shape factor $\chi \geq 1$ [45, pp.51] can be applied to the electrical mobility diameter D_p^{EM} in order to obtain the so-called equivalent volume diameter D_p^e of the particle

$$D_p^e = \frac{\chi}{D_p^{EM}} \quad (3.3)$$

which is defined as the diameter of a sphere having the same volume as the non-spherical particle. This is important in relation to determining the amount of compound contained within a given particle; in this work this is accomplished by use of particle constituent mass densities, and therefore the particle volume must be known.

The CCNC

The total number concentration of particles in the aerosol flow is measured with a TSI Model 3010 condensation particle counter (CPC) [2], where particles are exposed to

supersaturated butanol vapors and subsequently grow by condensation of butanol to reach sizes detectable by built-in optics of the instrument. In this context, particles are therefore interchangeably referred to as condensation nuclei (CN), and the total particle number concentration, given as condensation nuclei number pr. cm^3 , is denoted by $N(\text{CN})$.

A DMA connected to a CPC can be programmed to scan through a given particle size range, and the CPC will then measure the condensation nuclei number concentration for each particle size, thus yielding the particle size distribution $d\text{CN}/dD_p$ for the given size interval.

Particles that activate at a given supersaturation SS are called cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) (see section 2.3.3); the number concentration of cloud condensation nuclei in the aerosol flow $N(\text{CCN})$ is measured as function of supersaturation using the University of Wyoming Model CCNC-100B cloud condensation nucleus counter (CCNC) at the aerosol laboratory at the University of Copenhagen. The CCNC-100B is a static parallel-plate thermal-gradient diffusion chamber type CCNC [33], where a controlled supersaturation is created inside the measurement chamber by a temperature gradient between two horizontal plates with water-saturated surfaces.

Figure 3.4: The diffusion chamber of the cloud condensation nucleus counter (CCNC), closed (left) and opened (right), with a view of the bottom plate lined with water-saturated filter paper.

The top and bottom plates of the diffusion chamber are lined with wetted filter papers (see fig. 3.4) and the top plate is kept at ambient temperature, while the temperature of the bottom plate is lowered by a thermostat to generate a temperature gradient in the chamber between the plates. The temperature gradient ΔT is assumed to be linear and give rise to a corresponding linear equilibrium water vapor pressure $p_w(T)$ gradient between the plates of the chamber [51]. Since the saturation vapor pressure of pure water over a flat surface $p_w^0(T)$ is however a non-linear function of temperature, a supersaturation $SS(T)/[\%] = [p_w(T)/p_w^0(T)] - 1$ profile is established between the plates with a maximum close to (but not exactly at) the center of the chamber (see fig.

3.5). The supersaturation profile is directly related to the temperature T and can be calculated for all vertical positions between the plates as function of the temperature gradient [52].

Figure 3.5: The supersaturation profile $SS(T)$ in the diffusion chamber established from the temperature gradient ΔT between the top and bottom plates of the chamber. The horizontal line mark the chamber center axis. Note the saturation vapor pressure of pure water over a flat surface $p_w^0(T)$ in the figure is denoted by p^s , while the water vapor pressure $p_w(T)$ is denoted by p and the supersaturation by S . Adapted from Rosenørn [88].

During measurements, a sample of the aerosol flow is directed into the diffusion chamber and exposed to a selected supersaturation SS' for a period of approximately 20 s. Particles with critical supersaturations $SS_c \leq SS'$ will activate and grow to the size of cloud droplets (of the order of $1 \mu\text{m}$), which are large enough to be detected by scattering of laser light from a 670 nm laser diode. The laser diode is focused on a small sampling volume on the chamber center axis where the supersaturation is known and close to the maximum value of the given profile. A photo-diode detector records the intensity of scattered laser light, which has been related to the number concentration $N(\text{CCN})$ of CCN in the sampling volume in terms of the detector output voltage.

By splitting the aerosol flow and simultaneously measuring the CN and CCN number concentrations, the activated fraction, or activation ratio, can be determined

$$f_{act} \equiv \frac{N(\text{CCN})}{N(\text{CN})} \quad (3.4)$$

A scan of the activation ratio f_{act} as function of supersaturation SS in the CCNC is called an activation spectrum; the University of Wyoming Model CCNC-100B is designed to measure activation spectra over supersaturation ranges of approximately 0.2-2.0 %.

By definition, the activation ratio f_{act} should assume values in the interval $[0-1]$, but activation ratios greater than unity are regularly obtained from the measured CN and

CCN number concentrations. This is likely due to inappropriate calibration of the photo-diode detector voltage with respect to CCN number concentration, or to the effects of varying particle growth rates with supersaturation on the scattered light intensity in the direction of the detector [33]. Strictly, a CCN number calibration of the CCNC photo-diode detector should be made to ensure correct evaluation of the measured activation ratios, but owing to the subsequent data treatment, the effect on the final experimental results is presumed to be small. However, this will be determined with more confidence by contemplated investigations of the CCNC operation by the Aerosol Group at the University of Copenhagen.

A discrepancy has been observed between the theoretically calculated and measured CCN number concentrations for monodisperse sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate particles [33] (and references herein), possibly owing to a difference in the temperature gradient reported by thermostats in the plates of the diffusion chamber compared to actual temperature gradient between the wetted filter paper surfaces covering the plates and determining the actual supersaturation profile. Therefore, the CCNC must be calibrated with respect to the supersaturation in the sampling volume using activation measurements of pure sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate particles, for which Köhler theory is supposed to be valid. Supersaturation calibration of the CCNC is treated in section 3.2.2.

3.1.2 Particle Generation

The particles investigated in this study are either composed of a single organic or salt compound or consist of binary mixtures of one organic and one salt component, respectively. Table 3.1 lists the names, formulas, abbreviations and manufacturer purity specifications of the compounds used for particle generation in the present work.

compound	abbrev.	formula	purity	manufacturer
ammonium sulfate	AS	$(NH_4)_2SO_4$	-	Merck
<i>cis</i> -pinonic acid	CPA	$C_{10}H_{16}O_3$	98%	Aldrich
citric acid	CA	$C_6H_8O_7$	99.5+%	Aldrich
L-malic acid	MA	$C_4H_6O_5$	97%	Aldrich
sodium chloride	SC	$NaCl$	>99.8%	Riedel-deHaën
sodium dodecyl sulfate	SDS	$C_{12}H_{25}O_4S \cdot Na$	>99%	Sigma

Table 3.1: Names, formulas, abbreviations and manufacturer purity specifications for the compounds used in laboratory particle generation for the experimental work.

Initially, a wet aerosol is generated by atomization of an aqueous solution in a TSI 3076 constant output atomizer [6]; the solution is contained within an atomizer bottle connected to the atomizer and drawn by capillary forces through a narrow vertical passage into the atomizer where it is atomized by a jet of pressurized air (see fig. 3.6). Large droplets subsequently impact on the atomizer wall and return to the atomizer solution,

but droplets with inertia small enough to follow the air stream exit the atomizer as an aqueous solution aerosol. Typical pressures applied were of the magnitude $\simeq 35$ Psi.

Figure 4: Schematic of the TSI 3076 constant output atomizer.

Figure 3.6: A schematic representation of the atomizer. The atomizer solution is drawn into the atomizer and atomized by a jet of pressurized air. Droplets sufficiently small to move with the air flow exit the atomizer as an aqueous solution aerosol. Adapted from Rosenørn [88].

The wet aerosol is subsequently dried by passage through a set of 2 or 3 diffusion driers in series containing granulated silica gel, which gradually lower the relative humidity of the aerosol flow by absorption of water. The aerosol relative humidity upon exiting the diffusion driers is of the order $RH \leq 10\%$ [88, pp.24] and it is generally assumed that the wet aerosol solution droplets crystallize to form solid dry particles. The validity of this assumption will be discussed in connection with the results obtained.

Following charging by the bipolar chargers and further dilution with purified air, a quasi-monodisperse size distribution is selected from the resulting dry polydisperse aerosol based on particle electrical mobility in the DMA as described in section 3.1.1. The nominal electrical mobility diameter reported by the DMA is taken as the maximum of this narrow distribution and applied as the selected diameter D_p of the singly charged particles comprising the majority of the aerosol flow. When possible from availability of equipment, an SMPS scan of the generated dry polydisperse aerosol size distribution dCN/dD_p is performed prior to selecting the monodisperse particles, in order to see if the aerosol covers the desired particle sizes and if the number concentration of particles

with these sizes are appropriate for conduction of the experiments. When this is not the case, the properties of the aerosol is adjusted before commencing the experiments; usually further dilution with purified air is required. The total number concentrations $N(CN)$ of particles in the quasi-monodisperse aerosols during experiments were in the range 200-700 pr. cm^3 .

The atomizer aqueous solutions were prepared directly in the atomizer bottle by dissolving a small amount of the dry crystalline compound(s) of interest in water purified to a conductivity of $18.2 \text{ m}\Omega = 0.055 \text{ }\mu\text{S}$ with a MilliQ PLUS Ultra Pure Water System. Total solute concentrations were in the range 0.10-0.25 g/L.

For the composite particles, the solutes are assumed to be perfectly mixed in the atomizer solution such that the generated particles are internally mixed, and the resulting dry particle composition can be determined from the relative amounts of the solute compounds initially dissolved in the atomizer solution. The respective mass fractions of organic (o) and salt (s) comprising the particles (p) are then given in terms of the weighed (superscript w) amounts of solute, m_o^w and m_s^w , by

$$x_{o\ p}^m = \frac{m_o^w}{m_o^w + m_s^w}, x_{s\ p}^m = \frac{m_s^w}{m_o^w + m_s^w}, x_{o\ p}^m + x_{s\ p}^m = 1 \quad (3.5)$$

The corresponding mass percentages are denoted by capital letters, so that $X_{o\ p}^m [\%] = x_{o\ p}^m \cdot 100\%$, $X_{s\ p}^m [\%] = x_{s\ p}^m \cdot 100\%$ and $X_{o\ p}^m + X_{s\ p}^m = 100\%$.

It is implicitly assumed by application of equation 3.5, that the processes of atomization and crystallization upon drying do not change the aerosol solute component mixing state compared to the atomizer solution; this follows the practice of [14]. For some of the particle compositions studied in this work, this assumption is nevertheless questioned, which will be discussed further in chapter 5.

3.1.3 Activation Measurements

The generated dry monodisperse aerosol flow comprising particles with diameters D_p is split between the CPC and CCNC, where the respective total particle number concentration $N(CN)$ in the aerosol flow and the number concentration $N(CCN)$ of activated particles at a given supersaturation SS are measured, thus giving the activation ratio f_{act} defined in equation 3.4 for the supersaturation in question.

For a selected particle size, the activation spectrum, given as a collection of measured activation ratios over a range of supersaturations, is obtained by scanning the approximate supersaturation interval $SS \in [0.1 - 2.5] \%$ in steps of $\delta SS \in [0.01 - 0.1] \%$ with the CCNC. The upper supersaturation limit of the scan depends on the composition and size of the particles being investigated, but in each case a range of supersaturations is covered ensuring that all particles in the aerosol flow have activated for the largest supersaturation attained and thereby that the measured activation ratio will assume its minimum f_{act}^{min} and maximum f_{act}^{max} values as function of supersaturation over the

interval scanned. Activation of the particles in question is then defined in terms the activation ratio by $f_{act}^{min} \rightarrow f_{act}^{max}$. This is of importance with respect to the interpretation of the measurements, as will be seen in section 3.2.1. As mentioned in section 3.1.1, ideally values of the activation ratio would span the interval $f_{act} \in [0 - 1]$, however, due to properties of the CCNC detector, other extreme values are occasionally observed.

The activation spectrum obtained for particles of a given chemical composition and selected diameter D_p will be referred to as an activation measurement of the particles in question. An example of the outcome of an activation measurement in terms of the measured activation ratios f_{act} as function of supersaturation SS over the interval scanned by the CCNC is shown in fig. 3.7 for the case of 37 nm sodium chloride particles.

Figure 3.7: Example of the raw data outcome of an activation measurement. The supersaturation SS is varied in steps over the interval $[0.1-2.0]$ % and for each step, the corresponding activation ratio f_{act} of the particles is measured. The steep rise in f_{act} around the critical supersaturation SS_c of the particles constituting the maximum of the selected quasi-monodisperse size distribution $dN(CN)/d\log D_p$ is very clear. Activation of doubly charged particles is suggested by the initial rise in the activation ratio f_{act} to a level of about 0.1.

For a perfectly monodisperse aerosol, the activation ratio f_{act} is expected to be a step function of the supersaturation SS , since all particles in the flow will activate upon reaching the single critical supersaturation SS_c defined by the unique particle diameter D_p for a given particle chemical composition. From fig. 3.7 it is nevertheless seen that the rise in the activation ratio f_{act} is not infinitely steep, but rather occurs over a narrow

range of supersaturations ΔSS corresponding to the critical supersaturations ΔSS_c of particles with a narrow range of diameters ΔD_p given by the quasi-monodisperse aerosol size distribution selected by the DMA.

Assuming that the quasi-monodisperse size distribution $dN(CN)/d\log D_p$ is symmetric about the maximum number concentration $N(CN)^*(D_p^*)$ at the diameter D_p^* , the point where half of the particles in the aerosol flow have activated will correspond to the critical supersaturation SS_c^* of the particles with diameter D_p^* . Since the particle diameter D_p^* constituting the the maximum of the quasi-monodisperse size distribution $dN(CN)/d\log D_p$ is interpreted as the diameter D_p of the selected aerosol, the critical supersaturation SS_c of the aerosol particles is consequently determined as the supersaturation SS for which half the particles in the aerosol flow have activated, given by $f_{act} = 0.5(f_{act}^{max} - f_{act}^{min})$ [88, pp.25].

As mentioned in section 3.1.1, most of the particles in the aerosol flow will be singly charged due to the nature of the charge distribution acquired in the bipolar chargers. Still, the aerosol with a selected monodisperse electrical mobility will contain a fraction of multiply charged particles which according to equation 3.1 are larger and therefore will activate for smaller supersaturations than the predominant singly charged particles (see section 2.3.3). The majority of the multiply charged particles are doubly charged, as given by the bipolar charge distribution [7, pp.B-10] and will therefore collectively be referred to as such. When a significant fraction of particles in the aerosol flow carry double charges, the activation of these doubly charged particles appear in the measurements as a premature rise of the activation ratio f_{act} to a level f_{act}^D , where all doubly charged particles have activated. As the singly charged particles subsequently activate for larger supersaturations, f_{act} accordingly rises from the level of f_{act}^D to the level where all particles in the flow have activated f_{act}^{max} .

The value of the full doubly charged particle activation level f_{act}^D represents the fraction of doubly charged particles in the flow, corresponding to the sum of the fractions of positively charged particles with different multiple charge numbers. Usually, this fraction is of the order $f_{act}^D \leq 0.1$; the activation of doubly charged particles is suggested in fig. 3.7 for an activation ratio of about this value.

For each particle chemical composition investigated, a collection of activation measurements is performed for a range of particle diameters D_p with critical supersaturations SS_c spanning the supersaturation interval available by the CCNC. In this way, measured data sets are obtained for the critical supersaturation SS_c as function of particle diameter D_p for particles of the given chemical composition.

3.2 Data Fitting and Calibration

The final experimental results are obtained from the original raw data of the measurements by applying a series of procedures and interpretations as described in the following. Henceforth, the distinction is made that the original raw data will be re-

ferred to as the measured values and the worked up data as the final experimental values.

3.2.1 Fitting the Measurements

For each dry particle composition and size, the measured activation ratios f_{act} are fitted as function of the varied supersaturation SS by a 4-parameter sigmoidal function [40], [41], [82]

$$y = y_0 + \frac{a}{1 + e^{-\left(\frac{x-x_0}{b}\right)}} \quad (3.6)$$

The fitted curve will be called the activation curve for the particles in question (see figure 3.8). Parameter y_0 denotes the bottom level (minimum function value), a the difference between top (maximum function value) and bottom levels, x_0 the position of the curve midpoint between the top and bottom levels ($y_0 + a/2$) and b determines the curve slope. Thus, interpreting the bottom level y_0 as $f_{act} = 0$ and the top level $y_0 + a$ as $f_{act} = 1$, x_0 yields the critical supersaturation SS_c corresponding to the activation curve midpoint $f_{act} = 0.5$. This presupposes that all particles in the flow activate within the supersaturation SS interval scanned, which seems reasonable for the experimental procedure applied as mentioned in section 3.1.3.

It should be mentioned, that all experimental data obtained for this study has also been fitted to a different fitting function based on the DMA transfer functions and the resulting width of the particle electrical mobility distribution selected by the DMA, which has been employed by the Aerosol Group at the University of Copenhagen in previous work [88, pp.25]. Good agreement was found between the critical supersaturations determined from the measurements by the two methods, but the sigmoidal fit 3.6 yields a better overall description of the measured activation ratios and has therefore been used for obtaining the results presented here.

Furthermore, the Aerosol Group at the University of Copenhagen is currently developing a method for activation measurement data fitting and uncertainty analysis deploying errorfunctions; this work is taking place as part of the LExNo project (http://www.mpch-mainz.mpg.de/~schneid/schneider/AtmosphericAerosolChemistryPage/LEXNO_AAC-.htm, last accessed 17-09-2006) in a joint effort to establish appropriate conventions for fitting cloud droplet activation measurements and evaluating the involved experimental uncertainty [32], [33].

Figure 3.8: Example of an activation curve obtained by fitting the experimentally measured activation ratios f_{act} (raw data) as function of the supersaturation SS with the 4-parameter sigmoidal function 3.6. The curve midpoint is interpreted as $f_{act} = 0.5$ and its position x_0 consequently as the critical supersaturation SS_c of the particles in question.

Correction for Doubly Charged Particles

The presence of doubly charged particles in an activation measurement will affect the shape of the fitted curve and thereby the value determined for the fitting parameter x_0 . Measures must thus be taken to correct the fit for the activation of the doubly charged particles, in order to deduce the required critical supersaturation SS_c of the single charged particles.

In this work, such a correction is achieved by establishing the level of doubly charged particles f_{act}^D from inspection of the activation measurements and then fixing the fitting parameter y_0 to its value (see fig. 3.9). This way, the fitted curve will constitute an activation curve for the single charged particles only and the activation curve midpoint position x_0 can be interpreted as the critical supersaturation SS_c of the single charged particles specifically.

Figure 3.9: Example of an activation curve fitted to the experimentally measured activation ratios f_{act} (raw data) with the 4-parameter sigmoidal function 3.6, employing a fixed value of parameter y_0 equal to the level of doubly charged particles f_{act}^D .

Determining the level of doubly charged particles f_{act}^D by inspection involves a subjective judgement which renders the method somewhat arbitrary. However, the value of x_0 obtained from the fit is not very sensitive to the exact position of the level y_0 (see appendix B.1). Furthermore, no standard procedure for doubly charged particle correction has been agreed upon, and other approaches to the matter are also used. The method proposed by Frank et al. [32], where the measured numbers of total and activated particles $N(CN)$ and $N(CCN)$ are corrected by subtraction of the number of doubly charged particles $N(CN)f_{act}^D$ before evaluating the activated fraction of single charged particles f_{act} , however yields the same results for selected cases as the one used here (see appendix B.1).

When no doubly charged particle activation level f_{act}^D can readily be discerned, the activation ratio f_{act} is fitted as function of the supersaturation SS with y_0 as a free fitting parameter.

3.2.2 Calibration of Measured Critical Super Saturations

As mentioned in section 3.1.1, a discrepancy has been observed between the CCN number concentrations for monodisperse sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate particles measured by the CCNC and calculated theoretically using Köhler theory [33] (and refer-

ences herein); this is interpreted as a discrepancy between the nominal supersaturation values SS reported by the CCNC and the supersaturations experienced by particles in the aerosol sample inside the CCNC measurement chamber.

Sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate particles are assumed to comply with Köhler theory as described in section 2.3.3. Thus, measuring the activation for sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate particles in terms of the critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{meas})$ and calculating the corresponding values $SS_c(\text{calc})$ using Köhler theory, a relation between $SS_c(\text{meas})$ and $SS_c(\text{calc})$ can be derived and used for calibrating all critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{meas})$ subsequently measured by the CCNC, to arrive at the final experimental results in the form of the calibrated critical supersaturation values $SS_c(\text{calibr})$. This relation between measured and calculated critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{meas})$ and $SS_c(\text{calc})$ for sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate particles will be called the calibration equation or calibration curve for the CCNC, depending on the form it is presented in. Supersaturation calibration using sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate particle activation measurements has been employed by Raymond and Pandis [84], Bilde and Svenningsson [14] and Frank et al. [33] among others.

In the following, the abbreviations SC and AS will frequently be used for sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate, respectively. The subscripts w , s and p shall denote "water", "salt" and "dry particle", whereas no subscript is used for depicting droplet properties.

Measurements

Activation measurements of sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate particles have been performed as described in section 3.1.3 and the corresponding activation curves subsequently fitted as described in section 3.2.1 to yield the measured critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{meas})$. The values are listed below in table 3.3.

Calculations

The calculated critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{calc})$ for sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate particles are iterated as the maxima of the appropriate Köhler curves, given by equation 2.84. Since the measured values $SS_c(\text{meas})$ are reported in units of [%], the Köhler equation is applied in the form

$$SS = \left(a_w \exp \left(\frac{4M_w \sigma}{RT \rho_w d} \right) - 1 \right) \cdot 100\% \quad (3.7)$$

likewise yielding $SS_c(\text{calc})$ in [%]. SS denote the equilibrium supersaturation of a droplet with diameter d , M_w and ρ_w the molar mass and mass density of water, R and T the gas constant and temperature, and a_w and σ are the droplet solution water activity and liquid/air surface tension.

A number of assumptions have been made to carry out the calculations.

The dry sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate particles selected by the DMA are assumed to be spherical so that no shape factor is applied [100], [14], and the electrical mobility diameter D_p^{EM} is interpreted as the physical diameter D_p . Particle sphericity has been determined as a good assumption for ammonium sulfate particles, whereas a shape factor of 1.08 is sometimes applied to account for cubic sodium chloride particles [61], [45, pp.52]. However, as will be seen, mutual agreement of the activation properties for sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate particles is found in this study without application of a shape factor for the sodium chloride particles. For spherical particles, the dry particle volume can thus be calculated from

$$V_p = \frac{\pi}{6} D_p^3 \quad (3.8)$$

The sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate particles are assumed to be fully soluble in the droplets, so that the droplet solution salt (s : SC or AS) molality in either case can be calculated from

$$b_s = \frac{n_s}{m_w}, \quad n_s = \frac{m_s}{M_s} = \frac{\rho_s V_p}{M_s}, \quad m_w = (V - V_p) \rho_w, \quad V = \frac{\pi}{6} d^3 \quad (3.9)$$

n_s and m_s are the amount in moles and mass of salt in the dry particle, M_s and ρ_s the salt molar mass and density, and V_p the dry particle volume given in 3.8. m_w is the mass of water in a droplet of size d , and V the droplet volume. The droplets are assumed to be spherical, which must be reasonable since they are liquid.

The respective water solubilities of sodium chloride [67, pp.4-84], [67, pp.8-135] and ammonium sulfate [67, pp.4-42], [67, pp.8-135] are

$$C_{SC}^{sol} = 36.0 \text{ g/100 g } H_2O \text{ or } b_{SC}^{sol} = 6.153 \text{ mol/kg } H_2O \text{ (25}^\circ\text{C)} \quad (3.10)$$

and

$$C_{AS}^{sol} = 76.4 \text{ g/100 g } H_2O \text{ or } b_{AS}^{sol} = 5.790 \text{ mol/kg } H_2O \text{ (25}^\circ\text{C)} \quad (3.11)$$

In table 3.3 below, calculations show that the droplet solution molal concentrations at activation range between $b_c^{SC} \in [0.0294-0.1218]$ mol/kg and $b_c^{AS} \in [0.0207-0.1592]$ mol/kg for the dry particle sizes in question. Consequently, the particles must be fully dissolved at activation and the assumption of full solubility is therefore valid in this case.

The droplet solution water activity a_w and surface tension σ are concentration dependent and have been parameterized as functions of sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate molality.

The sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate solution water activities a_w^{SC} and a_w^{AS} are parameterized as functions of the respective molal concentrations b_{SC} and b_{AS} by fitting water activity data for different concentrations from Low [71] to 3rd order polynomials.

$$a_w^{SC} = 1 - 0.031715b_{SC} - 0.0012582b_{SC}^2 - 2.2921 \cdot 10^{-5}b_{SC}^3 \quad (3.12)$$

$$a_w^{AS} = 1 - 0.039767b_{AS} + 0.0079808b_{AS}^2 - 0.0022641b_{AS}^3 \quad (3.13)$$

The considerations involved in arriving at the particular parameterization expressions and the corresponding validity ranges are described in appendix B.2. The water activity data reported by Low [71] appear to be calculated by an equation corresponding to 2.60, using the molal osmotic coefficients for sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate solutions, measured at different concentrations at 25°C, listed in Robinson and Stokes [86, pp.483,488].

Kreidenweis et al. [61] have investigated a number of empirical and theoretical models of water activity for aqueous solutions of both sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate and their application to prediction of activation properties of sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate particles; it is found that the results of using the various water activity descriptions mutually agree, albeit with some variation. Thus, some of these water activity models for ammonium sulfate solutions have been compared to parameterization 3.13.

Tang and Munkelwitz [102] parameterize ammonium sulfate solution water activity a_w^{AS} as function of ammonium sulfate mass percent in solution $X_{AS}^m \equiv \frac{m_{AS}}{m_w} \cdot 100\%$ (m_{AS} and m_w are the masses of ammonium sulfate and water in solution, respectively) based on electrodynamic balance measurements (see section 4.1.3) at subsaturation conditions ($RH < 100\%$). Young and Warren [109] have parameterized the ammonium sulfate van't Hoff factor i_{AS} as function of ammonium sulfate solution molality b_{AS} using both tabulated and modeled values of the ammonium sulfate mean ionic activity coefficient γ_{\pm} . The ammonium sulfate van't Hoff factor i_{AS} has also been parameterized as function of ammonium sulfate molality b_{AS} by Merete Bilde (private communication) based on the van't Hoff factor values reported by Low [71], which corresponds to the water activities used for obtaining parameterization 3.13. This expression is used for activation calculations in chapter 4. All three parameterizations yield water activity descriptions very close to the one developed here for the ammonium sulfate molal concentration range $b_{AS} \in [0 - 1.0]$ mol/kg (see appendix A.4).

Both sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate raise the solution surface tension upon dissolution [84]. The concentration dependent surface tensions σ^{SC} and σ^{AS} of sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate solutions have been estimated as linear functions of the respective molal concentrations b_{SC} and b_{AS} from Low [71], who concludes from measured data available in literature, that the surface tension increases approximately linearly over the whole solubility range for both sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate solutions.

$$\sigma^{SC} = \sigma_w + 0.0016625b_{SC} = 0.07275 + 0.0016625b_{SC} \quad (3.14)$$

$$\sigma^{AS} = \sigma_w + 0.0021875b_{AS} = 0.07275 + 0.0021875b_{AS} \quad (3.15)$$

It should be noted, that the sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate solution surface tensions could be calculated more exactly using the parameterizations of Yu et al. [110], which also account for the surface tension temperature dependence that has been ignored here. Nevertheless, as seen immediately below, it is found that the solution droplets are sufficiently dilute at the point of activation, that the sensitivity of the

calculated activation to the functional form of the surface tension expression can be disregarded in the present case.

Other parameter values used in the calculations of sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate particle Köhler curves are listed in table 3.2

parameter	value	unit	reference
T	298.15	K	-
R	8.314472	J/mol·K	[67, cover]
M_w	18.01528	g/mol	[67, pp.6-4]
ρ_w	997.0480(25°C)	kg/m ³	[67, pp.6-5]
σ_w	72.75(20°C)	mN/m	[67, pp.6-3]
M_{SC}	58.443	g/mol	[67, pp.4-84]
ρ_{SC}	2170	kg/m ³	[67, pp.4-84]
M_{AS}	132.141	g/mol	[67, pp.4-42]
ρ_{AS}	1770	kg/m ³	[67, pp.4-42]

Table 3.2: Parameter values used in calculations of activation of sodium chloride (SC) and ammonium sulfate (AS) particles. Symbols are explained in the text.

The calculated critical supersaturation values $SS_c(\text{calc})$ for sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate particles are listed in table 3.3. The sensitivity of the calculations to variation in selected parameter values is investigated in appendix B.2. It is seen, that the Köhler curve shapes are somewhat sensitive to the variations in the functional form of the water activity parameterization a_w , especially for the smaller salt molalities b_s . Therefore, in particular the resulting critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{calc})$ are affected by the water activity parameterization expressions. The calculated critical supersaturations are also somewhat sensitive to the perturbations in the values used for the dry particle diameter D_p and the temperature T of a magnitude believed to reflect the variation in these parameters present during experiments. On the other hand, the resulting $SS_c(\text{calc})$ are not very sensitive to the variation in the water density value $\rho_w(T)$ resulting from the experimental temperature perturbations, or to the precise functional form solution surface tension parameterization σ used. In the latter case, the reason is believed to be the rather dilute state of the solution droplets predicted at activation, as seen by the values of $b_{sc}(\text{calc})$ in table 3.3 below. This notable dilution also lends justification to the original assumption from section 2.3.2 of substituting the water molar volume in solution v_w^{sol} for the pure water value v_w^0 in the Kelvin equation 2.80.

The Calibration Relation

As mentioned, the measured and corresponding calculated critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{meas})$ and $SS_c(\text{calc})$ for sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate particles are listed in table 3.3. To facilitate assessment of the return of the respective measurement and calculation procedures, the standard deviations $\sigma_{SS_c(\text{meas})}$ for the measured values from fitting the activation curves, as well as the calculated water activities $a_{wc}(\text{calc})$, surface

tensions $\sigma_c(\text{calc})$ and concentrations $b_c(\text{calc})$ at the Köhler curve critical points, have been included in the table. It must be stressed that the number of digits depicting the different values is only for the benefit of comparison and to avoid loss of generality along the data treatment chain and should therefore not be attributed any physical significance in terms of precision of the values in question.

measurement	$SS_c(\text{meas})$ [%]	$\sigma_{SS_c(\text{meas})}$	$SS_c(\text{calc})$ [%]	$a_{w_c}(\text{calc})$	$\sigma_c(\text{calc})$ [mN/m]	$b_c(\text{calc})$ [mol/kg]
27 nm SC	1.0761	0.0055	0.7822	0.9961	72.95	0.1218
28 nm SC	1.1015	0.0113	0.7405	0.9963	72.94	0.1153
30 nm SC	0.9545	0.0066	0.6675	0.9967	72.92	0.1040
32 nm SC	0.8324	0.0051	0.6058	0.9970	72.91	0.0945
35 nm SC	0.7409	0.0049	0.5295	0.9974	72.89	0.0828
37 nm SC	0.6794	0.0048	0.4870	0.9976	72.88	0.0762
40 nm SC	0.6271	0.0030	0.4332	0.9978	72.86	0.0678
50 nm SC	0.4647	0.0044	0.3098	0.9985	72.83	0.0486
60 nm SC	0.3534	0.0048	0.2356	0.9988	72.81	0.0370
70 nm SC	0.3012	0.0030	0.1869	0.9991	72.80	0.0294
27 nm AS	1.6958	0.0143	1.1838	0.9939	73.10	0.1592
28 nm AS	1.5923	0.0107	1.1197	0.9942	73.08	0.1501
30 nm AS	1.4627	0.0088	1.0076	0.9948	73.04	0.1341
35 nm AS	0.9302	0.0092	0.7966	0.9959	72.98	0.1047
40 nm AS	0.7952	0.0094	0.6503	0.9967	72.94	0.0848
50 nm AS	0.7155	0.0102	0.4638	0.9976	72.88	0.0599
60 nm AS	0.5993	0.0052	0.3522	0.9982	72.85	0.0452
70 nm AS	0.4632	0.0035	0.2791	0.9986	72.83	0.0356
80 nm AS	0.4282	0.0079	0.2282	0.9989	72.81	0.0291
90 nm AS	0.3881	0.0033	0.1912	0.9990	72.80	0.0243
100 nm AS	0.3263	0.0036	0.1631	0.9992	72.80	0.0207

Table 3.3: Measured and calculated critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{meas})$ and $SS_c(\text{calc})$ for sodium chloride (SC) and ammonium sulfate (AS) particles used to attain the calibration relation for the Cloud Condensation Nucleus Counter (CCNC) in equation 3.16. Also listed are the standard deviations $\sigma_{SS_c(\text{meas})}$ on the measured critical supersaturations from fitting the activation curves and the calculated droplet solution water activities $a_{w_c}(\text{calc})$, surface tensions $\sigma_c(\text{calc})$ and molalities $b_c(\text{calc})$ at the Köhler curve critical points. The number of digits included is strictly for the sake of comparison.

The measured critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{meas})$ are plotted as function of the corresponding calculated values $SS_c(\text{calc})$ for each particle composition and size in fig. 3.10. It is seen, that two points depicted by symbol "o" deviate somewhat from the near-linear relation of the remainder; these points originate from the activation measurements of 35 nm and 40 nm ammonium sulfate particles, which were made on the same day, and were the only measurements made on that day. It is possible that some error or change in the experimental conditions has occurred on this day. Therefore, the

particular points have been omitted from the basis of the calibration relation. Linear regression then yields the calibration curve as plotted in fig. 3.10 with the equation

$$SS_c(\text{meas}) = 0.0734 + 1.3453SS_c(\text{calc}) , R^2 = 0.9982 \quad (3.16)$$

Figure 3.10: The CCNC calibration curve: Relation between measured and calculated critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{meas})$ and $SS_c(\text{calc})$ for sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate particles used to calibrate the fitted results from the CCNC measurements. The two points depicted with symbol "o" are not included in the regression basis.

All critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{meas})$ determined from the activation curves fitted to CCNC measurements are thus calibrated according to 3.16 by

$$SS_c(\text{calibr}) = -0.0546 + 0.7433SS_c(\text{meas}) \quad (3.17)$$

These calibrated values $SS_c(\text{calibr})$ are the final outcome of the data treatment chain applied to the measurements and will be interpreted as the experimentally determined critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{exp})$.

It should be noted, that the points originating from measurements of both sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate particles lie approximately on the same line in fig. 3.10, whence the practice of not applying a shape factor in the sodium chloride particle activation calculations appears to be justified.

3.3 Experimental Error Estimates

Owing to the nature of the activation measurements and the construction of the calibration curve, standard expressions for calculation of random errors on experimental values obtained from calibration relations do not strictly apply to the critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{exp})$ determined from the experimental and subsequent raw data treatment procedure described above. For this work, the experimental errors are therefore determined from an expression based on the general formula for propagation of uncertainty, derived in the following as suggested by Bo Svensmark (private communication).

The calibration curve in fig. 3.10 has been obtained by linear regression of the calibration points (x_i, y_i) using the method of least squares [73, pp.114-115]. The calibration point coordinates are here the corresponding pairs of calculated and measured sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate particle critical supersaturations $x_i = SS_c(\text{calc})$ and $y_i = SS_c(\text{meas})$. The least squares regression method involves minimizing the y-residuals $y_i - \hat{y}_i$, which are the differences between the resulting calibration curve value \hat{y}_i and the calibration point y_i -coordinate for a given x_i -coordinate, and thus employs the assumption that all error resides in the calibration point y_i -coordinate [73, pp.110]. In this case, the intercept of the regression line with functional expression

$$y = a + bx \quad (3.18)$$

is given by [73, pp.115]

$$a = \bar{y} - b\bar{x} \quad (3.19)$$

where b is the regression line slope and \bar{x} and \bar{y} are the (arithmetic) means of the calibration point coordinates [73, pp.20]

$$\bar{x} = \sum_i \frac{x_i}{n}, \quad \bar{y} = \sum_i \frac{y_i}{n} \quad (3.20)$$

Here, n is the number of calibration points (x_i, y_i) used for evaluating the regression line. Inserting equation 3.19 into 3.18 gives

$$y = (\bar{y} - b\bar{x}) + bx \quad (3.21)$$

The calibration relation 3.16 is employed to obtain the calibrated critical supersaturation $x_0^{cal} = SS_c(\text{calibr})$ from the corresponding value $y_0^{cal} = SS_c(\text{meas})$ determined by fitting the activation measurements to the sigmoidal function 3.6. (Note that the values x_0^{cal} and y_0^{cal} being related upon calibration are *not* identical to the parameters x_0^{fit} and y_0^{fit} of the sigmoidal fitting function 3.6, for which $SS_c(\text{meas}) = x_0^{fit}$.) For a pair of values (x_0^{cal}, y_0^{cal}) thus related by the calibration curve, equation 3.21 specifically yields

$$y_0^{cal} = (\bar{y} - b\bar{x}) + bx_0^{cal} \Leftrightarrow x_0^{cal} = \frac{(y_0^{cal} - \bar{y})}{b} + \bar{x} \quad (3.22)$$

Assuming the variables y_0^{cal} , \bar{y} , b and \bar{x} are mutually independent, which is a necessary yet reasonable requirement for the following analysis, the partial derivatives of x_0^{cal} with

respect to each of these variables are

$$\frac{\partial x_0^{cal}}{\partial y_0^{cal}} = \frac{1}{b}, \quad \frac{\partial x_0^{cal}}{\partial \bar{y}} = \frac{-1}{b}, \quad \frac{\partial x_0^{cal}}{\partial b} = \frac{(y_0^{cal} - \bar{y})}{-b^2}, \quad \frac{\partial x_0^{cal}}{\partial \bar{x}} = 1 \quad (3.23)$$

In this work, the error on the final value of the experimental critical supersaturation $SS_c(\text{exp}) = SS_c(\text{calibr}) = x_0^{cal}$ is determined as the standard deviation of x_0^{cal} , denoted by $\sigma_{x_0^{cal}}$, which can be evaluated from the general formula for propagation of uncertainty [39, pp.AP3] as

$$\sigma_{x_0^{cal}}^2 = \left(\frac{\partial x_0^{cal}}{\partial y_0^{cal}} \right)^2 \sigma_{y_0^{cal}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial x_0^{cal}}{\partial \bar{y}} \right)^2 \sigma_{\bar{y}}^2 + \left(\frac{\partial x_0^{cal}}{\partial b} \right)^2 \sigma_b^2 + \left(\frac{\partial x_0^{cal}}{\partial \bar{x}} \right)^2 \sigma_{\bar{x}}^2 \quad (3.24)$$

Here, $\sigma_{y_0^{cal}}$, $\sigma_{\bar{y}}$, σ_b and $\sigma_{\bar{x}}$ are the individual errors in the variables y_0^{cal} , \bar{y} , b and \bar{x} ; application of the formula for propagation of uncertainty assumes that these individual errors are mutually independent [39, pp.AP3], which must apply if the variables themselves are independent.

$\sigma_{y_0^{cal}}$ is the standard deviation of the measured critical supersaturation to be calibrated $y_0^{cal} = SS_c(\text{meas}) = x_0^{fit}$ and is thus given as the standard deviation $\sigma_{x_0^{fit}}$ of the parameter x_0^{fit} determined upon fitting the sigmoidal function 3.6 to the measured activation ratios

$$\sigma_{y_0^{cal}} = \sigma_{x_0^{fit}} \quad (3.25)$$

$\sigma_{\bar{y}}$ is by definition the standard error of the mean \bar{y} [73, pp.29]

$$\sigma_{\bar{y}} \equiv \frac{\sigma_{y_i}}{\sqrt{n}} \quad (3.26)$$

where σ_{y_i} is the standard deviation of the calibration point values y_i . Due to the assumption imposed on the regression line, that all error in the calibration points resides with y_i , the corresponding standard error of the mean \bar{x} vanishes by definition of the regression line

$$\sigma_{\bar{x}} \equiv 0 \quad (3.27)$$

and σ_{y_i} equals the standard deviation $\sigma_{y/x}$ of the y -residuals given by [73, pp.116]

$$\sigma_{y_i} \equiv \sigma_{y/x} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_i (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{n - 2}} \quad (3.28)$$

The value of $\sigma_{y/x}$ is evaluated by the fitting program as part of the linear regression of the calibration points [5, pp.719].

The standard deviation on the regression line intercept is given as [73, pp.117]

$$\sigma_b = \frac{\sigma_{y/x}}{\sqrt{\sum_i (x_i - \bar{x})^2}} \quad (3.29)$$

Substituting the functional forms of the partial derivatives of x_0^{cal} given in equations 3.23 and the above identities 3.26-3.29 for the individual errors into equation 3.24 and rearranging, the expression for the standard deviation $\sigma_{x_0^{cal}}$ becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
\sigma_{x_0^{cal}}^2 &= \left(\frac{1}{b}\right)^2 \sigma_{y_0^{cal}}^2 + \left(\frac{-1}{b}\right)^2 \sigma_{\bar{y}}^2 + \left(\frac{y_0^{cal} - \bar{y}}{-b^2}\right)^2 \sigma_b^2 + \sigma_{\bar{x}}^2 \\
&= \frac{1}{b^2} \sigma_{y_0^{cal}}^2 + \frac{1}{b^2} \frac{\sigma_{y/x}^2}{n} + \frac{(y_0^{cal} - \bar{y})^2}{b^4} \frac{\sigma_{y/x}^2}{\sum_i (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \\
&= \frac{\sigma_{y/x}^2}{b^2} \left[\frac{\sigma_{y_0^{cal}}^2}{\sigma_{y/x}^2} + \frac{1}{n} + \frac{(y_0^{cal} - \bar{y})^2}{b^2 \sum_i (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \right] \Rightarrow \\
\sigma_{x_0^{cal}} &= \frac{\sigma_{y/x}}{b} \left[\frac{\sigma_{y_0^{cal}}^2}{\sigma_{y/x}^2} + \frac{1}{n} + \frac{(y_0^{cal} - \bar{y})^2}{b^2 \sum_i (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}
\end{aligned} \tag{3.30}$$

Equation 3.30 yields the standard deviation $\sigma_{x_0^{cal}} = \sigma_{SS_c(\text{exp})}$ on the final results $SS_c(\text{exp})$ of the particle activation experiments from the combination of the activation measurement fitting and the calibration procedures. The expression closely resembles the standard formula given by Miller and Miller [73, pp.118], which however deploys the unity value instead of the entry $\sigma_{y_0^{cal}}^2/\sigma_{y/x}^2$; in the present work, the error on the measured critical supersaturation value $SS_c(\text{meas})$ obtained from the sigmoidal fit is not the same for the calibration point coordinates y_i as for the measured values subsequently to be calibrated y_0^{cal} , due to the different experimental conditions of the activation measurements given by the different chemical nature of the constituents of the activating particles concerned.

For the specific particle compositions investigated in this study, the errors on the critical supersaturation values $SS_c(\text{meas}) = y_0^{cal}$ to be calibrated, measured for particles containing various organic compounds, are in general greater than the errors on the measured critical supersaturation values $SS_c(\text{meas}) = y_i$ for the sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate salt particles, which are used for obtaining the calibration curve

$$\sigma_{y_i} = \sigma_{y/x} < \sigma_{y_0^{cal}} \tag{3.31}$$

Disregarding the outliers in the calibration plot (fig. 3.10) omitted from the linear regression, the number of calibration points is $n = 19$, and the numerical value of the standard deviation on the y -residuals is given by the regression of the calibration points as $\sigma_{y/x} = 0.0398$. The entries $\bar{x} = 0.5246$, $\bar{y} = 0.7791$ and $\sum_i (x_i - \bar{x})^2 = 1.8388$ are likewise determined from the collection of calibration points and are therefore the same for all the experimental errors $\sigma_{x_0^{cal}}$ calculated from equation 3.30. The value of the regression line slope is given in equation 3.16 as $b = 1.3453$.

Thus, for each calibrated experimental critical supersaturation $SS_c(\text{exp})$ the resulting standard deviation $\sigma_{SS_c(\text{exp})}$ from the data treatment chain applied is evaluated by substituting the corresponding values of the measured critical supersaturation $SS_c(\text{meas}) = y_0^{cal} = x_0^{fit}$ and its standard deviation $\sigma_{SS_c(\text{meas})} = \sigma_{y_0^{cal}} = \sigma_{x_0^{fit}}$, as determined from the

sigmoidal fit to the measured activation ratios, into the expression for equation 3.30 where the specific values pertaining to the calibration have been applied

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{SS_c(\text{exp})} &= \frac{0.0398}{1.3453} \left[\frac{\sigma_{x_0^{fit}}^2}{0.0398^2} + \frac{1}{19} + \frac{(x_0^{fit} - 0.7791)^2}{1.3453^2 \cdot 1.8388} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &= 0.0296 \left[\frac{\sigma_{x_0^{fit}}^2}{0.0016} + 0.0526 + \frac{(x_0^{fit} - 0.7791)^2}{3.3279} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}\end{aligned}\quad (3.32)$$

Adopting the standard deviation $\sigma_{SS_c(\text{exp})}$ as expression for the error on the experimental critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{exp})$, the resulting estimate of the experimental uncertainty [73, pp.98] is determined as

$$U = 2\sigma_{SS_c(\text{exp})} \quad (3.33)$$

corresponding to the confidence limits [73, pp.29-30]

$$SS_c(\text{exp}) \pm 2\sigma_{SS_c(\text{meas})} \quad (3.34)$$

The implied confidence intervals [73, pp.29-30] for the values $SS_c(\text{exp})'$ of the experimental critical supersaturations are then

$$SS_c(\text{exp}) - 2\sigma_{SS_c(\text{meas})} < SS_c(\text{exp})' < SS_c(\text{exp}) + 2\sigma_{SS_c(\text{meas})} \quad (3.35)$$

which approximately equal the 95%-confidence intervals [73, pp.99]. These are the uncertainties depicted for the experimentally determined critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{exp})$ in this study. The determination of experimental errors for cloud droplet activation measurements is subject to various approaches [33], [84], [89] and is something that the Aerosol Group at the University of Copenhagen will continue to work on.

Chapter 4

Acid Dissociation and Water Activity

This chapter deals with the ability of aerosol particles containing polyfunctional organic acids to act as cloud condensation nuclei (CCN). In particular, the aim is to investigate the extent of dissociation of such acids in activating cloud droplets and to establish a proper description of the resulting droplet solution water activity for use in the theoretical prediction of the activation properties of polyfunctional acids.

Several studies have demonstrated that atmospheric aerosols can contain significant fractions, usually in the range 10-90% of the total aerosol mass, of organic compounds, [37], [93], [50], a considerable part of which tends to be water soluble to some extent [90], [37]. A typical distribution of different chemical compound classes in continental fine aerosol displaying an organic carbon content of 24% by mass is shown in fig. 4.1.

Figure 4.1: Example of a typical mass distribution of different chemical compound classes in continental fine aerosol, showing a significant fraction of 24% organic carbon. Adapted from a presentation given by Merete Bilde.

Due to the large number of different species present and circumstances concerning the analytical techniques for resolving polar compounds, many of these water soluble organic components of atmospheric aerosols remain to be identified [90]. Saxena and Hildemann [90] propose from considerations of water solubilities and water-air partitioning properties, that C2-C7 hydrocarbons substituted with two or more functional groups are likely candidates for the water soluble organic aerosol fraction. A number of species containing carboxylic and carbonyl groups have already been identified as constituents of atmospheric aerosols [56], [93], [54] and especially the dicarboxylic acids are proposed to make an important compound class for organic CCN activity [93], [25]. Possible sources of low molecular weight carboxylic acids in atmospheric aerosol particles are direct emissions [82], [37], photooxidation of gasphase precursors [82], [37], [26] and oxidation of preexisting organic aerosol content in the aqueous phase during cloud processing [26].

The dissolution of water soluble organic constituents in water condensed onto an aerosol particle and the possible subsequent dissociation of any acidic groups will affect the water activity of the resulting droplet solution and in turn the activation of the droplet through the shape of its Köhler curve. Empirically based water activity descriptions have been employed for growing droplets utilizing either van't Hoff factors [72], [61], osmolality measurements [57], [89] or water activity measurements performed directly on droplets with a so-called electrodynamic balance [19], [76]. The use of van't Hoff factors requires knowledge or an assumption of the identity and mutual interactions of the species in solution and in particular of the dissociation state of the dissolved solute. The van't Hoff factors of organic acids have thus often been presumed equal to unity [84], [62], [82] or determined by the total number n of acidic functional groups as $n + 1$ [23], corresponding to either no or full dissociation in solution. Osmolality and water activity are on the other hand measured as properties of a solution and require no preceding knowledge of the solution constituents but yield no information of the individual interactions either.

Rosenørn et al. [89] showed for homologous series of mono- and disaccharides, respectively, that water activity descriptions employing either direct electrodynamic balance measurements, measured osmolalities or van't Hoff factors of unity all gave very good predictions of particle activation. This has invited the investigation of whether such agreements between measured and predicted activation are maintained for particles containing polyfunctional acids, where some dissociation must occur in the droplet solutions and the van't Hoff factors therefore cannot immediately be equaled to unity.

4.1 Method and Procedure

For particles containing selected polyfunctional organic acids, the activation is both measured with the CCNC and calculated from Köhler theory, employing different water activity parameterizations obtained from literature values of van't Hoff factors, osmolalities and electrodynamic balance water activity measurements.

4.1.1 Choice of Compounds

Citric acid (fig. 4.2) and L-malic acid (fig. 4.3) are two polyfunctional organic acids believed to be relevant for atmospheric aerosols and have therefore been chosen for the investigation of the cloud droplet activation properties of this compound class.

Citric acid is a C6 hydroxyl substituted tricarboxylic acid and L-malic acid is a C4 hydroxyl substituted dicarboxylic acid; thus, both acids fall under the description "short-chain polyfunctional organic" and have been proposed by Saxena and Hildemann [90] to be sufficiently non-volatile and water soluble to be likely candidates for the water soluble organic fraction of atmospheric aerosols. L-malic acid has been found in urban aerosols in Tokyo [93] as well as in aerosols collected at Antarctica [54]. Both citric and L-malic acid have been identified in marine water by the Atlantic coast [21] and subsequently hypothesized to exist in sea salt particles due to the nature of their formation processes [74], [105].

Citric and L-malic acid are both rather water soluble [90], and crude estimations based on their first dissociation constants $pK_{a,1}$ [67, pp.8-51,8-48] show that dissociation can be expected in activating droplets of the order of 10% and 5%, respectively.

Figure 4.2: Citric acid (CA).

Figure 4.3: Malic acid (MA).

Particles consisting of pure citric and L-malic acid have been investigated to determine the activation properties of the acids in their own right. Since atmospheric particles often contain significant fractions of both organic and inorganic material [37], [75] particles with binary compositions comprising each of the acids mixed with salt have likewise

been studied. For the salt was chosen ammonium sulfate to avoid complications concerning the possible need for application of particle shape factors [61].

The abbreviations CA, MA and AS will be used throughout the chapter for citric acid, L-malic acid and ammonium sulfate, respectively, and L-malic acid will from here on simply be referred to as malic acid. Subscripts a , s and w will alternatively denote properties of organic acid, salt and water; finally, dry particles are indicated with subscript p , whereas none is used for droplets.

4.1.2 Experimental

Particles were generated as described in section 3.1.2 composed of pure citric acid, mixed citric acid and ammonium sulfate, pure malic acid and mixed malic acid and ammonium sulfate, respectively. In each case, the precise composition in terms of mass percentages of acid and salt $X_{p,a}^m$ and $X_{p,s}^m$ was calculated from the respective masses of acid and salt m_a^w and m_s^w used for preparing the solution in the atomizer bottle with equation 3.5. The weighed acid and salt masses and resulting particle compositions are given in table 4.1.

particle composition	pure CA	mixed CA/AS	pure MA	mixed MA/AS
$X_{p,a}^m$ [%]	100	78.30	100	80.44
$X_{p,s}^m$ [%]	-	21.70	-	19.56
m_a^w [g]	0.1217	0.1081	0.1000	0.1032
m_s^w [g]	-	0.0299	-	0.0251

Table 4.1: Experimental particle compositions in terms of mass percentages X_p^m of citric acid (CA), malic acid (MA) and ammonium sulfate (AS), as well as the weighed compound masses m^w originally dissolved upon preparation of the solution in the atomizer bottle, from which the mass percentage values were determined.

Activation of the generated particles was measured as described in section 3.1.3 for dry particle diameters $D_p \in [30 - 130]$ nm over a supersaturation range of $SS \in [0.2 - 2.5]$ % (as reported by the CCNC, see sections 3.1.1 and 3.2.2). For each particle composition and selected dry size D_p , the measured activation ratios f_{act} were subsequently fitted as function of the supersaturation SS by the 4-parameter sigmoidal function 3.6 according to the procedure outlined in section 3.2.1. Finally, the measured critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{meas})$ achieved from the fits were calibrated using equation 3.17, thus yielding the experimental critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{exp})$ reported in section 4.2. Here, the experimental critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{exp})$ are accompanied by estimates of the combined errors from the activation curve fitting and calibration procedures, as expounded in section 3.3.

4.1.3 Calculations

For the particle compositions concerned, the critical supersaturations were calculated for dry particle diameters over the range $D_p \in [30-130]$ nm by iterating the maximum of the appropriate Köhler curves, as given by equation 2.84. Such calculated values will be called the theoretical critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$. Since the experimental critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{exp})$ are reported in [%], the Köhler equation was applied in the form that proportionately yields the theoretical critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$ in [%]

$$SS = \left(a_w \exp \left(\frac{4M_w\sigma}{RT\rho_w d} \right) - 1 \right) \cdot 100\% \quad (4.1)$$

Here, SS denote the equilibrium supersaturation of a solution droplet with diameter d , and each Köhler curve is evaluated for the droplet diameter interval $d \in [1.5D_p - 1.5D_p + 1000]$ nm. M_w and ρ_w are the molar mass and mass density of water, R and T the gas constant and temperature, and a_w and σ are the droplet solution water activity and liquid/air surface tension.

General Considerations

A number of considerations that apply to all calculations performed for the acid containing particles are mentioned here, then the individual calculations pertaining to various aspects of the theoretical approach will be discussed.

By employing the Köhler equation 4.1, which describes the equilibrium conditions for a growing droplet, any kinetic limitations to the droplet growth are consequently neglected. Choi and Chan [20] and Prenni et al. [82] mention the possible influence of limited mass transfer on particle hygroscopic growth at subsaturation and cloud droplet activation at supersaturation conditions, respectively. Such effects have not been investigated for the present study, but are subject to ongoing research, including by the Aerosol Group at the University of Copenhagen.

In calculations, the compounds used are assumed to be devoid of impurities from either manufacturing or contamination. It is believed that since all constituents of the investigated particles are very water soluble (see below), small amounts of impurities will not affect the activation properties as observed by Bilde and Svenningsson [14] for particles comprising slightly soluble organics. Furthermore, chemical reactions of dissolved species in the activating droplets formed on mixed composition particles shall not be addressed in the present work. Ervens et al. [25] (and references herein) point out the possible formation of carboxylate salts with lower solubility than the original acids and inorganic salts. Such organic salts would affect CCN properties by precipitating in activating droplets, thereby reducing the Raoult effect. It is thus assumed that carboxylate salts of reduced solubility do not form from citric and malic acid and ammonium sulfate in the particles investigated. There is no indications from the experimental results presented in section 4.2 that both assumptions are not valid for the present case.

Both dry particles and growing droplets are assumed to be spherical [84], [62], [108]

and can thus be parameterized solely in terms of the respective diameters D_p and d . The dry particle and droplet volumes were consequently calculated as

$$V_p = \frac{\pi}{6} D_p^3, \quad V = \frac{\pi}{6} d^3 \quad (4.2)$$

The dry particle physical diameter is equated to the electrical mobility diameter selected in the DMA $D_p = D_p^{EM}$; it is thus implicitly assumed that no shape factor needs to be applied for the particles and that no subsequent evaporation occurs in the flow system between the DMA and the CCNC. This appears to be justified by the experimental results, but would strictly need to be justified by examination.

Additivity of volumes has been assumed, also for both the dry particles and the growing droplet solutions. In the first case, this means that the mass density of a mixed composition dry particle can be determined from the mass densities of its pure constituents ρ_a and ρ_s , each weighed by their respective mass fractions in the dry particle, $x_{p,a}^m$ and $x_{p,s}^m$, as given by equation 3.5 [14], [42], [16]

$$\rho_p = \left(\frac{x_{p,a}^m}{\rho_a} + \frac{x_{p,s}^m}{\rho_s} \right)^{-1} \quad (4.3)$$

In the latter case, the volume of water in a droplet solution was consequently calculated as the difference between the droplet and dry particle volumes [16], [61]

$$V_w = V - V_p \quad (4.4)$$

This is essentially an assumption of solution ideality [13, pp.902] and therefore not strictly valid, however the effect is likely negligible. Non-ideal solution effects are discussed in section 4.2.3.

Both citric and malic acid are highly water soluble; Apelblat and Manzurola [10] found the solubilities (superscript *sol*) at 298.15 K in terms of saturated solution mole fractions to be $x_{CA}^{n, sol} = 0.1321$ and $x_{MA}^{n, sol} = 0.1578$. These values can be converted using the molar masses for water, citric and malic acid given by Apelblat and Manzurola [10] into $C_{CA}^{sol} = 162.3$ g/100 g H_2O and $C_{MA}^{sol} = 139.4$ g/100 g H_2O , consistent with the values reported by Peng et al. [77] and Saxena and Hildemann [90]. The solubility of ammonium sulfate is $C_{AS}^{sol} = 76.4$ g/100 g H_2O [67, pp.4-42]. Thus, all compounds are assumed to be fully soluble in the droplet solutions, the molal concentrations of which can then for each solute (subscript s : CA, MA, AS) be calculated by

$$b_s = \frac{n_s}{m_w}, \quad n_s = \frac{m_s}{M_s}, \quad m_s = x_s^m m_p, \quad m_p = \rho_p V_p, \quad m_w = \rho_w V_w \quad (4.5)$$

n_s and m_s are the amount in moles and mass of the solute in question present in the dry particle, and M_s its molar mass. x_s^m is the dry particle mass fraction of the solute, determined by eq. 3.5 from the experimentally weighed amounts of the different dry particle constituents; it is thus implicitly assumed that the weighed compounds have 100% purity. m_p , ρ_p (from eq. 4.3) and V_p (from eq. 4.2) are the mass, density and

volume of the dry particle, and m_w , ρ_w and V_w (from eq. 4.4) are the mass, density and volume of water in the droplet. The molar solute concentrations can be calculated similarly as $c_s = n_s/V$, where V is the droplet volume.

Citric and malic acid both lower the solution surface tension slightly [68], [48], whereas ammonium sulfate on the other hand increases surface tension [71]. Since none of the compounds are however very surface active, and the droplet solutions at activation are expected to be rather dilute (recalling the findings for sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate presented in section 3.2.2 and appendix B.2), the resulting surface tension effects are assumed to be small and the solution surface tension has been approximated to that of water $\sigma \approx \sigma_w$.

The temperature was set to $T = 298.15$ K in all calculations, which is believed to be representative of the average ambient temperature in the laboratory during conduction of the experiments. This coincided with a period of warm weather where, due to extensive building reconstruction, the air condition system was turned off and the whole building section comprising the laboratory was enveloped in plastic. Therefore, this relatively high average ambient temperature is believed to be appropriate. In addition, many of the remainder parameter values adopted from literature are reported at $T = 298.15$ K.

At the heart of this chapter are the properties and description of the water activity a_w in the activating droplets. Calculations were therefore performed using three different parameterizations of the water activity as function of concentration in a growing droplet, based on van't Hoff factors, osmolality and direct water activity measurements, respectively.

Varying the Acid Van't Hoff Factor

The water activity has been parameterized in terms of the van't Hoff factors i_a and i_s of the dry particle acid and salt constituents according to equations 2.52 and 2.53 [89], [42] for pure acid and mixed acid/salt particles, respectively

$$a_w = \frac{n_w}{n_w + i_a n_a}, \quad a_w = \frac{n_w}{n_w + i_a n_a + i_s n_s} \quad (4.6)$$

n_w , n_a and n_s are the amounts in moles of water, acid and salt in the growing droplet solution.

Calculations were performed for each dry particle composition with different acid van't Hoff factors $i_a = [0.3; 0.4; 0.5; 0.6; 0.7; 0.8; 0.9; 1.0; 1.1; 1.2; 1.3; 1.4; 1.5; 1.6; 1.7]$, in each case kept constant over the whole droplet solution concentration range. For the mixed acid/salt particles, the ammonium sulfate van't Hoff factor was applied in two ways; first assigned a constant value of $i_{AS} = 2.2$ and second as a concentration dependent parameterization. The parameterization of the ammonium sulfate van't Hoff factor in the ammonium sulfate droplet solution molality b_{AS} was achieved by fitting the values reported by Low [71] for the concentration range $b_{AS} \in [0.1 - 5.5]$ mol/kg to a 5th order

polynomial function (private communication, Merete Bilde)

$$i_{AS} = -0.002b_{AS}^5 + 0.032b_{AS}^4 - 0.197b_{AS}^3 + 0.5997b_{AS}^2 - 0.8431b_{AS} + 2.3552 \quad (4.7)$$

It should be noted, that the ammonium sulfate van't Hoff factors reported by Low [71] used for parameterization 4.7 are calculated with the same data from which the ammonium sulfate solution water activities applied in the parameterization 3.13 are attained [71] and therefore strictly pertain to aqueous solutions containing ammonium sulfate as the sole solute. Thus, application of the parameterization 4.7 in the mixed particle calculations is valid only under the assumption that the acid and salt solutes do not interact in the droplet solution. The reason that parameterization 3.13 is not directly applied here, is the need to account for the presence of both acid and salt in the droplet solutions resulting from the mixed composition particles, which is achieved through the water activity parameterization 4.6. The constant value of $i_{AS} = 2.2$ has been chosen as an educated guess of an effective average of the parameterized values over the droplet solution concentration range in question. Wise et al. [108] correspondingly uses a constant value of $i_{AS} = 2.31$.

Osmolality

In terms of the droplet solution osmolality b_{osm} , water activity was parameterized according to equation 2.54 [89], [57]

$$a_w = \frac{M_w^{-1}}{M_w^{-1} + b_{osm}} \quad (4.8)$$

where M_w is the molar mass of water reported in units of [kg/mol]. Solution osmolality can be determined from measurements of the freezing point depression or vapor pressure deficit, two of the colligative properties, of the solution [59], or the osmolality can be measured directly by a so-called osmometer, which essentially measures the amount of heat released by condensation of water vapor onto an aqueous solution droplet as a consequence of the droplet's vapor pressure deficit compared to pure water [1].

Weast and Astle [107, pp.D-272] lists measured osmolalities $b_{osm}^{CA} \in [0.028-2.285]$ Osm/kg for aqueous solutions of citric acid with molal concentrations $b_{CA} \in [0.0261-2.2312]$ mol/kg. These data were fitted by a 4th order polynomial function with the constraint $b_{osm}^{CA}(b_{CA} = 0) = 0$, yielding a parameterization of solution osmolality as a function of molality for aqueous citric acid solutions

$$b_{osm}^{CA} = -0.0060105b_{CA}^4 - 0.0022520b_{CA}^3 + 0.029392b_{CA}^2 + 1.0352b_{CA} \quad (4.9)$$

The attainment of the parameterization expression is described in appendix A.1. Since osmolality data has not been available for aqueous solutions of other compounds relevant to this study, activation calculations using this water activity parameterization were only made for pure citric acid particles.

Electro Dynamic Balance

Several techniques are available for direct measurements of water activity, which can then be parameterized as function of solution concentration for use in activation calculations.

The concentration dependent water activity of droplet solutions can be measured at subsaturation conditions ($RH < 100\%$) for either a collection of droplets in a hygroscopic tandem differential mobility analyzer (HTDMA) [61], [99], [100], or for a single droplet using an electrodynamic balance (EDB) [19], [76]. In both cases, the solution concentration is determined from the droplet growth to attain its equilibrium size at a given relative humidity RH , which is related to the water activity through the combination of equations 2.38 and 2.41, with possible correction for the Kelvin effect (see section 2.3.2).

The EDB method seems promising for application to aerosol activation properties, since it involves water activity measurements directly on single droplets and thus does not concern either bulk solutions or average properties of a collection of droplets [19]. Furthermore, the measurements pertain directly to droplet mass and does not require an assumption of droplet solution density, which must be made when using the HTDMA technique. It should however be noted, that whereas HTDMA measurements can be performed with atmospheric aerosol samples, the EDB method applies to laboratory studies of solution droplets generated for the purpose.

The details of EDB water activity measurements are described in Peng and Chan [76] and Chan et al. [19]: A single charged droplet of approximate size $d \approx 20 \mu\text{m}$ is fixed in position by an AC field and balanced against gravity (levitated) with a DC field. The droplet condenses or evaporates water to attain the equilibrium water activity corresponding to a controlled RH . Ignoring the Kelvin effect due to the relatively large droplet size, the water activity and RH are related by equations 2.38 and 2.41. The size, and thus the amount of water in the droplet, at equilibrium is proportional to the DC voltage needed to levitate it, and so the equilibrium droplet concentration can be determined by comparison to a reference state of known RH and composition. The droplet concentration is given as the mass fraction of solute, here the respective organic acids, x_a^m defined as

$$x_a^m \equiv \frac{m_a}{m_a + m_w}, \quad x_w^m \equiv \frac{m_w}{m_a + m_w}, \quad x_a^m + x_w^m = 1 \quad (4.10)$$

where m_a and m_w are the respective masses of acid and water in the droplet and x_w^m is the corresponding droplet water mass fraction. The droplet acid solute mass fraction

can be converted to the acid molal droplet concentration b_a by

$$\begin{aligned}
 x_a^m &\equiv \frac{m_a}{m_a + m_w} \Leftrightarrow \\
 m_a &= x_a^m (m_a + m_w) \Rightarrow \\
 n_a &= \frac{x_a^m (m_a + m_w)}{M_a} \Rightarrow \\
 b_a &= \frac{n_a}{m_w} = \frac{x_a^m (m_a + m_w)}{m_w M_a} = \frac{x_a^m}{x_w^m M_a} \stackrel{(4.10)}{=} \frac{x_a^m}{(1 - x_a^m) M_a}
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.11}$$

where n_a and M_a denote the amount in moles and molar mass of the organic acid. Due to the rather concentrated droplet solutions in equilibrium at subsaturation conditions, the mass fraction scale is however convenient. It should be noted, that the droplets in the EDB measurements are 1-3 orders of magnitude larger than the droplets concerned in the present activation measurements, which are in addition performed at supersaturation conditions ($RH > 100\%$) where the droplets are far more dilute.

EDB water activity measurements have been performed for aqueous citric acid [78] and malic acid [77] solution droplets; the measurements are made at 25°C and cover the ranges $RH \in [5 - 90] \%$ for citric acid and $RH \in [5 - 93] \%$ for malic acid. The data has been made available on the web page <http://ihome.ust.hk/~keckchan/hygroscopic.html> (last accessed 23-08-2006) which also lists results from bulk measurements (see below), in the case of citric acid from several different studies. Using both bulk and EDB water activity measurements, the coverage for dilute solution concentrations is extended to $a_w = RH/100\% \in [0.0500 - 0.9961]$ and $a_w = RH/100\% \in [0.0400 - 0.9860]$, corresponding to the concentrations $x_{CA}^m \in [0.9167 - 0.0370]$ and $x_{MA}^m \in [0.9424 - 0.1189]$. The water activity has been parameterized as function of the citric and malic acid solution mass fractions x_{CA}^m and x_{MA}^m , respectively, by fitting the data to a 5th order polynomial for citric acid

$$a_w^{CA} = -3.7664x_{CA}^m{}^5 + 5.5603x_{CA}^m{}^4 - 3.4861x_{CA}^m{}^3 + 0.5844x_{CA}^m{}^2 - 0.13172x_{CA}^m + 1 \tag{4.12}$$

and to an 8th order polynomial for malic acid

$$\begin{aligned}
 a_w^{MA} &= 6.2131x_{MA}^m{}^8 - 0.46271x_{MA}^m{}^7 - 8.3046x_{MA}^m{}^6 - 1.7894x_{MA}^m{}^5 \\
 &\quad + 7.0823x_{MA}^m{}^4 - 3.5412x_{MA}^m{}^3 + 0.26506x_{MA}^m{}^2 - 0.10561x_{MA}^m + 1
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.13}$$

In both cases, the constraint $a_w(x^m = 0) = 1$ has been applied to obtain physically representative parameterizations. The fitting procedure was not straightforward, likely owing to the large solution concentration ranges involved and is described in more detail in appendix A.2.

Bulk Water Activity

For aqueous bulk solutions of known concentration, the water activity can be determined from measurement of the dew point of water vapor in equilibrium with the solution [78], [77]. The dew point T_d is the temperature for which the water vapor pressure reaches

saturation in the sense $p_w = p_w^0 \Rightarrow RH = 100\%$ according to equation 2.41. The initial saturation ratio or relative humidity can then be found from the saturation water vapor pressure temperature dependence $p_w^0(T)$ given by the Clausius-Clapeyron equation [92, pp.794], and the water activity is thus determined from equation 2.38. The water vapor pressure of the solution can also be measured directly by manometric methods [111], [22].

Since the water activity parameterizations using the collected bulk and EDB measurements above were not trivial to come by, and since cloud droplet activation involves dilute rather than the highly supersaturated droplet solutions of the EDB measurements, activation has also been calculated for pure citric acid particles using a water activity parametrization based only on the bulk measurements of various studies given by Peng et al. [78]. These bulk water activity measurements collectively cover the range $a_w = RH/100\% \in [0.779154 - 0.996120]$ corresponding to the citric acid solution mass fractions $x_{CA}^m \in [0.619909 - 0.037012]$. The water activity has been parameterized as a function of citric acid solution mass fraction x_{CA}^m by fitting the data to a 5th order polynomial function under the constraint $a_w(x_{CA}^m = 0) = 1$

$$a_w^{CA} = -1.6955x_{CA}^m{}^5 + 0.5201x_{CA}^m{}^4 + 0.06433x_{CA}^m{}^3 - 0.27781x_{CA}^m{}^2 - 0.078701x_{CA}^m + 1 \quad (4.14)$$

The details of obtaining the parameterization are given in appendix A.3.

Hydrous Particles

So far it has been assumed that the particles concerned are completely dry, i.e. anhydrous. However, in electro dynamic balance hygroscopic studies both citric and malic acid solution droplets have been observed to contain residual water, even when dried to relative humidities as low as 5% [78], [77]. The droplets absorb and desorb water continuously and reversibly [77] and thus do not display the hysteresis behavior of deliquescence and crystallization [92, pp.507], [45, pp.291] expected for dry crystalline solids, like anhydrous citric acid [78]. It is suggested that this behavior may be explained by strong interactions of the polar functional groups of citric and malic acid with water at the high solution supersaturations [77].

Peng et al. [78] observe that citric acid solution droplets contain 8% by mass of residual water at $RH = 5\%$, whereas Peng et al. [77] find that both citric and malic acid solution droplets contain 5% by mass residual water at the same RH . In the present study, the RH has been measured to be of similar magnitude in the aerosol production line before the DMA; to avoid exposing the detector to large amounts of particles, these RH measurements are not performed continuously during experiments, but the RH has been measured in the aerosol flow system on a regular basis with many different aerosols and has been in the range of a few % to 20% (private communication, Merete Bilde). Thus, there may be reason to suspect that the particles in our activation experiments are not completely dry. As mentioned earlier, however, the particles concerned in this study are at least an order of magnitude smaller than the droplets used in the hygroscopic EDB studies of Peng et al. [78] and Peng et al. [77] and thus the Kelvin effect will be

important for the particles in the present case. Also, the drying methods and times are different; in this study, particles are dried in diffusion driers within seconds, whereas the droplets in the EDB studies evaporate to attain equilibrium with an airflow of controlled RH over a period of tens of minutes [78], [77]. This may affect the structure and possible crystallization of the resulting dried particles.

Tentative calculations of particle activation have been made assuming in the acid fraction of the dried particles a residual water content by mass of $X_{CA, w}^m = 8\%$ for citric acid $X_{MA, w}^m = 5\%$ for malic acid. Peng et al. [78] note that the 8% by mass of residual water for citric acid corresponds to the stoichiometry of citric acid monohydrate $HOC(CO_2H)(CH_2CO_2H)_2 \cdot H_2O$; with the values of the molar masses of citric acid and water $M_{CA} = 192.124$ g/mol [67, pp.3-130] and $M_w = 18.01528$ g/mol [67, pp.6-4], this would formally be $X_{CA, w}^m = 8.6\%$. Still, since the residual water content of citric acid differs in Peng et al. [77], no assumptions of structure is made for the present calculations.

The densities of the dried hydrous particles have instead been calculated assuming volume additivity of acid and water in the hydrous acid fraction, analogously to equation 4.3. For hydrous particles of pure acid the density is then calculated as

$$\rho_p^{hy} = \left(\frac{x_{a, a}^m}{\rho_a} + \frac{x_{a, w}^m}{\rho_w} \right)^{-1} \quad (4.15)$$

where $x_{a, a}^m$ and $x_{a, w}^m$ are the mass fractions of acid and water in the dried hydrous particle and ρ_a and ρ_w are the respective densities of solid acid and liquid water. The densities used correspond to the state of the pure compound at the temperature of the calculations 25°C. The hydrous citric acid density calculated with $X_{CA, w}^m = 8\%$ from equation 4.15 using $\rho_{CA} = 1665$ kg/m³ [67, pp.3-130] and $\rho_w = 997.0480$ kg/m³ [67, pp.6-5] is $\rho_{p, CA}^{hy} = 1580$ kg/m³, compared to the citric acid monohydrate density $\rho_{CA}^{mh} = 1542$ kg/m³ [67, pp.3-130].

In mixed acid and ammonium sulfate particles with the original acid and salt mass fractions $x_{p, a}^m$ and $x_{p, s}^m$, the acid fraction is assumed to contain the same amount of residual water as observed for the pure acid particles. The hydrous particle density then becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_p^{hy} &= \left(\frac{x_{p, a}^m}{\left(\frac{x_{a, a}^m}{\rho_a} + \frac{x_{a, w}^m}{\rho_w} \right)^{-1}} + \frac{x_{p, s}^m}{\rho_s} \right)^{-1} \\ &= \left(\left(\frac{x_{a, a}^m}{\rho_a} + \frac{x_{a, w}^m}{\rho_w} \right) x_{p, a}^m + \frac{x_{p, s}^m}{\rho_s} \right)^{-1} \\ &= \left(\frac{x_{a, a}^m x_{p, a}^m}{\rho_a} + \frac{x_{a, w}^m x_{p, a}^m}{\rho_w} + \frac{x_{p, s}^m}{\rho_s} \right)^{-1} \end{aligned} \quad (4.16)$$

where $x_{a, a}^m$ and $x_{a, w}^m$ are the mass fractions of acid and water comprising the acid part $x_{p, a}^m$ of the hydrous mixed acid and salt particle.

For a hydrous particle of diameter D_p , the volume V_p is calculated as before from equation 4.2, which also gives the volume V of a droplet that has grown to size d . The mass of water in the droplet is assumed to be the sum of water condensed on the particle m_w^{cond} and residual water released by dissolution of the hydrous particle m_w^{hy} .

$$m_w = m_w^{cond} + m_w^{hy}, \quad m_w^{cond} = V_w^{cond} \rho_w, \quad V_w^{cond} = V - V_p \quad (4.17)$$

V_w^{cond} is the volume of water condensed on the particle to form the droplet, again determined by assuming volume additivity. The mass of residual water in the hydrous particle is calculated by

$$m_w^{hy} = x_{a,w}^m x_{p,a}^m m_p^{hy}, \quad m_p^{hy} = \rho_p^{hy} V_p \quad (4.18)$$

Here, m_p^{hy} is the mass of the hydrous particle.

Finally, the masses of acid and salt in the hydrous particle are calculated as

$$m_a^{hy} = x_{a,a}^m x_{p,a}^m m_p^{hy}, \quad m_s^{hy} = x_{p,s}^m m_p^{hy} \quad (4.19)$$

For the pure acid particles, m_w^{hy} and m_a^{hy} are calculated analogously to equations 4.18 and 4.19, putting $x_{p,a}^m = 1$.

The validity of the above assumptions is rather doubtful; it is neither given that the particles will form the same structure upon drying in our experiments as in the EDB studies, as mentioned, nor that water will be retained to the same degree in the mixed acid and ammonium sulfate particles as in those consisting otherwise of the pure acids. Also, the assumption of volume additivity of liquid water and dry acid in both pure acid and mixed acid and salt particles is likely a severe oversimplification, but the only option readily at hand. The hydrous particle calculations are merely intended as a tentative investigation of a possible effect.

Degree of Dissociation

As part of the activation calculations employing osmolality derived and directly measured water activity parameterizations, the acid dissociation degree at the point of activation (the critical point, subscript c) α_{ac} has been calculated; the procedure for this is described in principle in section 2.2.6. Citric acid has 3 carboxylic acid groups and malic acid has 2; the acid constants pK_{an} corresponding to the different dissociation steps are given in table 4.2.

citric acid	$pK_{CA,1}$	3.13	[67, pp.8-51]
	$pK_{CA,2}$	4.76	[67, pp.8-51]
	$pK_{CA,3}$	6.40	[67, pp.8-51]
malic acid	$pK_{MA,1}$	3.40	[67, pp.8-48]
	$pK_{MA,2}$	5.11	[67, pp.8-48]

Table 4.2: Acid constants for the stepwise dissociation of citric (CA) and malic (MA) acid.

It has been found that the equilibrium concentration of undissociated citric or malic acid at droplet activation determined from consideration of the full 3 or 2 dissociation steps is essentially the same as when only the first dissociation step is taken into account (see appendix B.3). To ease the calculations, this approximation has therefore been employed. The generalized first dissociation step of acid H_nA is according to equation 2.64

which gives the equilibrium conditions

$$[H_nA]_{eq} = [H_nA]_{in} - X_1, [H_{n-1}A^-]_{eq} = X_1, [H_3O^+]_{eq} = X_1 \quad (4.20)$$

and equilibrium concentration of undissociated acid $[H_nA]_{eq}$ can then be calculated from the first acid constant K_{a1}

$$\begin{aligned}
 K_{a1} &= \frac{[H_{n-1}A^-]_{eq}[H_3O^+]_{eq}}{[H_nA]_{eq}} = \frac{X_1^2}{[H_nA]_{in} - X_1} \Rightarrow \\
 X_1 &= \frac{-K_{a1} + \sqrt{K_{a1}^2 + 4K_{a1}[H_nA]_{in}}}{2}
 \end{aligned} \quad (4.21)$$

The initial concentration of acid before dissociation $[H_nA]_{in}$ is the acid molar concentration in the droplet at activation c_{ac} , which is calculated as

$$[H_nA]_{in} = c_{ac} = n_a/V_c \quad (4.22)$$

where n_a is the amount in moles of acid originating from the dry particle determined from equation 4.5 and V_c is the droplet volume at activation calculated from equation 4.2 using the droplet critical diameter d_c iterated along with the Köhler curve evaluation.

For comparison with the results of the activation calculations using the water activity parameterizations based on van't Hoff factors, the acid van't Hoff factor at activation i_{ac} is determined from the dissociation degree at activation α_{ac} , using equation 2.69

$$\alpha_a = \frac{i_a - 1}{N_a - 1} \Rightarrow i_a = \alpha_a(N_a - 1) + 1 \stackrel{N_a=2}{=} \alpha_a + 1 \quad (4.23)$$

Since only the first dissociation step is considered, the number of ions generated for each acid molecule that dissociates is set to $N_a = 2$ for both citric and malic acid. In principle, N_a depends on the equilibrium with succeeding dissociation steps and is therefore concentration dependent, whence its evaluation for each individual activating droplet would be somewhat cumbersome if all dissociation steps are taken into account. This is another reason for using the approximation concerned.

Parameter Values

The values used for the various parameters in the calculations described above are listed in table 4.3. T and R denote the temperature and the ideal gas constant. M_w , ρ_w , M_{CA} , ρ_{CA} , M_{MA} , ρ_{MA} , M_{AS} and ρ_{AS} are the molar mass and mass density of water, citric and malic acid and ammonium sulfate, respectively. The citric and malic acid and ammonium sulfate molar masses agree with those given by the respective manufacturers. The water mass density is specifically chosen at the temperature of the calculations $\rho_w = 997.0480(25^\circ\text{C}) \text{ kg/m}^3$ [67, pp.6-5], just as the pure water surface tension $\sigma_w = 71.98(25^\circ\text{C}) \text{ mN/m}$ has been interpolated from the values given in literature $\sigma_w = 72.75(20^\circ\text{C}) \text{ mN/m}$ [67, pp.6-3] and $\sigma_w = 71.20(30^\circ\text{C}) \text{ mN/m}$ [67, pp.6-3], assuming a linear temperature dependence between these values as a first order approximation [80, pp.12.11], [100]. Finally, $pK_{CA, 1}$, $pK_{CA, 2}$, $pK_{CA, 3}$, $pK_{MA, 1}$ and $pK_{MA, 2}$ are the 1st, 2nd and 3rd acid constant of citric acid and the 1st and 2nd acid constant of malic acid, as given in table 4.2.

The results of the calculated activation and related properties are presented in section 4.2.

parameter	value	unit	reference
T	298.15	K	-
R	8.314472	J/molK	[67, cover]
M_w	18.01528	g/mol	[67, pp.6-4]
ρ_w	997.0480	kg/m ³	[67, pp.6-5]
σ_w	71.98	mN/m	-
M_{CA}	192.124	g/mol	[67, pp.3-130]
ρ_{CA}	1665	kg/m ³	[67, pp.3-130]
$pK_{CA, 1}$	3.13		[67, pp.8-51]
$pK_{CA, 2}$	4.76		[67, pp.8-51]
$pK_{CA, 3}$	6.40		[67, pp.8-51]
M_{MA}	134.088	g/mol	[67, pp.3-352]
ρ_{MA}	1601	kg/m ³	[67, pp.3-352]
$pK_{MA,1}$	3.40		[67, pp.8-48]
$pK_{MA,2}$	5.11		[67, pp.8-48]
M_{AS}	132.141	g/mol	[67, pp.4-42]
ρ_{AS}	1770	kg/m ³	[67, pp.4-42]

Table 4.3: Parameter values used in calculations of activation and related properties for pure citric and malic acid and mixed acid and ammonium sulfate particles.

Calculations Sensitivity

The sensitivity of the theoretical critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$ calculated as described above to variations in selected experimental parameters have been investigated for a few cases.

Since all the activation calculations share the same basic structure, only applying different water activity parameterization approaches and assumptions of the dry particle acid content, the EDB water activity parameterization calculations, which have been performed for both pure citric and pure malic acid particles, are selected for the sensitivity test. The dry particle sizes 50 and 100 nm are considered as representative for the smaller and larger pure citric acid particles, respectively, whereas for pure malic acid particles the dry sizes selected are 40 and 80 nm.

The critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$ calculated with the EDB water activity parameterization for 50 and 100 nm pure citric acid particles were first tested for variations in the ambient temperature $\Delta T = \pm 5$ K, believed to cover the maximum variation occurring during conduction of the experiments, and in the dry particle diameter $\Delta D_p = \pm 1$ nm, representing the experimental uncertainty in the particle sizes selected by the DMA. It is seen that the calculated critical supersaturation values are not very sensitive to the given variations in neither the temperature nor the dry particle size (tables 4.4 and 4.5).

D_p^{CA}	$SS_c(\text{theo})$ [%]	$\frac{\Delta SS_c}{SS_c(\text{theo})}$ [%]	d_c [nm]	b_{CAc} [mol/kg]	a_{wc}
50 nm	0.7642		169.8	0.2277	0.9953
+1 nm	0.7400	-3.2	175.7	0.2179	0.9954
-1 nm	0.7898	3.3	164.1	0.2377	0.9951
100 nm	0.2559		533.6	0.0576	0.9986
+1 nm	0.2520	-1.5	542.0	0.0566	0.9986
-1 nm	0.2599	1.6	525.2	0.0586	0.9986

Table 4.4: Critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$, as well as droplet diameters d_c , citric acid molalities b_{CAc} and solution water activities a_{wc} at activation, calculated with the EDB water activity parameterization approach for 50 and 100 nm pure citric acid particles and for dry diameter variations of $\Delta D_p = \pm 1$ nm.

D_p^{CA}	T [K]	$SS_c(\text{theo})$ [%]	$\frac{\Delta SS_c}{SS_c(\text{theo})}$ [%]	d_c [nm]	b_{CAc} [mol/kg]	a_{wc}
50 nm	298.15	0.7642		169.8	0.2277	0.9953
	+5	0.7438	-2.7	171.9	0.2193	0.9954
	-5	0.7856	2.8	167.8	0.2362	0.9951
100 nm	298.15	0.2559		533.6	0.0576	0.9986
	+5	0.2495	-2.5	538.8	0.0559	0.9987
	-5	0.2627	2.7	528.3	0.0593	0.9986

Table 4.5: Critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$, as well as droplet diameters d_c , citric acid molalities b_{CAc} and solution water activities a_{wc} at activation, calculated with the EDB water activity parameterization approach for 50 and 100 nm pure citric acid particles with temperatures $T = 298.15 \pm 5$ K.

Next, the sensitivity of the EDB water activity parameterization activation calculations for 50 and 100 nm pure citric acid particles was tested for substituting the hydrous particle density ρ_p^{hy} calculated with equation 4.15 assuming volume additivity, for the citric acid monohydrate density ρ_{CA}^{mh} tabulated in Lide [67, 3-130]. Substitution of these particular hydrous particle densities only produces small variations in the calculated critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$ (table 4.6).

D_p^{CA}	ρ_p [kg/m ³]	$SS_c(\text{theo})$ [%]	$\frac{\Delta SS_c}{SS_c(\text{theo})}$ [%]	d_c [nm]	b_{CAc} [mol/kg]	a_{wc}
50 nm	1580(ρ_p^{hy})	0.8227		157.3	0.2508	0.9949
	1542(ρ_{CA}^{mh})	0.8334	1.3	155.2	0.2551	0.9948
100 nm	1580(ρ_p^{hy})	0.2744		496.7	0.0623	0.9985
	1542(ρ_{CA}^{mh})	0.2779	1.3	490.4	0.0633	0.9985

Table 4.6: Critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$, as well as droplet diameters d_c , citric acid molalities b_{CAc} and solution water activities a_{wc} at activation, calculated with the EDB water activity parameterization approach for 50 and 100 nm hydrous pure citric acid particles, using the hydrous particle density ρ_p^{hy} calculated with equation 4.15 and the tabulated citric acid monohydrate density ρ_{CA}^{mh} from Lide [67, 3-130].

For malic acid solutions, the surface tension σ_{MA} has been parameterized by Hyvärinen et al. [48] as function of both temperature T and solution composition in terms of malic acid mole fraction x_{MA}^n . The temperature dependence of the pure liquid malic acid surface tension σ_{MA}^l is

$$\frac{\sigma_{MA}^l}{[\text{mN/m}]} = 83.00 - 0.11 \frac{T}{K} \quad (4.24)$$

For aqueous solutions, the malic acid mole fraction is defined as

$$x_{MA}^n \equiv \frac{n_{MA}}{n_w} = x_{MA}^m \frac{M_w}{M_{MA}} \quad (4.25)$$

where x_{MA}^m is the corresponding malic acid mass fraction. The composition dependence of the malic acid aqueous solution surface tension σ_{MA} is given as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\sigma_{MA}}{[\text{mN/m}]} = & \frac{\sigma_w}{[\text{mN/m}]}(1 - x_{MA}^n) + \frac{\sigma_{MA}^l}{[\text{mN/m}]}x_{MA}^n \\ & - R \frac{T}{K} x_{MA}^n (1 - x_{MA}^n) \left[\frac{-0.052418}{x_{MA}^n + 0.005632(1 - x_{MA}^n)} + \frac{9.5337}{177.69x_{MA}^n + (1 - x_{MA}^n)} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (4.26)$$

This solution surface tension parameterization has been substituted for the pure water surface tension σ_w in the EDB water activity parameterization calculations for 40 and 80 nm pure malic acid particles. The resulting variation in the calculated critical supersaturations $\frac{\Delta SS_c}{SS_c(\text{theo})}$ is only moderate, and the surface tension at droplet activation σ_c is

not very different in the two cases (table C.1). Furthermore, the malic acid aqueous solution surface tension σ_{MA} given by equation 4.26 is believed to yield unrealistically low values of the calculated critical supersaturation $SS_c(\text{theo})$ for especially the smaller dry particles, since surfactant partitioning has not been accounted for in the calculations [97].

D_p^{MA}	σ	$SS_c(\text{theo})$	$\frac{\Delta SS_c}{SS_c(\text{theo})}$	d_c	b_{MAc}	a_{w_c}	σ_c
	[mN/m]	[%]	[%]	[nm]	[mol/kg]		[mN/m]
40 nm	σ_w	1.1679		121.6	0.4420	0.9944	71.98
	σ_{MA}	1.1224	-3.9	124.8	0.4077	0.9948	70.12
80 nm	σ_w	0.4070		338.6	0.1601	0.9979	71.98
	σ_{MA}	0.3978	-2.3	346.9	0.1487	0.9980	70.93

Table 4.7: Critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$, as well as droplet diameters d_c , malic acid molalities b_{MAc} and solution water activity a_{w_c} and surface tension σ_c at activation, calculated with the EDB water activity parameterization approach for 40 and 80 nm pure malic acid particles, using a constant surface tension equal to the value for pure water σ_w and the malic acid aqueous solution surface tension σ_{MA} from equation 4.26 given by Hyvärinen et al. [48].

The critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$ calculated with the EDB water activity parameterization approach for the selected pure citric and malic acid particle sizes are not very sensitive to the specific variations applied to any of the parameters investigated above. The results of the activation calculations evaluated with the perturbed parameter values diverge less than 5% from the critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$ calculated with the actual parameter values applied in this study, as listed in table 4.3.

Considerably larger variations in the calculated critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$ are seen between calculations applying different water activity parameterization approaches, and when comparing anhydrous to hydrous particle calculations (see tables 4.10 and 4.11 in the following section 4.2). In the case of 50 nm and 100 nm pure citric acid particles, the percentage deviation of the critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$ calculated with the various water activity parameterization approaches for both anhydrous and hydrous particles, from the value obtained with the EDB water activity parameterization assuming anhydrous particles has been evaluated (table 4.8). The EDB water activity calculations were chosen as basis to make the evaluated variations $\Delta SS_c(\text{theo})/SS_c(\text{edb})$ comparable to those determined in the sensitivity analysis above. The deviations are expectedly greater for the hydrous particle calculations, since the calculated critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$ are being compared to the result from an approach that assumes anhydrous particles; nevertheless, the variation of the calculated critical supersaturation $SS_c(\text{theo})$ is greater with the different water activity parameterization approaches and the hydrous particle assumption applied, than for the above investigated perturbations in ambient temperature, dry particle diameter, hydrous density and droplet solution surface tension.

D_p^{CA}	type		$SS_c(\text{theo})$ [%]	$\frac{\Delta SS_c(\text{theo})}{SS_c(\text{edb})}$ [%]
50 nm	anhydrous	$SS_c(\text{edb})$	0.7642	-
		$SS_c(\text{osm})$	0.8139	6.5
		$SS_c(\text{bulk})$	0.8608	12.6
	hydrous	$SS_c(\text{edb, hy})$	0.8227	7.7
		$SS_c(\text{osm, hy})$	0.8704	13.9
		$SS_c(\text{bulk, hy})$	0.9186	20.2
	experimental	$SS_c(\text{exp})$	0.8953	17.2
100 nm	anhydrous	$SS_c(\text{edb})$	0.2559	-
		$SS_c(\text{osm})$	0.2896	13.2
		$SS_c(\text{bulk})$	0.3145	22.9
	hydrous	$SS_c(\text{edb, hy})$	0.2744	7.2
		$SS_c(\text{osm, hy})$	0.3098	21.1
		$SS_c(\text{bulk, hy})$	0.3361	31.3
	experimental	$SS_c(\text{exp})$	0.2722	6.4

Table 4.8: Critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$ calculated for 50 nm and 100 nm pure citric acid particles with the different water activity parameterizations applied in this study, assuming both anhydrous and hydrous particles. The experimentally measured value $SS_c(\text{exp})$ is included for comparison.

4.2 Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of the experimental and theoretical studies outlined above of the activation properties of citric and malic acid containing particles. Since the amount of especially theoretical data is rather large, representative results have been selected for presentation.

4.2.1 Experimental Results

The experimentally determined critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{exp})$ of the citric and malic acid containing particles for all dry particle sizes D_p and compositions measured are shown in fig. 4.4, along with the activation measurement results for pure ammonium sulfate particles originally performed for calibration of the CCNC as described in section 3.2.2. In fig.s 4.5 and 4.6, the same experimental results have been separated into pure acid and mixed acid/ammonium sulfate particles and citric and malic acid containing particles, respectively.

For all sizes and compositions of the citric and malic acid containing particles investigated, the combined estimated uncertainties in the experimental critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{exp})$ from fitting and calibration of the measurements are in the range $2\sigma_{SS_c(\text{exp})} \in [0.0148 - 0.0528]$ %. Generally, the estimated experimental uncertainties in the activation results are thus quite small for the citric and malic acid containing particles investigated. Since the errors lie with the 2nd decimal numbers, it is appro-

appropriate to state the experimental results accordingly with 2 significant decimal numbers [73, pp.33]. As will be seen in section 4.2.2 below, theoretical results are given with 4 significant decimal numbers, owing to the very precise values for the various parameters employed in the calculations. The experimentally determined critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{exp})$ are therefore presented in tables with 2 significant decimal numbers and the subsequent 3rd and 4th decimal numbers included in parenthesis. It must be stressed, that no physical significance should be attributed to these digits in parenthesis, which are included only for the sake of facilitating comparison of experimental and theoretical results.

The measurements of citric and malic acid containing particles span the dry particle size ranges, as selected by the DMA, and corresponding calibrated experimental critical supersaturations listed in table 4.9. All four citric and malic acid containing particle compositions display the same decline of the critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{exp})$ for increasing dry particle diameters D_p as expected from the Köhler theory (see section 2.3.3) and with the exception of maybe the pure malic acid particles, which show a somewhat irregular activation, the remaining three particle compositions activate in a very regular fashion for ascending dry particle sizes.

composition	D_p [nm]	$SS_c(\text{exp})$ [%]
pure CA	43-120	1.14(90)-0.19(48)
78.30% CA/21.70% AS	32-110	1.58(06)-0.18(80)
pure MA	38-80	1.08(29)-0.32(21)
80.44% MA/19.56% AS	38-125	1.13(65)-0.15(10)

Table 4.9: Ranges of dry particle sizes D_p and corresponding critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{exp})$ covered in the experiments for all particle compositions studied.

Figure 4.4: Experimental critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{exp})$ measured at dry particle sizes D_p for the four citric and malic acid particle compositions studied, together with the activation of pure ammonium sulfate particles measured for the CCNC calibration described in section 3.2.2. For each particle composition, the critical supersaturation declines with increasing dry particle size in a regular fashion, as expected from Köhler theory (see section 2.3.3). Neither the pure nor the mixed acid containing particles activate as easily as the pure ammonium sulfate particles.

Fig. 4.5 (left) clearly shows the qualitative activation order pure citric acid > pure malic acid > pure ammonium sulfate in terms of decreasing critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{exp})$ for a given dry particle diameter D_p , which can be expected from the ratios of mass density to molar mass for the three compounds

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\rho_{CA}}{M_{CA}} &= \frac{1.665[\text{g}/\text{cm}^3]}{192.124[\text{g}/\text{mol}]} = 8.666 \cdot 10^{-3}[\text{mol}/\text{cm}^3] \\
 \frac{\rho_{MA}}{M_{MA}} &= \frac{1.601[\text{g}/\text{cm}^3]}{134.088[\text{g}/\text{mol}]} = 11.94 \cdot 10^{-3}[\text{mol}/\text{cm}^3] \\
 \frac{\rho_{AS}}{M_{AS}} &= \frac{1.770[\text{g}/\text{cm}^3]}{132.141[\text{g}/\text{mol}]} = 13.39 \cdot 10^{-3}[\text{mol}/\text{cm}^3]
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.27}$$

Recalling the water activity relation 2.53 and expressing the amount in moles of compound i as $n_i = m_i/M_i = (\rho_i V)/M_i$ (where m_i , M_i , ρ_i and V are the mass, molar mass,

mass density and volume of i), a particle of a given dry diameter D_p (and thus a given volume V) will contain an increasing amount in moles of compound and consequently attain a larger Raoult effect resulting in a smaller critical supersaturation SS_c , when composed of citric acid, malic acid and ammonium sulfate, respectively.

Figure 4.5: The experimental results from fig. 4.4 divided into results for pure acid (left) and mixed acid and ammonium sulfate (right) particles, respectively. For the pure component particles, the activation order citric acid > malic acid > ammonium sulfate is clear, whereas for the mixed acid and ammonium sulfate particles, there is no significant difference between the citric and malic acid containing particle activation. Still, both mixed particle types activate for notably higher supersaturations than the pure ammonium sulfate particles. Again, note the different axis scales used for the left and right figure.

Figure 4.6: The experimental results from fig. 4.4 divided into results for citric (left) and malic (right) acid containing particles, respectively. The relatively easier activation of the mixed acid and ammonium sulfate particles is clearly evident for citric acid, but is only suggestive for malic acid. However, both citric and malic acid containing particles activate for higher supersaturations than the pure ammonium sulfate particles. Note the different axis scales used in the two figures.

By the same argument, assuming that volume additivity holds for the mixed composition particles, the mixed acid and ammonium sulfate particles should similarly activate with lower critical supersaturations than the respective pure acid particles and for higher supersaturations than pure ammonium sulfate particles, as the mass density to molar mass ratio for ammonium sulfate is larger than for either acid. This is evident for the citric acid containing particles in fig. 4.6 (left), but far less obvious for the malic acid containing particles in fig. 4.6 (right). This may owe partly to the difference in the mass density to molar mass ratio being smaller between malic acid and ammonium sulfate than between citric acid and ammonium sulfate; nevertheless, it is evident from the results in fig.s 4.6 (left), 4.6 (right) and 4.5 (left) that the quantitative differences in observed activation for the different particle compositions investigated cannot be rationalized solely in terms of the mass density to molar mass ratios of the particle constituents. This is interpreted as experimental evidence for the effects of dissociation of the particle components in the activating droplets on the observed activation properties.

Ammonium sulfate is a strong electrolyte generating $N_{AS} = 3$ ions upon full dissociation, whereas citric and malic acid are both weak acids, for which dissociation is expected to be partial and only generate $N_a = 2$ ions when occurring (see section 4.1.3). Activation of the mixed acid and ammonium sulfate particles is thus proportionately facilitated through an increased Raoult effect due to a greater total number of dissolved species produced by dissociation of ammonium sulfate compared to the acids upon droplet formation. This may then contribute to rationalize the very close activation behavior of the pure and mixed malic acid containing particles in fig. 4.6 (right); both pure and mixed malic acid containing particles activate for considerably larger supersaturations SS_c than the pure ammonium sulfate particles, also in agreement with the presumed greater dissociation of ammonium sulfate. Similarly, a more pronounced dissociation of ammonium sulfate than of the acids may explain the observation in fig. 4.5 (left) that the difference in measured critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{exp})$ is larger between pure malic acid and pure ammonium sulfate, for which the difference in the mass density to molar mass ratio is smaller, than between pure malic acid and pure citric acid. The quantification of the dissociation states of the different particle components, and of the acids in particular, in the activating droplets in terms of the resulting droplet solution water activities is the aim of the theoretical analysis in the following section 4.2.2.

A somewhat puzzling feature of the experimental results is the completely indistinguishable activation properties of the mixed citric acid/ammonium sulfate and mixed malic acid/ammonium sulfate particles seen in fig. 4.5 (right). Although the first does contain a larger mass fraction of ammonium sulfate than the latter, this is not thought to be sufficient to offset the difference in the citric and malic acid mass density to molar mass ratios; still, citric acid has a larger first acid dissociation constant and a higher acid valence than malic acid, and should thus be expected to dissociate relatively more. The observed activation may thus be a coincidence of compound properties and experimental conditions given by the particular particle component mixing ratios studied.

Overall, citric and malic acid have been shown to constitute rather good CCN species, in

agreement with the results of Raymond and Pandis [84], that "secondary organic aerosols with low carbon numbers and various functional groups are an excellent source of CCN". The present results however also comply with the findings of Wise et al. [108], that selected short-chain dicarboxylic acids mixed with ammonium sulfate yield a suppressed hygroscopic growth compared to pure ammonium sulfate. Thus, the model results of Ervens et al. [25], that soluble \leq C6 dicarboxylic acids mixed with ammonium sulfate do not show activation abilities significantly different from pure ammonium sulfate, do not seem to fully apply to citric and malic acid.

4.2.2 Theoretical Results

The theoretical critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$, calculated with the various water activity parameterization approaches described in section 4.1.3 for the relevant dry particle size ranges D_p , covering the corresponding experimental values, are shown for each dry particle composition below. In both figures and tables, the experimental results for the given particle composition have been included for evaluating the calculation performances.

Pure Citric Acid Particles

Figure 4.7: Theoretical critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$ for pure citric acid particles calculated using the water activity parameterization in terms of van't Hoff factors given in equation 4.6 with different constant citric acid van't Hoff factors i_{CA} .

Figure 4.8: Theoretical critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$ for assumed hydrous pure citric acid particles calculated using the water activity parameterization in terms of van't Hoff factors given in equation 4.6 with different constant citric acid van't Hoff factors i_{CA} .

Figure 4.9: Theoretical critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$ for pure citric acid particles calculated assuming anhydrous and hydrous particles, respectively, and using the water activity parameterization in terms of osmolality given in equation 4.8, with the osmolality parameterization 4.9.

Figure 4.10: Theoretical critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$ for pure citric acid particles calculated assuming anhydrous and hydrous particles, respectively, and using the water activity parameterization derived from EDB water activity measurements given in equation 4.12.

Figure 4.11: Theoretical critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$ for pure citric acid particles calculated assuming anhydrous and hydrous particles, respectively, and using the water activity parameterization derived from bulk water activity measurements given in equation 4.14.

Figure 4.12: Theoretical critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$ for pure citric acid particles calculated assuming both anhydrous and hydrous particles, and using osmolality derived, EDB and bulk measurement water activity parameterizations. All calculation approaches yield the same overall magnitude and display the same monotony trend of the critical supersaturation values, and the overall agreement with the experimental data is good.

D_p [nm]	43	50	60	80	120
$SS_c(\text{exp})[\%]$	1.14(90)	0.89(53)	0.67(55)	0.40(79)	0.19(48)
$SS_c(\text{osm})[\%]$	1.0182	0.8139	0.6206	0.4041	0.2205
$SS_c(\text{osm, hy})[\%]$	1.0888	0.8704	0.6638	0.4323	0.2359
$SS_c(\text{edb})[\%]$	0.9784	0.7642	0.5694	0.3616	0.1935
$SS_c(\text{edb, hy})[\%]$	1.0538	0.8227	0.6121	0.3881	0.2073
$SS_c(\text{bulk})[\%]$	1.0686	0.8608	0.6619	0.4359	0.2406
$SS_c(\text{bulk, hy})[\%]$	1.1399	0.9186	0.7066	0.4656	0.2571
$d_c(\text{osm})[\text{nm}]$	140.4	174.9	228.5	349.3	637.7
$d_c(\text{osm, hy})[\text{nm}]$	131.4	163.7	213.8	326.7	596.2
$d_c(\text{edb})[\text{nm}]$	131.8	169.8	231.9	373.4	710.4
$d_c(\text{edb, hy})[\text{nm}]$	122.4	157.3	214.7	346.9	662.0
$d_c(\text{bulk})[\text{nm}]$	138.8	171.1	220.8	331.6	593.6
$d_c(\text{bulk, hy})[\text{nm}]$	130.4	160.7	207.2	311.0	556.1
$b_{CAc}(\text{osm})[\text{mol/kg}]$	0.2571	0.2079	0.1603	0.1057	0.0583
$b_{CAc}(\text{osm, hy})[\text{mol/kg}]$	0.2744	0.2218	0.1711	0.1129	0.0623
$b_{CAc}(\text{edb})[\text{mol/kg}]$	0.3127	0.2277	0.1532	0.0863	0.0421
$b_{CAc}(\text{edb, hy})[\text{mol/kg}]$	0.3420	0.2508	0.1689	0.0941	0.0454
$b_{CAc}(\text{bulk})[\text{mol/kg}]$	0.2664	0.2225	0.1780	0.1238	0.0724
$b_{CAc}(\text{bulk, hy})[\text{mol/kg}]$	0.2809	0.2348	0.1883	0.1311	0.0769
$a_{wc}(\text{osm})$	0.9952	0.9961	0.9970	0.9980	0.9989
$a_{wc}(\text{osm, hy})$	0.9949	0.9959	0.9968	0.9979	0.9988
$a_{wc}(\text{edb})$	0.9938	0.9953	0.9966	0.9980	0.9990
$a_{wc}(\text{edb, hy})$	0.9934	0.9949	0.9963	0.9978	0.9989
$a_{wc}(\text{bulk})$	0.9955	0.9963	0.9971	0.9980	0.9989
$a_{wc}(\text{bulk, hy})$	0.9953	0.9961	0.9969	0.9979	0.9988
$\alpha_{CAc}(\text{osm})[\%]$	5.2	5.8	6.6	8.0	10.7
$\alpha_{CAc}(\text{osm, hy})[\%]$	5.1	5.6	6.4	7.8	10.3
$\alpha_{CAc}(\text{edb})[\%]$	4.8	5.6	6.7	8.9	12.4
$\alpha_{CAc}(\text{edb, hy})[\%]$	4.6	5.3	6.4	8.5	12.0
$\alpha_{CAc}(\text{bulk})[\%]$	5.1	5.6	6.3	7.5	9.6
$\alpha_{CAc}(\text{bulk, hy})[\%]$	5.0	5.5	6.1	7.3	9.4
$i_{CAc}(\text{osm})$	1.052	1.058	1.066	1.080	1.107
$i_{CAc}(\text{osm, hy})$	1.051	1.056	1.064	1.078	1.103
$i_{CAc}(\text{edb})$	1.048	1.056	1.067	1.089	1.124
$i_{CAc}(\text{edb, hy})$	1.046	1.053	1.064	1.085	1.120
$i_{CAc}(\text{bulk})$	1.051	1.056	1.063	1.075	1.096
$i_{CAc}(\text{bulk, hy})$	1.050	1.055	1.061	1.073	1.094

Table 4.10: Experimental and theoretical critical supersaturations SS_c for pure citric acid particles of selected dry sizes D_p . The theoretical values are calculated using the different water activity parameterization approaches described in section 4.1.3, assuming both anhydrous and hydrous particles, respectively. In addition are listed critical droplet diameters d_c , water activities a_{wc} and citric acid molal concentrations b_{CAc} , dissociation degrees α_{CAc} and acid constant $pK_{a,1}$ derived van't Hoff factors i_{CAc} at activation, calculated for each particle size with the different approaches.

Mixed Citric Acid and Ammonium Sulfate Particles

Figure 4.13: Theoretical critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$ for mixed citric acid and ammonium sulfate particles calculated using the water activity parameterization in terms of van't Hoff factors given in equation 4.6 with different constant citric acid van't Hoff factors i_{CA} and with the ammonium sulfate van't Hoff factor i_{AS} parameterized by equation 4.7.

Figure 4.14: Theoretical critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$ for assumed hydrous mixed citric acid and ammonium sulfate particles calculated using the water activity parameterization in terms of van't Hoff factors given in equation 4.6 with different constant citric acid van't Hoff factors i_{CA} and with the ammonium sulfate van't Hoff factor i_{AS} parameterized by equation 4.7.

Pure Malic Acid Particles

Figure 4.15: Theoretical critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$ for pure malic acid particles calculated using the water activity parameterization in terms of van't Hoff factors given in equation 4.6 with different constant malic acid van't Hoff factors i_{MA} .

Figure 4.16: Theoretical critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$ for assumed hydrous pure malic acid particles calculated using the water activity parameterization in terms of van't Hoff factors given in equation 4.6 with different constant malic acid van't Hoff factors i_{MA} .

Figure 4.17: Theoretical critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$ for pure malic acid particles calculated assuming anhydrous and hydrous particles, respectively, and using the water activity parameterization derived from EDB water activity measurements given in equation 4.13.

D_p [nm]	38	45	50	60	80
$SS_c(\text{exp})[\%]$	1.08(29)	0.87(71)	0.73(79)	0.58(81)	0.32(21)
$SS_c(\text{edb})[\%]$	1.2608	0.9785	0.8343	0.6320	0.4070
$SS_c(\text{edb, hy})[\%]$	1.3125	1.0192	0.8692	0.6586	0.4242
$d_c(\text{edb})[\text{nm}]$	113.2	143.6	167.1	218.8	338.6
$d_c(\text{edb, hy})[\text{nm}]$	109.1	138.1	160.7	210.1	324.9
$b_{MAc}(\text{edb})[\text{mol/kg}]$	0.4708	0.3802	0.3297	0.2521	0.1601
$b_{MAc}(\text{edb, hy})[\text{mol/kg}]$	0.4855	0.3946	0.3421	0.2628	0.1671
$a_{w_c}(\text{edb})$	0.9940	0.9951	0.9958	0.9967	0.9979
$a_{w_c}(\text{edb, hy})$	0.9938	0.9950	0.9956	0.9966	0.9978
$\alpha_{MAc}(\text{edb})[\%]$	2.9	3.2	3.4	3.9	4.9
$\alpha_{MAc}(\text{edb, hy})[\%]$	2.8	3.1	3.4	3.8	4.8
$i_{MAc}(\text{edb})$	1.029	1.032	1.034	1.039	1.049
$i_{MAc}(\text{edb, hy})$	1.028	1.031	1.034	1.038	1.048

Table 4.11: Experimental and theoretical critical supersaturations SS_c for pure malic acid particles of selected dry sizes D_p . The theoretical values are calculated with the water activity parameterization 4.13 derived from EDB measurements, assuming both anhydrous and hydrous particles, respectively. In addition are listed critical droplet diameters d_c , water activities a_{w_c} and malic acid molal concentrations b_{MAc} , dissociation degrees α_{MAc} and acid constant $pK_{a,1}$ derived van't Hoff factors i_{MAc} at activation, calculated for each particle size.

Mixed Malic Acid and Ammonium Sulfate Particles

Figure 4.18: Theoretical critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$ for mixed malic acid and ammonium sulfate particles calculated using the water activity parameterization in terms of van't Hoff factors given in equation 4.6 with different constant malic acid van't Hoff factors i_{MA} and with the ammonium sulfate van't Hoff factor i_{AS} parameterized by equation 4.7.

Figure 4.19: Theoretical critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$ for assumed hydrous mixed malic acid and ammonium sulfate particles calculated using the water activity parameterization in terms of van't Hoff factors given in equation 4.6 with different constant malic acid van't Hoff factors i_{MA} and with the ammonium sulfate van't Hoff factor i_{AS} parameterized by equation 4.7.

General Remarks to Calculations

The acid and ammonium sulfate molal concentrations b_{ac} and b_{ASc} and the droplet water activity a_{wc} at activation have been evaluated along with the theoretical critical supersaturations. Table 4.12 below lists the ranges of these values for particle size ranges and compositions corresponding to those investigated experimentally, considering all calculation approaches. In tables 4.10 and 4.11, results are shown for the specific calculation approaches applying to pure citric and pure malic acid particles, respectively.

The droplet solutions are indeed rather dilute at activation; the concentrations of the various particle constituents are well below the respective solubility limits, so the assumption of full solubility is justified. Also, substitution of the solution surface tension σ with the analogous pure water value σ_w , as well as the original assumption of equating the water molar volume in solution v_w^{sol} to the pure water value v_w^0 in the Kelvin equation 2.80 seem reasonable from this perspective.

However, the resulting water activities at droplet activation are at the limit of, or even exceeding, the different parameterization validity ranges, as given by the ranges of the measured values upon which they are based (see section 4.1.3). Only for the osmolality derived water activity calculations for pure citric acid particles is the droplet solution water activity at activation within the parameterization validity range for all particle sizes considered. In case of the EDB and bulk water activity calculations, the dilute parameterization validity limit is exceeded for pure citric acid particle sizes of 60 nm and up. Finally, for pure malic acid particles, the EDB water activity parameterization validity range is exceeded in the dilute limit for all particle sizes investigated. The need to extrapolate the water activity parameterizations beyond their respective measurement basis is yet another incentive to apply the various constraints as explained in section 4.1.3.

composition	b_{ac} [mol/kg]	b_{ASc} [mol/kg]	a_{wc}
pure CA	0.0361-0.3763	-	0.9934-0.9991
78.30% CA/21.70% AS	0.0188-0.3279	0.0082-0.1321	0.9923-0.9991
pure MA	0.0680-0.4855	-	0.9938-0.9984
80.44% MA/19.56% AS	0.0217-0.2902	0.0056-0.0716	0.9944-0.9993

Table 4.12: Ranges of the calculated acid and ammonium sulfate molal concentrations b_{ac} and b_{ASc} and water activity a_{wc} at the droplet activation points, considering all calculation approaches over the dry particle size ranges D_p covered by experiments for the different particle compositions studied.

For all calculation approaches, the critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$ calculated assuming presence of residual water in the dried particles are consistently higher than those calculated for presumably completely dry particles of the same size and remainder composition. Hydrous particles of a given size and composition will contain comparatively less remainder compound and thus attain a smaller Raoult effect for a given droplet size than the corresponding anhydrous particles. It is therefore not surprising, that activation also occurs for larger critical supersaturations in the case of hydrous particles.

The calculations for the mixed acid and ammonium sulfate particles give almost identical results whether the constant ammonium sulfate van't Hoff factor $i_{AS} = 2.2$ or parameterization 4.7 is used; therefore only results for the latter are shown above. This similarity supposedly reflects the very dilute activating droplets, for which the amount in moles of water n_w is so much greater than the amount of ammonium sulfate n_{AS} , that the exact value of the ammonium sulfate van't Hoff factor i_{AS} given by the constant value $i_{AS} = 2.2$ or parameterization 4.7 makes little difference for the water activity parameterized by equation 4.6.

4.2.3 Comparison of Experimental and Theoretical Results

The main features in the comparison of the experimental and theoretical results for the cloud droplet activation properties of citric and malic acid containing particles and

some interesting implications are discussed in the following.

Generally, the theoretical calculations represent the experimental values well, by and large capturing both the magnitude and decline of the critical supersaturation SS_c as function of the dry particle diameter D_p . In addition, calculations applying the different measurement based approaches to water activity parameterization appear mutually consistent, all yielding the same overall magnitude and monotony trend of the calculated critical supersaturation values $SS_c(\text{theo})$, as seen for pure citric acid particles in fig. 4.12. As such, both the osmolality derived and the EDB or bulk measurement water activity parameterizations give valid descriptions of the water activity for cloud droplet activation of the investigated pure citric acid particles.

Acid Van't Hoff Factors and Degree of Dissociation

When compared with the experimental results, the calculations using the water activity parameterization 4.6 in terms of van't Hoff factors show consistently for the four dry particle compositions studied, that the constant acid van't Hoff factor i_a best describing the overall activation behavior of the particles increases for increasing dry particle diameter D_p . This variation is much greater over the size ranges studied for each particle composition than differences resulting from assuming anhydrous (fig.s 4.7, 4.13, 4.15 and 4.18) or hydrous (fig.s 4.8, 4.14, 4.16 and 4.19) particles in the calculations, respectively; therefore, the hydrous particle assumption is not essential for this observation. It is furthermore evident, that the constant acid van't Hoff factor i_a needed to obtain a critical supersaturation $SS_c(\text{theo})$ equal to the experimentally determined value $SS_c(\text{exp})$ is often well below $i_a = 1.0$ for the smaller half of the particles of a given composition, especially for the mixed acid and ammonium sulfate particles.

A constant acid van't Hoff factor i_a applied in the water activity parameterization will in particular be the acid van't Hoff factor yielding the droplet water activity at the point of activation. The increase with dry particle diameter D_p for a given composition of the acid van't Hoff factor i_a best describing the experimentally measured activation is therefore interpreted as a manifestation of increased acid dissociation due to greater droplet dilution at activation.

Comparison with the acid van't Hoff factors i_{ac} and dissociation degrees α_{ac} at droplet activation determined from the respective first acid constants $pK_{a,1}$ for the pure acid particles as part of the calculations using osmolality derived and directly measured water activity parameterizations (tables 4.10 and 4.11) supports this interpretation. Here, the acid van't Hoff factors and dissociation degrees have been calculated from the corresponding acid molal concentrations b_{ac} at droplet activation, which are also listed along with the activating droplet diameters d_c . The calculations clearly show, how larger dry particles experience larger relative growth before activation and thus form increasingly dilute activating droplets, in which the acid solutes accordingly become increasingly dissociated. Kiss and Hansson [57] also calculates a larger relative growth for larger dry particles of a given composition just as both Raymond and Pandis [84] and Kreidenweis

et al. [61] notice how the van't Hoff factor should actually be a function of droplet size, even if a constant value is invoked for dilute solutions.

The increased acid dissociation with droplet dilution is a direct consequence of the shift in equilibria 2.64 according to Le Chatelier's principle [11, pp.223]. The simple connection between the degree of dissociation and the van't Hoff factor given in equation 4.23 translates the increased acid dissociation α_a into a larger acid van't Hoff factor i_a . Equivalently, for dilute solutions the van't Hoff factor i_a is predicted from Debye-Hückel theory to increase toward the number of solute species generated upon complete dissociation N_a (see section 4.1.3) in the limit of infinite dilution [72].

There are some important differences between the acid van't Hoff factors determined from comparison of the experimental activation results with the calculations using the van't Hoff factor parameterized water activity, and the acid van't Hoff factors i_{ac} derived from droplet concentrations via the acid constants $pK_{a,1}$ in the osmolality and direct measurement water activity parameterization calculations: Their values are not nearly the same for a given dry particle diameter D_p and composition, and whereas the first attain values far below $i_a = 1.0$, the latter is always greater than unity. Furthermore, the variation over the experimentally studied particle sizes and compositions is an order of magnitude greater in the first case than in the latter. The variation in acid dissociation state observed from comparison with experiments is thus much larger than expected from the calculations using the acid dissociation constants.

Comparing with other studies, a similar ambiguity of values depending on the method used for determining van't Hoff factors is seen: Kiss and Hansson [57] calculate from the acid dissociation constants the citric acid van't Hoff factor $i_{CA} = 1.08$ for a 0.1 mol/kg solution, which agrees well with the values found for activating droplets from pure citric acid particles calculated correspondingly (table 4.10). On the other hand, Wise et al. [108] determine a constant aqueous solution malic acid van't Hoff factor $i_{MA} = 1.87$ from fitting water activity measurements for malic acid bulk solutions of varying concentration at subsaturation conditions. This value is even larger than the constant malic acid van't Hoff factor values found from comparison with experiments in this study and is determined for more concentrated solutions, which is puzzling. Svenningsson et al. [100] find experimental van't Hoff factors smaller than unity for Fulvic acid, a collection of non-specified humic like substances sharing certain properties, but ascribe these values to lacking knowledge of the precise density and molar mass for the compounds involved. For Fulvic acid, Dinar et al. [23] determine a van't Hoff factor of 1.25 by fitting calculations to activation experiments and assuming the droplet solution surface tension equal to that of water; however they note, that the experiments might just as well be fitted using a van't Hoff factor of 1 and a measured surface tension for solutions corresponding to the droplets, lowered by the surface activity of Fulvic acid.

No exhaustive explanation for these differences appears readily at hand, but some considerations on the matter are elaborated in the following. Still, both the comparative and the calculated citric and malic acid van't Hoff factors show, that dissociation of

these acids in the droplet solutions is neither negligible nor close to complete, as has been assumed for some organic acids in other studies [84], [62], [57], [23]. As the acid van't Hoff factors at droplet activation appear to be closer to unity than to the values depicting full dissociation, the first would thus be the preferable approximation of the two, even if neither give an appropriate account of the acid dissociation state in the activating droplets.

Solution Effects

The acid van't Hoff factor i_a gives the number solute species resulting in solution for each acid molecule initially dissolved. An acid van't Hoff factor smaller than unity thus implies the presence of solution phenomena that decrease the effective number of solute species in solution below that initially dissolved.

Since the acid van't Hoff factor i_a is the only variable that has been adjusted in the individual calculations applying the water activity parameterization 4.6, whereas the ammonium sulfate van't Hoff factor i_{AS} for the mixed particles is fixed as function of concentration by the parameterization 4.7, any effects unaccounted for pertaining to ammonium sulfate will be captured by the acid van't Hoff factor when comparing the experimental results with the calculations. As noted above, the smallest acid van't Hoff factors from comparison of calculations and experiments are seen for the mixed acid and ammonium sulfate particles. It is possible that the ammonium sulfate van't Hoff factor parameterization 4.7, which is based on measurements of aqueous solutions with ammonium sulfate being the sole solute, overestimates the ammonium sulfate van't Hoff factor i_{AS} in the mixed acid and ammonium sulfate droplet solutions. On the other hand, Kiss and Hansson [57] mentions that the presence of ammonium sulfate may suppress the acid dissociation in a droplet solution by salting out. Either way, this would then translate to a smaller apparent acid van't Hoff factor i_a to compensate for the effect when comparing with the experimental activation.

Due to the extensive dilution of the activating droplets, exceeding of the solubility limit for either the acids or ammonium sulfate given in section 4.1.3 is ruled out as explanation for decreasing the resulting number of species in solution.

Dilution does however not preclude non-ideal solution effects, such as hydrogen bonding, particularly dimerization (see section 2.2.6) of the dissolved acid molecules, or electrostatic pairing between ions (see section 2.2.5) produced by dissociated acid or ammonium sulfate. These phenomena are different types of association processes and will indeed decrease the number of independent species in solution, thereby decreasing the acid van't Hoff factor i_a . Particularly, if association dominates dissociation in solution, the acid van't Hoff factor should be smaller than unity by definition. This is not allowed for, when the acid van't Hoff factors i_a are calculated from the acid dissociation degrees α_a by relation 4.23; the dissociation degree is evaluated from consideration of only the acid dissociation equilibrium 2.64 with an implicit assumption of solution ideality using concentrations rather than activities for expressing the acid constant K_{a1} in

equation 4.20.

From the perspective of water, the comparatively large carboxylate ions resulting from dissociation of the organic acids may decrease the coherency of water molecules in the solution by disrupting the highly ordered hydrogen bonded structure existing in pure liquid water and thus increase the water vapor pressure over the solution compared to pure water: In the pure liquid phase, the water molecules are interconnected through an extensive network of hydrogen bonds, providing water with a high degree of order and cohesion [94], [12, pp.169-172], [86, pp.4-5]. The structure is dynamic, but on average, only about 20% of the hydrogen bonds are broken compared to ice [43], [98]. Dissolution of electrolytes in water alters the hydrogen bond structure and consequently the properties depending hereupon through interactions of the produced ions; the effect is particularly large for anions and increases with ionic size and charge [103]. Such ions may increase the solution entropy, i.e. disorder, by breaking the hydrogen bond structure of water [34], [86, pp.16-17]. The nature of the intermolecular forces in solution is reflected by the vapor pressures of the solution constituents [49, pp.654]. Decreasing the water coherency may then increase the water vapor pressure p_w over the acid solution compared to the vapor pressure p_w^0 over pure water, corresponding to a water activity a_w increased above unity according to equation 2.38. This would require an acid van't Hoff factor i_a smaller than unity for parameterizing the water activity by equation 4.6. However, within such a theoretical framework the water activity description as treated in section 2.2 is no longer applicable. The possibility is only mentioned here to draw attention to the fact that solution phenomena may be important in the activating droplets, for which the theoretical description adopted for this work is inadequate.

Finally, since both citric and malic acid are slightly surface active [68], [48], partitioning of the dissolved acid to the droplet surface may occur (see section 2.3.4). Contrary to the solution phenomena described above, partitioning does not directly affect the acid van't Hoff factor; the droplet water vapor pressure is increased through an increased water activity and an increased Kelvin effect resulting from the decreased amount of surface active acid solute in the droplet bulk due to partitioning. But since the acid van't Hoff factor i_a is the only parameter adjusted in the theoretical formalism of equations 4.1 and 4.6, its apparent value from comparison with experimental results will decrease to compensate for the lacking account of the decreased amount in moles of acid solute n_a in the droplet bulk caused by partitioning of the acid to the droplet surface. The actual van't Hoff factor of the acid remaining in the droplet bulk may however increase due to the increased dilution.

Partitioning is treated further in chapter 5. In connection to the work described there, the significance of citric and malic acid partitioning in activating droplets will be looked into in the future, together with the group of Professor Ari Laaksonen at the University of Kuopio, using their model accounting for surfactant partitioning in cloud droplet activation. Surface tension data are reported by Hyvärinen et al. [48] for malic acid; substituting these data for σ into the theoretical description of cloud droplet activation applied here has not been attempted, in light of the conclusions of Sorjamaa et al. [97]

that simply accounting for the surface tension lowering as function of solution concentration without regard for the effect of partitioning on both the Kelvin and Raoult effects will lead to a greater deviation from observed activation behavior than using the surface tension value of pure water, as applied here.

Hydrous Particles and Evaporation

Several processes may also occur that actually decrease the amount of compound initially dissolved in the droplet solutions; if this is not taken into account, the decreased amount in moles of dissolved compound n_a will instead be compensated by a smaller apparent acid van't Hoff factor i_a required to match the experimental critical supersaturation values $SS_c(\text{exp})$. Residual water in the dried particles will cause particles of a given selected size to contain less of the remainder compounds, than reckoned on, which will result in a smaller Raoult effect for the growing droplets. Evaporation of the particles in the flow system between size selection (DMA) and activation measurement (CCNC) similarly decreases the amount of compound dissolving in the droplets and the smaller particle sizes furthermore provide larger Kelvin effects to be overcome at the initial stages of water condensing on the particles, which again would be captured by a smaller apparent acid van't Hoff factor in comparison of measurements with theory.

The vapor pressures of anhydrous solid citric and malic acid are $p_{CA} = 1.7 \cdot 10^{-11}$ mmHg = $2.3 \cdot 10^{-9}$ Pa and $p_{MA} = 3.3 \cdot 10^{-8}$ mmHg = $4.4 \cdot 10^{-6}$ Pa, respectively [77]. Using the model of Bilde et al. [15] for calculating evaporation rates from vapor pressures, a rough estimate of the particle residence time in the flow system of 10 s shows that the pure citric acid particles are not likely to evaporate significantly, whereas the pure malic acid particles may decrease on the order of 1 nm in diameter D_p from evaporation between the DMA and the CCNC. Furthermore, if the particles contain residual water, they can formally be regarded as highly supersaturated aqueous solutions, which are only metastable and will display considerably higher acid vapor pressures than the acids exert as anhydrous solids [85], [15]. Whether such hydrous particles are actually liquid is maybe revealed from the contemplated investigations by the Aerosol Group at the University of Copenhagen of the presence of bulk water in highly concentrated droplet solutions with Raman spectroscopy. Prenni et al. [82] find evaporation occurring in activation experiments of Malonic and Glutaric acid particles, which however have considerably higher vapor pressures than citric and malic acid. They note that the dilution of the aerosol flow before activation may promote evaporation, presumably by shifting the gas-particle phase equilibrium upon dilution of the gas phase. The present calculations assume no evaporation of the dried particles, but this will need to be investigated further by evaporation measurements.

Incomplete drying resulting in hydrous particles has been observed in studies of other carboxylic acids and subsequently invoked to explain overestimation of measured activation properties by Köhler theory [82], [62]. The phenomenon is expected to be pronounced for polyfunctional acids as due to "the strong interactions between the polar functional groups and water molecules at high degrees of (droplet solution) su-

persaturation” [41]. Calculations have been made in this work assuming a content of 8% for citric acid and 5% for malic acid by mass of residual water in the acid fraction of the dried particles, both for pure acid and mixed acid and ammonium sulfate particles. These calculations can be thought of as a preliminary investigation of any of the mechanisms discussed above, that would decrease the initial or resulting amount of compound dissolved in the droplets or the number of independent species present in the resulting droplet solution.

As would be expected for the calculations applying constant acid van’t Hoff factors, the acid van’t Hoff factors i_a best describing the experimentally measured activation are larger when the experiments are compared to these hydrous particle calculations (fig.s 4.8, 4.14, 4.16 and 4.19) than to the calculations assuming anhydrous particles (fig.s 4.7, 4.13, 4.15 and 4.18), as larger acid van’t Hoff factors are needed in the water activity parameterization to compensate for the smaller amounts in moles n_a of acid taken to be dissolved in the droplets for the hydrous calculations. This is seen for all particle compositions. The hydrous calculations however still yield acid van’t Hoff factors $i_a < 1$ from comparison with the experimental critical supersaturation values $SS_c(\text{exp})$, so the decrease in the dissolved amount of compound assumed in the hydrous calculations is insufficient to explain the discrepancy of the compared and calculated acid van’t Hoff factors.

For pure citric acid particles, the calculations using osmolality derived and bulk water activity parameterizations (fig.s 4.9 and 4.11) yield a better agreement with the experimental critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{exp})$ for the small dry particles and a poorer agreement for the large dry particles, when assuming the particles are hydrous as opposed to anhydrous. The calculations using the EDB water activity parameterization (fig. 4.10) give a better agreement with experiments all together for hydrous than for anhydrous particles. In the case of pure malic acid particles, agreement with the experimental values decreases when assuming hydrous particles in the calculations with the EDB water activity parameterization (fig. 4.17). At least for pure citric acid particles then, it is not unlikely that some effect unaccounted for in the calculations tends to increase the water activity in the droplet solutions and thus impede activation of the droplets. For pure malic acid particles, no conclusions about this seem reasonable based on the present results.

Prenni et al. [82] similarly find, that residual water is not sufficient to fully account for the observed differences between theoretical and measured activation of Oxalic acid particles, and proposes kinetically limited droplet growth as an additional possibility. The dependence of activation on exposure time to given supersaturation conditions is currently being investigated for humic like substances by the Aerosol Group at the University of Copenhagen; it thus seems like an interesting perspective for short-chain carboxylic acids as well.

Particle Size Dependence

Any solution effects like association and dissociation should immediately be accounted for by using the osmolality derived or directly measured water activity parameterizations. Nevertheless, the results for pure citric acid particles presented in fig. 4.12 show that none of the activation calculations applying these parameterizations fully capture the slope in the variation of the experimentally measured activation with dry particle size. Equivalently, the acid van't Hoff factors giving the best agreement with the experimental results in fig.s 4.7 and 4.8 are larger than the equivalent acid van't Hoff factors, calculated from acid droplet concentrations at activation, for the small dry particle sizes and greater than the latter for the large dry particle sizes. And, as already mentioned, in fig.s 4.9 and 4.11 the calculations assuming hydrous particles, and thus a decreased amount of dissolved compound in the activating droplets, seem to fit the experimental critical supersaturations better than the calculations assuming anhydrous particles for small particles, but less good than the latter for the large particles. A similar trend may be present in the measurements of Svenningsson et al. [100] for Fulvic acid.

This suggests a size dependent effect, which would not be implied in the water activity parameterizations using measurements of either osmolality, EDB or bulk water activity, which are all performed on bulk solutions or droplets much larger than those studied in the present activation measurements. Svenningsson et al. [100] point out that water activity parameterizations based on measurements of droplets much more concentrated than in the activation measurements, where the droplet solutes are less dissociated, as is the case for the EDB water activity measurements, tend to overestimate the water activity for the droplets at supersaturation and thus the activation. However, since the EDB measurements water activity parameterization used here also include bulk measurements which pertain to solution water activities much closer to unity than the EDB method, this is believed to be less important for the present study.

Several of the above mentioned mechanisms that decrease the amount of compound initially or eventually dissolved in the droplets or the number of species in the resulting droplet solution will be either directly or indirectly size dependent: Since smaller particles form smaller and more concentrated activating droplets, association processes will be favored as opposed to dissociation according to Le Chatelier's principle, and the larger surface to volume ratio of small droplets will promote partitioning of surfactants to the surface depleting the droplet bulk [97]. Evaporation of the dried particles will also be more pronounced for small particles due the enhanced Kelvin effect. It is already seen, that the assumption of hydrous particles with the amount of residual water found by Peng et al. [78] and Peng et al. [77] cannot completely account for the observed activation behavior of the citric and malic acid containing particles studied here. Either the water content in the current particles is greater than assumed in the calculations, or some combination of different effects is at play, the relative significance of which is yet to be revealed by further investigations.

Calculation Artifacts

One other explanation for the discrepancy of the acid van't Hoff factor values, that needs to be mentioned, is calculation artifacts in terms of failure to represent the physical system even when returning results that comply with measurements. As stated by the Köhler equation 2.84, the equilibrium supersaturation SS for a droplet of diameter d is given by a combination of the droplet water activity and Kelvin effect.

A constant acid van't Hoff factor fails to represent the changing acid dissociation state as the droplet grows and becomes increasingly dilute, whereas this is intrinsically accounted for by measuring the osmolality or water activity directly. Specifically, the water activity a_w will rise more steeply with droplet diameter d from a fixed dry particle size D_p , when parameterized applying a constant acid van't Hoff factor i_a , than if the parameterization accounts for the changing dissociation with dilution. This leads to a steeper rise in the equilibrium supersaturation SS in the first case, compared to the latter.

The equilibrium supersaturation value corresponding to a given measured critical supersaturation $SS_c(\text{exp})$ will then be reached for a smaller droplet size with a constant acid van't Hoff factor i_a water activity parameterization than with one accounting for the changing acid dissociation state as the droplet grows. For a smaller droplet, a larger Kelvin effect must then be balanced by a smaller water activity, if the equilibrium supersaturation value calculated for the droplet should represent the critical point and thus the calculated curve maximum. Since a smaller droplet is also more concentrated, this could however imply either a larger or a smaller acid van't Hoff factor, depending on the balance between the effects of dilution and dissociation.

The Köhler curves from the different calculation approaches have been plotted for pure citric acid particles of selected dry sizes and show, that in each case the activation point is predicted for similar droplet diameters d_c with the different calculations. Unfortunately, the critical supersaturation $SS_c(\text{theo})$ values resulting from the different calculations are not sufficiently close to make any firm conclusions about the occurrence of this kind of calculation artifact; but an effect large enough to explain the observations concerning the acid van't Hoff factors does seem unlikely.

4.3 Conclusions and Perspectives

The cloud droplet activation of particles consisting of pure citric acid, pure malic acid, mixed citric acid/ammonium sulfate and mixed malic acid/ammonium sulfate has been measured in laboratory experiments and calculated from Köhler theory applying parameterizations of droplet water activity in terms of solute van't Hoff factors, solution osmolality and direct solution EDB and bulk water activity measurements.

Generally, all water activity parameterizations given the constraint that $a_w \rightarrow 1$ for infinite dilution provide good theoretical descriptions of the measured activation prop-

erties and are thus suitable for application to cloud droplet activation in the case of the citric and malic acid containing particles investigated.

However, the constant acid van't Hoff factor best describing the overall activation behavior increases with increasing dry particle size within all four particle compositions. This is interpreted as being due to increased acid dissociation at droplet activation caused by the greater relative growth and thus dilution before activation experienced by the droplets originating from larger dry particles. The extent of dissociation at activation has not been determined with confidence, owing to discrepancies likely caused by failure to account for non-ideal droplet solution effects such as hydrogen bonding and dimerization, which are characteristic properties of carboxylic acids, but is at most of the order of either 50% or 10% depending on the method of evaluation. It seems reasonable that for the particles investigated the acid van't Hoff factors describing the activating droplet water activities should neither be unity, corresponding to no dissociation, nor equal to the maximum number of ions as generated by complete dissociation, but nevertheless closer to the first than to the latter. Furthermore, the dissociation behavior citric and malic acid during cloud droplet activation appears too complex for a single constant acid van't Hoff factor to sufficiently describe the activation behavior of all particles with a given composition over the investigated size ranges.

The changing acid dissociation with droplet concentration, as well as any non-ideal solution effects, are innately accounted for when applying a water activity parameterization based on osmolality, EDB or bulk water activity measurements. Activation calculated for pure citric acid particles using any of these water activity parameterizations agree well with the experimental results of this study, even if the droplet dilution at activation often requires extrapolation of the parameterizations beyond their validity range. For pure malic acid particles, the agreement with experiments of activation calculations performed with the EDB water activity parameterization is not as good as for the pure citric acid particles, but still reasonable. It is reassuring in respect to the validity of the theory, that the activation calculations employing different water activity parameterizations based on different types of measurements from different literature sources give concurrent results.

The variation of acid van't Hoff factors with dry particle sizes seen in this study for both pure and mixed citric and malic acid particles, as well as the mutual agreement of the osmolality derived, EDB and bulk measurement water activity parameterizations found for the pure citric acid particles should be investigated for particles containing other polyfunctional organic acids, preferably to obtain results for a homologous series of such compounds, similar to those studied for sugars by Rosenørn et al. [89].

A judgment of which water activity parameterization approach produces the best description of the observed cloud droplet activation properties cannot be made solely from the results for pure citric acid particles obtained here. With reference to the very dilute nature of the activating droplets, osmolality and bulk water activity measurements seem promising for future parameterizations of water activity in prediction of cloud droplet

activation; since both these measurement types can be performed on very dilute solutions [57], [111], this would imply less severe or perhaps even preclude extrapolations of the resulting water activity parameterizations when applied to cloud droplet activation.

Furthermore, as neither osmolality nor bulk water activity measurements require specific knowledge of the nature of solutes present in solution, water activity parameterizations in terms hereof should be applicable in prediction of activation properties for atmospheric samples of indeterminate composition as well as for any mixed composition particles, whose individual component van't Hoff factors in the resulting droplet solution are not known as function of concentration. Particularly the application to humic like substances (HULIS), which are high molecular weight polifunctional organic compounds with non-welldefined structure and properties, making up a significant fraction of the watersoluble organic carbon content (WSOC) in atmospheric aerosols [23] (and references herein), [57] (and references herein), seems promising. A full prospective would however require knowledge of the precision, ease and cost of each measurement method, which I have not become acquainted with during the present work.

It is not unlikely that particles in our experiments contain some residual water after drying, which may affect the activation of the particles and decrease the level of agreement between the measured and predicted properties; specific measurements are needed to further investigate if this is indeed the case and then determine if the amount of residual water in the particles is the same as found by Peng et al. [78] and Peng et al. [77]. However, there appears to be some additional and probably size dependent effect still unaccounted for in the theoretical description of the cloud droplet activation for the particles investigated; likely candidates are evaporation of dried anhydrous or hydrous particles in the flow system and partitioning of the surface active dissolved acids to the droplet surface, which both provide interesting subjects for further investigation.

Chapter 5

Surfactant Partitioning and Surface Tension

The work described in this chapter aims to investigate the influence of surfactant component properties on the cloud droplet activation of aerosol particles, in particular the effects of surfactant partitioning in activating droplets. As part of the ongoing collaboration between the Aerosol Group at the University of Copenhagen, Denmark, and the group of Professor Ari Laaksonen at the University of Kuopio, Finland, I spent 5 weeks in Kuopio, Finland, for this part of my study.

Surfactant properties are potentially important characteristics of organic atmospheric aerosol components. Many of the polar functional groups identified in ambient organic compounds are associated with surfactants [66] and a number of surface active organics have been detected in atmospheric aerosol particles and cloud droplets [27]. Facchini et al. [27] found a positive correlation between measured decrease in surface tension from that of pure water and the water soluble organic carbon (WSOC) content for atmospheric samples of wet aerosol and cloud and fog water. Surface tension measurements for different fractions of the WSOC, as well as dynamic surface tension measurements, further indicated that the organic surfactants concerned were mainly water soluble and largely belonging to the class of polyacidic compounds, or humic like substances (HULIS).

Shulman et al. [95] recognized that surface active compounds present in atmospheric particles could enhance cloud droplet activation by lowering the droplet solution surface tension upon dissolution. Calculations using surface tension parameterizations derived from measurements of aqueous mixed organic acid and salt solutions in a modified form of the Köhler equation, accounting for limited solubility as well as surface tension variations, showed a depression of the critical supersaturation due to the dependence of the Kelvin effect on surface tension. Facchini et al. [28] observed up to 30% decrease in surface tension from the pure water value for cloud and fog samples evaporated to concentrations expected for droplets near activation and showed that especially for smaller particle sizes a significant difference entailed in critical supersaturation for the Köhler curves calculated with and without consideration of this surface tension lowering.

Some evidence has been obtained for the significance of surfactants on activation properties of atmospheric aerosol particles. Henning et al. [42] found experimentally measured critical supersaturations for aqueous droplet solutions of selected organic acids and salt to agree well with those predicted from Köhler theory using a concentration dependent surface tension parameterized from measurements. Broekhuizen et al. [18] presented experimental evidence that the presence of even small amounts of surface active species can notably facilitate activation of particles comprising moderately soluble species. Moreover, based on model simulations, Lohmann and Leck [70] found that surface active species in the smaller particle size ranges can be invoked to explain the observed number of cloud condensation nuclei for high Arctic aerosol.

Since activating atmospheric solution droplets are sufficiently small that surfactant surface adsorption and thus droplet solution surface tension will be affected by the much greater surface to volume ratio compared to bulk solutions, Li et al. [66] proposed that surfactant partitioning should be accounted for when evaluating the surface tension of activating solution droplets. They calculated the activation of internally mixed particles comprising the surfactant sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride in various proportions from Köhler theory using the Szyszkowski equation of state [8, pp.67] for the surface tension as function of sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride bulk concentrations and modeled the change in sodium dodecyl sulfate bulk concentration due to surface adsorption with the Gibbs adsorption equation [8, pp.73-74]. Sodium dodecyl sulfate is not an atmospherically relevant compound, but is an effective, water soluble surfactant with well-known properties and thus used as a model compound for studying the principles of surfactant properties affecting cloud droplet activation behavior.

Li et al. [66] found that for pure sodium dodecyl sulfate particles, the critical supersaturation of the calculated Köhler curve is indeed lowered when the surface tension decrease due to the surfactant is accounted for. However, compared to pure sodium chloride particles the reduction in critical supersaturation due to surface tension lowering by the surfactant is dominated by an opposing increase in critical supersaturation caused by a smaller Raoult effect owing to the larger molar mass of sodium dodecyl sulfate compared to sodium chloride. This was supported by good agreement of the model results with experiments for all sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride particle mixing ratios concerned [87]. The relative importance of the CCN properties of organic surfactants and inorganic salts and the significance of taking surfactant partitioning into account when evaluating the Kelvin effect have been subject to some debate [87], [29]; nevertheless, agreement exists on the assertion that further investigation and experimental data are needed.

Sorjamaa et al. [97] noted that, as surfactant partitioning in activating droplets significantly affects the surfactant bulk concentration, this should not only be accounted for in the Kelvin effect, but also in the Raoult effect, for a proper evaluation of surfactant activation properties. With a similar approach to Gibbs surface thermodynamics as in the study of Li et al. [66], yielding only negligible difference in the Kelvin term for the droplet sizes concerned, they showed for the same internally mixed sodium dodecyl

sulfate and sodium chloride particle compositions that accounting for partitioning of sodium dodecyl sulfate in the Raoult term increases the predicted critical supersaturations compared to those of Li et al. [66]. In some cases the critical supersaturations may even exceed the values calculated using the surface tension of water without considering partitioning of the surfactant solute. For pure sodium dodecyl sulfate particles, the model predictions were compared to experimental results and it was concluded that "the experimentally determined critical supersaturations agree very well with theoretical calculations taking the surface to bulk partitioning fully into account and are much higher than those calculated neglecting partitioning".

Sorjamaa et al. [97] have also performed model calculations for the activation of particles comprising *cis*-pinonic acid, an atmospherically relevant compound, internally mixed with ammonium sulfate in varying ratios, using solubility and surface tension parameterizations based on data from Shulman et al. [95]; This has motivated the present experimental investigation of the cloud droplet activation properties of both the *cis*-pinonic acid/ammonium sulfate and the sodium dodecyl sulfate/sodium chloride particles studied by Sorjamaa et al. [97], to expound the agreement between experimental and model results found for pure sodium dodecyl sulfate particles.

5.1 Method and Procedure

For the surfactant containing particles, cloud droplet activation has been measured experimentally with the CCNC and the results compared to those of theoretical calculations, most importantly the results of the model developed by the group of Professor Ari Laaksonen at the University of Kuopio, Finland. This model takes surfactant partitioning into account in both Kelvin and Raoult terms when evaluating particle critical supersaturation from Köhler theory; it will here be referred to as the Kuopio model.

5.1.1 Choice of Compounds

The compounds chosen for investigation of the cloud droplet activation properties of surfactants are those already studied by Sorjamaa et al. [97]. Sodium dodecyl sulfate (fig. 5.1) is a model compound for water soluble surfactants obeying the Szyszkowski equation of state [66], [97], and is studied to further investigate the good agreement of the Kuopio model with experiment found for pure sodium dodecyl sulfate particles by Sorjamaa et al. [97]. As sodium dodecyl sulfate is not expected to be found in the atmosphere in significant amounts, *cis*-pinonic acid (fig. 5.2) is studied as an example of an atmospherically relevant compound; *cis*-pinonic acid is a major oxidation product of α -Pinene [91], [35], [65], a monoterpene abundantly emitted from trees on a global scale [38], [95], and has been found in secondary organic aerosol (SOA) in forests [53] as well as in smog-chamber experiments [36]. Thus, *cis*-pinonic acid is one of the organic compounds found in the atmosphere whose properties it is of greatest importance to understand in more detail.

Figure 5.1: Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS).

Figure 5.2: *cis*-Pinonic acid (CPA).

The abbreviations SDS, CPA, SC and AS will be used throughout the chapter for sodium dodecyl sulfate, *cis*-pinonic acid, sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate, respectively. Also, subscripts *sft*, *s* and *w* will generally denote properties of organic surfactant, salt and water.

5.1.2 Experimental

Particles composed of sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride mixed in approximate mass ratios 80:20, 50:50 and 20:80, pure *cis*-pinonic acid and approximate mass mixing ratios 95:5, 80:20, 50:50 and 20:80 of *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate were generated as described in section 3.1.2. The precise particle compositions in terms of respective surfactant and salt mass percentages $X_{p, sft}^m$ and $X_{p, s}^m$ were calculated with equation 3.5 from the weighed masses of surfactant and salt m_a^w and m_s^w used for preparing the solution in the atomizer bottle; the weighed compound masses and resulting particle compositions are given in tables 5.1 and 5.2.

For the experiments concerning *cis*-pinonic acid containing particles, no aerosol size distributions were obtained from SMPS measurements. However, for the sodium dodecyl sulfate containing particles, size distributions were scanned before commencing the activation measurements with each particle composition;

The measured size distributions for particles comprising 50% and 80% sodium dodecyl sulfate turned out somewhat irregular and apparently bi- or multi-modal; thus a number of measures were adopted to improve the shape of the generated particle size distributions: First, the flow system was examined for leaks to ensure that the aerosol flow was not contaminated with particles from ambient air. To counter speculated insufficient

drying of the generated initially wet aerosol, the atomizer solution was diluted and the atomizer pressure was reduced. This results in fewer particles in the wet aerosol, which will be easier to dry during the limited time of passage through the diffusion driers. Fresh drying material was filled into the driers, and subsequently an additional drying element was inserted. The relative humidity was measured several places in the flow system and was below 10%. Finally, the atomizer solution was placed on magnetic stirring to ensure that the surfactant remained evenly distributed in solution throughout the experiments.

Despite the efforts, the 50% and 80% sodium dodecyl sulfate particle size distributions remained somewhat irregular, though not identical to those initially determined. Experiments were thus performed with particles selected from these distributions (fig. 5.3).

Figure 5.3: SMPS scans of size distributions for generated polydisperse mixed sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride particles containing 50% (left) and 80% (right) sodium dodecyl sulfate by mass respectively. The shapes of the distributions are irregular and at least two particle modes appear to be present. Note the different scales on the y-axes in the two plots.

Cloud droplet activation was measured for the generated sodium dodecyl sulfate and *cis*-pinonic acid containing particles in the size range $D_p \in [20 - 120]$ nm. Activation measurements and retrieval of the final experimental results for the particle compositions concerned in this chapter were performed completely analogous to the procedure applied for the acid containing particles as described in chapter 4.

particle composition	80:20 SDS/SC	50:50 SDS/SC	20:80 SDS/SC
$X_{p, SDS}^m$ [%]	80.78	51.40	19.50
$X_{p, SC}^m$ [%]	19.22	48.60	80.50
m_{SDS}^w [g]	0.0500	0.0494	0.0513
m_{SC}^w [g]	0.0119	0.0467	0.2118

Table 5.1: Experimental mixed sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) and sodium chloride (SC) particle compositions in terms of the respective mass percentages $X_{p, SDS}^m$ and $X_{p, SC}^m$, along with the originally weighed masses m_{SDS}^w and m_{SC}^w for preparation of the solution in the atomizer bottle.

particle composition	pure CPA	95:5 CPA/AS	80:20 CPA/AS	50:50 CPA/AS	20:80 CPA/AS
$X_{p, CPA}^m$ [%]	100	92.50	80.18	49.40	20.90
$X_{p, AS}^m$ [%]	-	7.50	19.82	50.60	79.10
m_{CPA}^w [g]	-	0.0970	0.0890	0.05737	0.0240
m_{AS}^w [g]	-	0.0079	0.0220	0.0550	0.0908

Table 5.2: Experimental mixed *cis*-pinonic acid (CPA) and ammonium sulfate (AS) particle compositions in terms of the respective mass percentages $X_{p, CPA}^m$ and $X_{p, AS}^m$, along with the originally weighed masses m_{CPA}^w and m_{AS}^w for preparation of the solution in the atomizer bottle.

5.1.3 The Kuopio Model

The basis for the Kuopio model is described in detail by Sorjamaa et al. [97], including references to Li et al. [66]; only the fundamental equations are mentioned here.

Modeling Partitioning

For each droplet solution component i (water w , organic surfactant solute sft and salt s , respectively), the surface excess number of moles is defined as in section 2.3.4 by

$$n_i^S = n_i^T - n_i^B \quad (5.1)$$

where n_i^T is the total number of moles of i in solution and n_i^B the number of moles of i in the solution bulk phase. The position of the Gibbs dividing surface is given by the condition

$$\sum_i n_i^S v_i = 0 \quad (5.2)$$

where v_i is the partial molar volume of component i in the solution. For the definition of the Gibbs dividing surface given by equation 5.2, it has been shown that the droplet surface tension equals that of a flat surface, regardless of the surface curvature [63]; thus any complications arising from the droplet surface tension curvature dependence

[8, pp.54-55] are avoided for all droplet sizes.

Partitioning is accounted for by application of the Gibbs adsorption equation in the form [8, pp.73]

$$A^S d\sigma + \sum_i n_i^S d\mu_i = 0 \quad (5.3)$$

for constant temperature and pressure. A^S and σ are the droplet surface area and surface tension, and μ_i is the chemical potential of component i , which at equilibrium must be identical in the surface and bulk phases according to condition 2.5. The chemical potentials are thus employed using the bulk activities $a_i^B = \gamma_i^B x_i^B$ as given in terms of the bulk mole fractions x_i^B and according activity coefficients γ_i^B . The solute bulk mole fractions are given by

$$x_j^B = \frac{n_j^B}{n_w^B + \sum_k \nu_k n_k^B} \quad (5.4)$$

where ν_j is the number of species generated upon dissolution of solute j , which exceeds unity in case of dissociation. Specifically, the values $\nu_{SC} = 2$, $\nu_{AS} = 3$, $\nu_{SDS} = 2$ and $\nu_{CPA} = 1$ have been employed. Note that equation 5.4 differs from the definition 2.18 used in the remainder of this work.

Assuming spherical droplets, the volume of a droplet with radius r is given by

$$V = \frac{4}{3}\pi r^3 = \sum_i n_i^T v_i \stackrel{5.2}{=} \sum_i n_i^B v_i \quad (5.5)$$

hereby relating the droplet size and number of bulk moles.

The equilibrium number of surface excess and bulk moles n_i^S and n_i^B for all droplet solution components i are determined by iterating the relations given above with adoption of appropriate expressions for the solution bulk activity coefficients γ_i^B ; the number of surfactant and salt solute bulk moles n_{sft}^B and n_s^B thus determined are then applied for assertion of the Kelvin and Raoult effects, respectively.

To attain a sufficient number of equations for the iteration procedure, the assumption that the ratio of water and salt moles is constant throughout the droplet is additionally applied

$$\frac{x_w^B}{x_s^B} = \frac{n_w^B}{n_s^B} = \frac{n_w^S}{n_s^S} = \frac{n_w^T}{n_s^T} \quad (5.6)$$

This is believed to be reasonable, since ammonium sulfate and sodium chloride are only weakly surface active, as seen in section 3.2.2, and the surface excess number of moles of the salts for the droplet solution compositions in question therefore expected to be small.

When determining the total number of surfactant moles n_{sft}^T in the droplet solution, solubilities of the organic surfactants in the appropriate salt solutions need to be considered. Sodium dodecyl sulfate is assumed to be completely soluble for all droplet sizes,

but *cis*-pinonic acid is only slightly soluble in aqueous solutions, and thus the magnitude of the *cis*-pinonic acid solubility as function of ammonium sulfate bulk concentration has been parameterized using measurements from Shulman et al. [95]

$$c_{CPA}^{sol,s} = \frac{c_{CPA}^{sol,w}}{1 - 0.15c_{AS}^B + 1.46c_{AS}^{B^2} + 0.55c_{AS}^{B^3}}, \quad c_{AS}^B < 3.0 \text{ mol/L}, \quad 273.15 \text{ K} \quad (5.7)$$

$c_{CPA}^{sol,w}$ is the solubility of *cis*-pinonic acid in pure water; Raymond and Pandis [84] give the value $C_{CPA}^{sol,w} = 0.64 - 0.71 \text{ g}/100 \text{ cm}^3 H_2O(293.15 \text{ K})$, from which the average value $C_{CPA}^{sol,w} = 0.675 \text{ g}/100 \text{ cm}^3 H_2O$ has been adopted.

Attaining the Kelvin and Raoult Terms

Droplet solution surface tensions are determined from the iterated number of surfactant and salt bulk moles and subsequently employed for evaluation of the Kelvin effect. For the mixed sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride solution droplets, the surface tension is given as function of the respective surfactant and salt bulk concentrations c_{sft}^B and c_s^B by the Szyszkowski equation of state

$$\sigma = \sigma_w - RT\Gamma_m \ln \left(\frac{c_{sft}^B}{\beta} + 1 \right) \quad (5.8)$$

$\sigma_w = 0.073 \text{ N/m}$ is the surface tension of pure water, and R and T the gas constant and Kelvin temperature; Γ_m and β are the so-called Szyszkowski parameters, representing the maximum (saturation) surfactant surface excess concentration $\Gamma_m = N_{sft}^S/A^S$ (where N_{sft}^S is defined in section 2.3.4 as the saturation value of the surfactant surface excess amount in moles) and the surfactant bulk concentration for which the surface excess concentration reaches half its maximum value $\Gamma(c_{sft}^B = \beta) = \Gamma_m/2$, respectively. The solution surface tension dependence on the salt bulk concentration originates from the effect of the salt on the surfactant surface adsorption efficiency (see section 2.3.4) and enters in equation 5.8 through the Szyszkowski parameters, which have been parameterized from measurements of sodium dodecyl sulfate solution surface tension as function of sodium chloride salt bulk concentration by Li et al. [66].

For *cis*-pinonic acid, the surfactant properties are less well-characterized owing to lack of information on the appropriate equation of state; the *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate solution surface tension bulk composition dependence is therefore parameterized from the measurements of Shulman et al. [95] as

$$\sigma = \sigma_w + 0.003167c_{AS}^B - 0.041085(1 + c_{AS}^B)c_{CPA}^B{}^{0.383714}, \quad c_{AS}^B < 2.0 \text{ mol/L} \quad (5.9)$$

where c_{CPA}^B and c_{AS}^B are the respective bulk concentrations of *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate. Interestingly, of the mixed organic and salt solutions studied by Shulman et al. [95], only the *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate solutions display dependence of the surface tension on concentrations of both solutes.

The Raoult effect is evaluated from the effective number of solute moles in the droplet bulk

$$n_m^B = \phi_{sft}^B \nu_{sft}^B f_{sft}^{dissolv} n_{sft}^B + \phi_s^B \nu_s^B n_s^B \quad (5.10)$$

which will yield the water activity explicitly as an effective mole fraction by

$$a_w^B = \frac{n_w^B}{n_w^B + n_m^B} \quad (5.11)$$

In equation 5.10, ϕ_{sft}^B and ϕ_s^B are the molal osmotic coefficients of surfactant and salt in the droplet solution bulk, for which the values $\phi_{SDS}^B = 0.75$ and $\phi_{CPA}^B = \phi_{SC}^B = \phi_{AS}^B = 1$ are used. ν_{sft}^B and ν_s^B are the mentioned number of solute species generated from each respective surfactant and salt molecule dissolved. $f_{sft}^{dissolv}$ is the dissolved fraction of surfactant, which for sodium dodecyl sulfate is assumed to be unity, and for *cis*-pinonic acid is determined from equation 5.7. Finally, n_{sft}^B and n_s^B are the number of bulk moles of surfactant and salt iterated accounting for partitioning as described above.

Given the appropriate evaluations of the Kelvin and Raoult effects, cloud droplet activation is then calculated from the Köhler equation in the form given by Seinfeld and Pandis [92, pp.786] (where the relation $\ln(s) = \ln(ss + 1) \approx ss$ between the saturation and supersaturation ratios s and ss has been applied).

5.1.4 Additional Calculations

The experimentally determined activation properties of the surfactant containing particles and the corresponding predictions by the Kuopio model are compared to the results of other calculation approaches for assessment of the importance of accounting for partitioning in evaluating the cloud droplet activation of the particle systems in question and to further explore the possible occurrence of other effects governing the activation process in addition to surfactant partitioning.

Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate Containing Particles

For the mixed sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride particles, the same calculation approaches are applied as by Sorjamaa et al. [97]:

- The Kuopio model, as described above, accounting for surfactant partitioning when evaluating both Kelvin and Raoult terms. Results of these calculations are referred to as "Kuopio model".
- The model of Li et al. [66], taking the effect of partitioning on surfactant bulk concentration into account when determining the droplet solution surface tension for the Kelvin term, but evaluating the Raoult effect assuming all surfactant and salt solute resides in the droplet bulk. It should be noted, that Li et al. [66] uses a definition of the Gibbs dividing surface which differs from that of Sorjamaa et al. [97], but the effect on the resulting surfactant bulk concentration is negligible for the sodium dodecyl sulfate containing particles concerned [97]. Results of these calculations are referred to as "Li, 1998".

- Activation calculations with no consideration of partitioning, where the magnitudes of both surface tension (ST) lowering and Raoult effect are thus determined assuming the concentration resulting from all surfactant solute being present in the droplet bulk. These results are referred to as "no partitioning, ST lowered".
- Activation calculations with no consideration of partitioning, assuming the droplet solution surface tension is constant and equal to that of pure water $\sigma_w = 0.073 \text{ N/m}$ [97] and evaluating the Raoult term for all surfactant solute residing in the droplet bulk. Results of these calculations are referred to as "no partitioning, ST water".

cis-Pinonic Acid Containing Particles

The model of Li et al. [66] cannot be used for predicting activation of the mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particles studied, since, in the form given, it only applies to the sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride containing particles. Moreover, as will be seen in section 5.2.2 below, the experimental activation results of the *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particles with the highest organic surfactant content gives reason to suspect that the particles are insufficiently dried and therefore constitute supersaturated solution droplets instead of dry solid particles. Consequently, for the mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particles, the following calculation approaches are applied:

- The Kuopio model, accounting for partitioning in both Kelvin and Raoult terms as well as the limited solubility of *cis*-pinonic acid given by equation 5.7. Results of these calculations are referred to as "Kuopio model, limited solubility".
- The Kuopio model, taking partitioning fully into account, but assuming full solubility of *cis*-pinonic acid in all droplet solutions: This approach is employed to represent the experimental behavior of supersaturated solution droplets, where the solute is fully dissolved from the beginning of droplet growth. These results are referred to as "Kuopio model, full solubility".
- Activation calculations with no consideration of partitioning, but accounting for the limited and ammonium sulfate concentration dependent solubility of *cis*-pinonic acid given by equation 5.7 when evaluating the *cis*-pinonic acid concentration for determination of both surface tension lowering and Raoult effect. These results are referred to as "no partitioning, limited solubility".
- Activation calculations with no consideration of partitioning, assuming full solubility of *cis*-pinonic acid and a constant droplet solution surface tension equal to that of a saturated solution of *cis*-pinonic acid $\sigma_{CPA}^{sat} = 0.053 \text{ N/m}$ [84]. These conditions are supposed to yield the largest attainable Kelvin and Raoult effects for the droplets in question and thus provide an estimate of the lowest possible critical supersaturations for the *cis*-pinonic acid containing particles studied. Consequently, the calculation results are referred to as "minimum".

It should be noted, that the *cis*-pinonic acid solubilities were measured by Shulman et al. [95] at 273.15 K, and the functional expression of parameterization 5.7 is therefore strictly valid only at this temperature. However, the value substituted for the solubility of *cis*-pinonic acid in pure water is determined at 293.15 K, whereas the Kuopio and other model calculations corresponding to the activation measurements of the mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particles were performed at 298.15 K. Employing the solubility parameterization derived from the lower temperature data may affect the applicability of the theoretical activation predictions; measurements of *cis*-pinonic acid solubility in aqueous ammonium sulfate solutions at ambient temperature are being contemplated for the derivation of a solubility parameterization appropriate for comparison with activation measurements performed at these temperatures.

At sufficiently high aqueous solution concentrations, surfactants begin to cluster and form particle-like structures called micelles imbedded in the solution; within the micelle structure, the hydrophobic hydrocarbon tails of the surfactant molecules are grouped together in the core and shielded from the aqueous environment by the hydrophilic polar ends pointing out towards the solution, thereby minimizing the unfavorable polar non-polar interactions between water and the hydrocarbon surfactant parts. The concentration at which micelles begin to form is called the critical micelle concentration. Above this threshold, the effective amount in moles of surfactant solute in the solution bulk and thus the solution surface tension are nearly constant [66], [8, pp.69].

The critical micelle concentration has been parameterized as function of salt concentration for mixed sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride solutions by Li et al. [66] and is accounted for in the activation calculations concerning sodium dodecyl sulfate containing particles. This has not been done for the mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particles; however, there is no indication that this has any significant effect on the present calculated activation results for *cis*-pinonic acid containing particles, likely owing to all droplets concerned being diluted below the critical micelle concentration at activation. Therefore, this effect will not be discussed further.

5.2 Results and Discussion

The experimental and model calculation results for the activation of sodium dodecyl sulfate and *cis*-pinonic acid containing particles are given in sections 5.2.1 and 5.2.2, respectively. The model results "Kuopio model", "Li, 1998", "no partitioning, ST lowered", and "no partitioning, ST water" for the sodium dodecyl sulfate/sodium chloride particles and "Kuopio model, limited solubility" and "Kuopio model, full solubility" for the *cis*-pinonic acid/ammonium sulfate particles have been calculated by Riikka Sorjamaa from the group of Professor Ari Laaksonen at the University of Kuopio, Finland, and kindly communicated to me for use in this work.

5.2.1 Results for Sodium Dodecyl Sulfate

The experimentally determined critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{exp})$ for the mixed sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride particles are shown in fig. 5.4 for all dry particle diameters D_p of the three compositions measured, along with the activation measurement results for pure sodium chloride particles originally performed for calibration of the CCNC as described in section 3.2.2.

Figure 5.4: Experimental critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{exp})$ measured at dry particle sizes D_p for particles comprising 80.78%, 51.40% and 19.50% by mass, respectively, of sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) mixed with sodium chloride (SC) and for pure sodium chloride particles, measured for the CCNC calibration as described in section 3.2.2. For each particle composition, the critical supersaturation declines with increasing dry particle size in a regular fashion, as expected from Köhler theory (see section 2.3.3), and the increase in critical supersaturation with increasing sodium dodecyl sulfate fraction for a given dry particle size is clearly evident.

The estimated experimental uncertainty is in the range $2\sigma_{SS_c(\text{exp})} \in [0.0165 - 0.0577] \%$ for all investigated mixed sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride particles and therefore not very large, as was also found for the citric and malic acid containing particles.

Particles of each composition are seen to activate in the regular fashion expected from Köhler theory (see section 2.3.3), with critical supersaturations steadily declining for

increasing dry particle sizes. Qualitatively, the relative order of activation is as expected from the respective mass density to molar mass ratios of sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride

$$\frac{\rho_{SDS}}{M_{SDS}} \stackrel{\text{see [97]}}{=} \frac{1.176[\text{g}/\text{cm}^3]}{288.38[\text{g}/\text{mol}]} = 4.078 \cdot 10^{-3}[\text{mol}/\text{cm}^3] \quad (5.12)$$

and

$$\frac{\rho_{SC}}{M_{SC}} \stackrel{\text{section 3.2.2}}{=} \frac{2.170[\text{g}/\text{cm}^3]}{58.443[\text{g}/\text{mol}]} = 37.13 \cdot 10^{-3}[\text{mol}/\text{cm}^3] \quad (5.13)$$

in that the critical supersaturation for particles with a given dry diameter consistently increases for increasing sodium dodecyl sulfate mass fraction. The very large difference in the sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride mass density to molar mass ratios is however not reflected in the experimental results, which clearly indicates the presence of an additional factor influencing the activation properties of the investigated particles. The dissociation properties of sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride are believed to be similar ($\nu_{SDS} = 2$ and $\nu_{SC} = 2$) and therefore not the cause of any difference in activation behavior for these compounds. Thus, the quantitative differences in observed activation for the particle compositions concerned strongly suggest an effect of sodium dodecyl sulfate surfactant properties on droplet activation.

The observed activation order nevertheless indicates, that the droplet solution surface tension lowering and resulting decreased Kelvin effect attained from the surfactant properties of sodium dodecyl sulfate is dominated by the decreased Raoult effect due to the greatly decreased amount in moles of solute in the droplet solutions formed when sodium dodecyl sulfate replaces sodium chloride in dry particles of a given size, owing to the smaller mass density to molar mass ratio of sodium dodecyl sulfate compared to sodium chloride. This effect was also found in the theoretical treatment of mixed sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride solution droplet activation properties by Li et al. [66] and subsequently observed experimentally by Rood and Williams [87].

The critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{model})$ calculated as function of dry particle diameter D_p from the different modeling approaches described in sections 5.1.3 and 5.1.4 above are shown together with the experimental results $SS_c(\text{exp})$ for each of the mixed sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride particle compositions in fig.s 5.5, 5.6 and 5.7.

Overall, the agreement with experiments of the model taking surfactant partitioning into account in both Kelvin and Raoult terms ("Kuopio model"), the model accounting for partitioning only in the Kelvin term ("Li, 1998") and the calculations without consideration of partitioning employing a surface tension value equal to that of pure water ("no partitioning, ST water") is fairly good, though only within the depicted experimental error for the particles containing the smallest fraction of sodium dodecyl sulfate. On the other hand, the agreement of the calculations assuming no partitioning and a surface tension lowering according to all surfactant being present in the droplet solution bulk ("no partitioning, ST lowered") is poor, as the approach clearly underestimates

the experimental critical supersaturations for all particle compositions and sizes. It is seen, that the level of agreement decreases for decreasing particle size for each sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride particle composition studied.

For the three calculation approaches agreeing well with experiment, the relative activation order in terms of calculated critical supersaturation for a given dry particle size, as well as the level of agreement with experiments, increases in the order "Li, 1998" < "no partitioning, ST water" < "Kuopio model". This is seen consistently for each of the mixed sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride particle compositions investigated. However, except for the particles comprising the largest fraction of surfactant, the differences in activation behavior predicted by these models are small.

Figure 5.5: Modeled and experimental critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{model})$ and $SS_c(\text{exp})$ for dry particles comprising 19.50% sodium dodecyl sulfate. Model "Kuopio model" accounts for surfactant partitioning in both Kelvin and Raoult terms, whereas model "Li, 1998" considers partitioning only in the Kelvin term. Calculations "no partitioning, ST lowered" determines surface tension lowering without account for partitioning and the approach "no partitioning, ST water" disregards surfactant properties deploying a surface tension equal to that of pure water. Further description of the model approaches is given in sections 5.1.3 and 5.1.4.

Figure 5.6: Modeled and experimental critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{model})$ and $SS_c(\text{exp})$ for dry particles comprising 51.40% sodium dodecyl sulfate. Model "Kuopio model" accounts for surfactant partitioning in both Kelvin and Raoult terms, whereas model "Li, 1998" considers partitioning only in the Kelvin term. Calculations "no partitioning, ST lowered" determines surface tension lowering without account for partitioning and the approach "no partitioning, ST water" disregards surfactant properties deploying a surface tension equal to that of pure water. Further description of the model approaches is given in sections 5.1.3 and 5.1.4.

Figure 5.7: Modeled and experimental critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{model})$ and $SS_c(\text{exp})$ for dry particles comprising 80.78% sodium dodecyl sulfate. Model "Kuopio model" accounts for surfactant partitioning in both Kelvin and Raoult terms, whereas model "Li, 1998" considers partitioning only in the Kelvin term. Calculations "no partitioning, ST lowered" determines surface tension lowering without account for partitioning and the approach "no partitioning, ST water" disregards surfactant properties deploying a surface tension equal to that of pure water. Further description of the model approaches is given in sections 5.1.3 and 5.1.4.

The differences in activation behavior predicted by the various calculation approaches can be rationalized as follows: The models "Kuopio model" and "Li, 1998" accounts for the effects of surfactant partitioning on both Kelvin and Raoult terms and on the Kelvin term only, respectively. The calculation approach "no partitioning, ST lowered" handles surfactant properties by determining surface tension lowering without consideration of partitioning, while the approach "no partitioning, ST water" disregards surfactant properties altogether, treating the surfactant as a general solute and deploying a surface tension equal to that of pure water. Therefore, the effect of accounting for surfactant partitioning on the established Kelvin effect in terms of the evaluated surface tension of the activating solution droplets can be discerned from the difference between the results of the model "Li, 1998" and the calculation approach "no partitioning, ST lowered", whereas the effect of taking surfactant partitioning into account when determining the Raoult effect from the amount in moles of dissolved solute in the droplet bulk is evident from the difference between the predicted activation of the models "Kuopio model"

and "Li, 1998". Finally, the difference between critical supersaturation results from the calculation approach "no partitioning, ST water" and "Kuopio model", "Li, 1998" and "no partitioning, ST lowered", respectively, yields the effect on cloud droplet activation of accounting for surfactant properties in each of these ways. Within this context, the relative levels of agreement with the experimentally determined activation properties of the investigated mixed sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride particles displayed by the results of each calculation approach are interpreted as indications of the significance of the particular effects underlying the differences in the theoretically predicted activation.

The experimental activation results for the investigated mixed sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride particles are first compared to the corresponding activation properties calculated from the approaches considering the effects of sodium dodecyl sulfate surfactant properties on droplet solution surface tension in different ways, "Li, 1998" and "no partitioning, ST lowered". The better agreement with experiments of the predictions by the model accounting for surfactant partitioning, "Li, 1998", compared to those of the calculations determining the surface tension lowering, by sodium dodecyl sulfate without consideration of partitioning, "no partitioning, ST lowered", clearly indicates, that if the surfactant properties of sodium dodecyl sulfate are to be considered when determining the droplet solution surface tension for calculation of cloud droplet activation properties of the particles concerned, it is important to account for the partitioning of sodium dodecyl sulfate in the activating droplets, to avoid underestimating the experimental critical supersaturations. If partitioning of sodium dodecyl sulfate is neglected, the droplet solution bulk concentration and thus the surface tension decrease due to sodium dodecyl sulfate appear to be highly overestimated, in turn leading to overestimating the magnitude of the Kelvin effect suppression caused by the presence of sodium dodecyl sulfate in the activating droplets and a subsequent underestimation of the experimental critical supersaturation, as seen for the calculation approach "no partitioning, ST lowered".

The relative difference in agreement with experiments of the respective activation behavior predicted by the model accounting for surfactant partitioning, "Li, 1998", and the calculations evaluating the sodium dodecyl sulfate surface tension lowering without considering partitioning, "no partitioning, ST lowered", increases for decreasing dry particle sizes; this is seen for each of the mixed sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride particle compositions studied, but the effect is greater for dry particles with larger mass fraction of the surfactant. The effects of surfactant partitioning on cloud droplet activation properties are expected to innately be more evident for smaller particles [97], since smaller dry particles form smaller solution droplets with larger surface area to volume ratios promoting surfactant surface adsorption, as well as for droplets with larger fractions of surfactant solute, where the surfactant properties will consequently pose a larger overall influence on activation. These observations therefore support the interpretation that the different levels of agreement with experiments displayed by the critical supersaturations predicted by accounting for and disregarding partitioning, respectively, are indeed caused by the different approaches to the effect of sodium dodecyl sulfate

partitioning on surface tension lowering in the activating solution droplets investigated. Thus, if the surface tension lowering by sodium dodecyl sulfate is considered, surfactant partitioning should also be taken into account when evaluating the cloud droplet activation properties of the investigated mixed sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride particles.

Comparing the relative level of agreement with the experimental critical supersaturations for the mixed sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride particles obtained by the activation predicted from the two models taking surfactant partitioning into account, "Kuopio model" and "Li, 1998", respectively, furthermore shows that accounting for sodium dodecyl sulfate partitioning in evaluation of both Kelvin and Raoult effects produces a better description of the experimentally determined activation properties than considering the effect of partitioning solely within the context of sodium dodecyl sulfate surface tension lowering. This is not unexpected, as partitioning should indeed affect activation through both Kelvin and Raoult terms by decreasing the amount in moles of surfactant solute in the droplet solution bulk. The difference between the critical supersaturations predicted by the two model approaches is barely discernible for the dry particles comprising approximately 20% by mass of sodium dodecyl sulfate, where both partitioning models give very good agreement with experiments; however, both the difference between the respective modeled activation results and the relatively better agreement with experiment of the model taking sodium dodecyl sulfate partitioning fully into account, "Kuopio model", increases with larger sodium dodecyl sulfate mass fractions of the dry particles. This implies that as sodium dodecyl sulfate comprises a larger fraction of the dry particles and thus makes a larger relative contribution to the cloud droplet activation properties of the solution droplets formed, a detailed evaluation of the collective effects of sodium dodecyl sulfate surfactant properties becomes increasingly important for a proper prediction of the experimental critical supersaturations.

The difference in the relative level of agreement with experiment is much greater between the activation properties predicted from the calculation approaches "Li, 1998" and "no partitioning, ST lowered" than between "Li, 1998" and "Kuopio model" for each of the mixed sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride particle compositions investigated. This is interpreted as the effect of surfactant partitioning being relatively more significant for evaluation of the Kelvin effect than of the Raoult effect when describing the activation properties of the mixed sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride particles in question. A likely explanation is the combined effect of the strong surfactant properties of sodium dodecyl sulfate, which enhances the importance for cloud droplet activation of surface tension and Kelvin effect relative to the Raoult effect, and the much lower mass density to molar mass ratio of sodium dodecyl sulfate compared to sodium chloride, which entails that a large dry particle sodium dodecyl sulfate mass fraction is required for the surfactant solute to make a significant relative contribution to the Raoult effect and thus for the influence of sodium dodecyl sulfate partitioning on the total Raoult effect to be discerned. Since neither sodium dodecyl sulfate nor the mixed sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride particle compositions studied are atmospherically relevant, however, this relatively greater importance of partitioning for

the Kelvin effect compared to the Raoult effect is not necessarily upheld for surfactant constituents of atmospheric aerosol particles.

The results for the mixed sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride particles investigated indicate, that the collective effect of sodium dodecyl sulfate partitioning in activating droplets is to increase the critical supersaturations compared to those expected from considering the surfactant properties of sodium dodecyl sulfate without accounting for partitioning, owing to a less effective suppression of the Kelvin effect and a decreased Raoult effect. Comparison with experimental results confirm the ability of the Kuopio model to successfully predict the cloud droplet activation behavior of the particles studied and thus extend the findings of Sorjamaa et al. [97] for pure sodium dodecyl sulfate particles to mixed sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride particles of the compositions in question.

Even though the model taking surfactant partitioning fully into account, "Kuopio model", gives unsurpassed agreement with the experimental critical supersaturations for the mixed sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride particles concerned, it is remarkable that the calculations disregarding sodium dodecyl sulfate surfactant properties completely, "no partitioning, ST lowered", predicts the observed activation nearly as well; the difference in the level of agreement with experiments of the two approaches only becomes significant for the dry particles with the largest sodium dodecyl sulfate mass fraction studied. This may lead to speculation of whether consideration of surfactant properties is important in connection to evaluating cloud droplet activation properties of aerosol particles comprising organic surfactants. However, the objective for studying sodium dodecyl sulfate containing particles has been to establish a model system comprising a water soluble, strong surfactant with well-quantified properties, where possible effects of surfactant properties on droplet activation are expected to be most easily discernible and quantifiable, and thus to test the ability of models employing these properties in various ways to predict the observed activation behavior for such particles. As mentioned, the surfactant and observed cloud droplet activation properties of sodium dodecyl sulfate may not be representative of organic surfactants found in atmospheric aerosol particles. It is therefore necessary to investigate the activation properties of atmospherically relevant surfactants before determining the significance of surfactant properties in general, and of surfactant partitioning in droplet solutions in particular, to cloud droplet formation in the atmosphere. One such organic surfactant found in the atmosphere is *cis*-pinonic acid, which is investigated in the next section.

5.2.2 Results for *cis*-Pinonic Acid

The experimental critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{exp})$ determined for each dry particle size D_p of pure *cis*-pinonic acid particles and the four different mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particle compositions studied are shown in fig. 5.8, accompanied by the activation results for pure ammonium sulfate particles originally measured for calibration of the CCNC as described in section 3.2.2.

For the mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particles, the estimated experimental uncertainties are of the same magnitude as seen for both citric and malic acid and sodium dodecyl sulfate containing particles and fall within the range $2\sigma_{SS_c(\text{exp})} \in [0.0151 - 0.0516] \%$. In the case of pure *cis*-pinonic acid particles, the estimated experimental uncertainties are about twice as large, covering the range $2\sigma_{SS_c(\text{exp})} \in [0.0224 - 0.1203] \%$.

Figure 5.8: Experimental critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{exp})$ measured at dry particle sizes D_p for particles comprising pure *cis*-pinonic acid (CPA), 92.50%, 80.18%, 49.40 and 20.90% by mass of *cis*-pinonic acid mixed with ammonium sulfate (AS), respectively, and for pure ammonium sulfate particles, measured for the CCNC calibration as described in section 3.2.2. Except for the pure *cis*-pinonic acid particles, the activation behavior for each particle composition is regular and displays the expected decline in critical supersaturation with increasing dry particle size according to Köhler theory (see section 2.3.3). However, the relative activation order show no immediate regularity with respect to decreasing mass fraction of ammonium sulfate for a given dry particle size.

For each of the mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particle compositions, the observed critical supersaturation $SS_c(\text{exp})$ decreases regularly for increasing dry particle size D_p as expected from Köhler theory (see section 2.3.3), whereas the activation trend for pure *cis*-pinonic acid particles is somewhat more irregular; some of this irregularity may be acquired upon fitting the activation measurement data, as the

activation point is not always well-defined for the pure *cis*-pinonic acid particles. Due to the large number of individually measured activation ratios, the uncertainty related to the fitting procedure and thus the estimated overall uncertainty for the experimental critical supersaturation of the pure *cis*-pinonic acid particles as described in section 3.3 nevertheless turn out reasonably small.

Pure *cis*-pinonic acid particles activate for larger critical supersaturations than both the mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particle of different compositions and the pure ammonium sulfate particles, as qualitatively expected from the respective dissociation behavior ($1 \leq \nu_{CPA} < 2$ and $\nu_{AS} \leq 3$) and mass density to molar mass ratios

$$\frac{\rho_{CPA}}{M_{CPA}} \stackrel{\text{see [84]}}{=} \frac{0.786[\text{g}/\text{cm}^3]}{184.24[\text{g}/\text{mol}]} = 4.266 \cdot 10^{-3}[\text{mol}/\text{cm}^3] \quad (5.14)$$

and $\rho_{AS}/M_{AS} = 13.39 \cdot 10^{-3}[\text{mol}/\text{cm}^3]$ (see section 4.2.1) of *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate. Unfortunately, no value for the acid dissociation constant of *cis*-pinonic acid has been found, but it is mentioned to be a weak acid [97] and a dissociation factor of $\nu_{CPA} = 1$ has previously been employed [97], [84], [41]. Consequently, the dissociation of ammonium sulfate in droplet solutions will contribute to the observed difference in activation for pure *cis*-pinonic acid and pure ammonium sulfate particles, which is clearly not overcome by the surfactant properties of *cis*-pinonic acid.

The relative activation order of a given size particles with the different mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate compositions is however more fortuitous; there appears to be no connection to either the dissociation behavior or the mass density to molar mass ratios of *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate, and it is remarkable that the mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particles of all compositions activate more or less like pure ammonium sulfate particles. Possible reasons for this observation will be discussed in the following.

In fig.s 5.9, 5.10, 5.11 and 5.12, the critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{model})$ calculated as function of dry particle diameter D_p from the different modeling approaches described in sections 5.1.3 and 5.1.4 are shown together with the corresponding experimental results $SS_c(\text{exp})$ for each of the mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particle compositions investigated. No model data is yet obtained for the pure *cis*-pinonic acid particle activation but is currently being contemplated by the group of Professor Ari Laaksonen at the University of Kuopio, Finland.

Figure 5.9: Modeled and experimental critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{model})$ and $SS_c(\text{exp})$ for dry particles comprising 20.90% by mass of *cis*-pinonic acid. Model "Kuopio model, limited solubility" takes *cis*-pinonic acid partitioning into account in both Kelvin and Raoult terms and applies parameterization 5.7 for the limited *cis*-pinonic acid solubility, while model "Kuopio model, full solubility" takes *cis*-pinonic acid partitioning fully into account, but assumes full solubility of *cis*-pinonic acid in droplet solutions. Calculations "no partitioning, limited solubility" considers the *cis*-pinonic acid solubility through parameterization 5.7, disregarding partitioning and the approach "minimum" gives a lower estimate of the activation by employing full *cis*-pinonic acid solubility and a constant surface tension equal to that of a saturated *cis*-pinonic acid solution. Further description of the model approaches is given in sections 5.1.3 and 5.1.4. Note the change of scale on the x-axis compared to fig. 5.8.

Figure 5.10: Modeled and experimental critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{model})$ and $SS_c(\text{exp})$ for dry particles comprising 49.40% by mass of *cis*-pinonic acid. Model "Kuopio model, limited solubility" takes *cis*-pinonic acid partitioning into account in both Kelvin and Raoult terms and applies parameterization 5.7 for the limited *cis*-pinonic acid solubility, while model "Kuopio model, full solubility" takes *cis*-pinonic acid partitioning fully into account, but assumes full solubility of *cis*-pinonic acid in droplet solutions. Calculations "no partitioning, limited solubility" considers the *cis*-pinonic acid solubility through parameterization 5.7, disregarding partitioning and the approach "minimum" gives a lower estimate of the activation by employing full *cis*-pinonic acid solubility and a constant surface tension equal to that of a saturated *cis*-pinonic acid solution. Further description of the model approaches is given in sections 5.1.3 and 5.1.4. Note the change of scale on the x-axis compared to fig. 5.8.

Figure 5.11: Modeled and experimental critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{model})$ and $SS_c(\text{exp})$ for dry particles comprising 80.18% by mass of *cis*-pinonic acid. Model "Kuopio model, limited solubility" takes *cis*-pinonic acid partitioning into account in both Kelvin and Raoult terms and applies parameterization 5.7 for the limited *cis*-pinonic acid solubility, while model "Kuopio model, full solubility" takes *cis*-pinonic acid partitioning fully into account, but assumes full solubility of *cis*-pinonic acid in droplet solutions. Calculations "no partitioning, limited solubility" considers the *cis*-pinonic acid solubility through parameterization 5.7, disregarding partitioning and the approach "minimum" gives a lower estimate of the activation by employing full *cis*-pinonic acid solubility and a constant surface tension equal to that of a saturated *cis*-pinonic acid solution. Further description of the model approaches is given in sections 5.1.3 and 5.1.4. Note the change of scale on both axes compared to fig. 5.8, the y-axis has been compressed to include model results.

Figure 5.12: Modeled and experimental critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{model})$ and $SS_c(\text{exp})$ for dry particles comprising 92.50% by mass of *cis*-pinonic acid. Model "Kuopio model, limited solubility" takes *cis*-pinonic acid partitioning into account in both Kelvin and Raoult terms and applies parameterization 5.7 for the limited *cis*-pinonic acid solubility, while model "Kuopio model, full solubility" takes *cis*-pinonic acid partitioning fully into account, but assumes full solubility of *cis*-pinonic acid in droplet solutions. Calculations "no partitioning, limited solubility" considers the *cis*-pinonic acid solubility through parameterization 5.7, disregarding partitioning and the approach "minimum" gives a lower estimate of the activation by employing full *cis*-pinonic acid solubility and a constant surface tension equal to that of a saturated *cis*-pinonic acid solution. Further description of the model approaches is given in sections 5.1.3 and 5.1.4. Note the change of scale on both axes compared to fig. 5.8, the y-axis has been compressed to include model results.

The calculation approaches "Kuopio model, limited solubility" and "no partitioning, limited solubility" equally consider the limited solubility of *cis*-pinonic acid by applying parameterization 5.7, but where the Kuopio model takes *cis*-pinonic acid partitioning into account upon evaluation of both Kelvin and Raoult terms, the calculations "no partitioning, limited solubility" disregards partitioning and thus determines both Kelvin and Raoult effects by assuming all *cis*-pinonic acid solute is in the bulk of the activating droplets. Comparing the results of the two calculation approaches consequently yields the overall effect of accounting for partitioning in describing the activation of the investigated mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particles; it is seen that

the effect is not very large for any of the particle compositions in question, but nevertheless notable for the particles comprising the largest mass fraction of *cis*-pinonic acid. This is interpreted as an expression of the low solubility of *cis*-pinonic acid, which limits the total concentration of dissolved surfactant and thus the absolute significance of accounting for surfactant partitioning in the calculations. Since the *cis*-pinonic acid solubility given by parameterization 5.7 may be unrealistically low, as mentioned in section 5.1.3, the effect of accounting for partitioning on the predicted activation of the mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particles may be greater than depicted in fig.s 5.9, 5.10, 5.11 and 5.12. New *cis*-pinonic acid solubility measurements will therefore be performed by the Aerosol Group at the University of Copenhagen to obtain a more appropriate solubility parameterization for application in the Kuopio model and other calculations involving mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particles.

The activation behavior predicted by the "Kuopio model, limited solubility" and "no partitioning, limited solubility" calculations agree reasonably well with experimentally determined critical supersaturations for the mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particles containing approximately 20% and 50% by mass of *cis*-pinonic acid. In case of the particles comprising 50% of *cis*-pinonic acid by mass, the agreement with experiment seems to be somewhat better for the calculations disregarding *cis*-pinonic acid partitioning, than for the Kuopio model. This is however believed to reflect the underestimation by both calculation approaches of the *cis*-pinonic acid solubility actually applying to activating droplets at ambient temperatures, rather than showing how accounting for *cis*-pinonic acid partitioning yields a poorer description of the observed activation behavior for the mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particles concerned. Underestimating the *cis*-pinonic acid solubility will entail an underestimation of the Raoult effect, as well as the surface tension lowering and resulting Kelvin effect suppression, attained from the amount of *cis*-pinonic acid dissolved upon droplet formation, which will subsequently produce an overestimation of the critical supersaturations observed in experiments. No conclusions pertaining to the significance for cloud droplet activation properties of *cis*-pinonic acid partitioning in the mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate solution droplets in question will therefore be based on the present results.

Contrary to the observations for particles comprising smaller amounts of *cis*-pinonic acid, the agreement of the critical supersaturations calculated from both the "Kuopio model, limited solubility" and "no partitioning, limited solubility" approaches with the experimental results is very poor for dry particles with approximate *cis*-pinonic acid mass percentages of 80% and 95%, in that the calculations largely overestimate the observed activation behavior. This lead to the speculation that the particles investigated in the experiments were insufficiently dried and therefore constituting supersaturated solution droplets, rather than solid dry particles, even before entering the CCNC. In such supersaturated droplet solutions, all solute, and in particular the slightly soluble *cis*-pinonic acid, resides entirely in the solution phase and the droplets will therefore attain a Raoult effect and activation properties corresponding to the solute components being completely water-soluble. The Kuopio model calculations have therefore

been performed for each of the mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particle compositions assuming full solubility of *cis*-pinonic acid in all droplet solutions and accordingly termed "Kuopio model, full solubility".

In addition, the individual Köhler curves have been calculated for 25 and 80 nm particles of each *cis*-pinonic acid mass fraction using the approach "limited solubility, no partitioning" (which was readily available and easy to modify for the purpose), in order to examine the relation between the critical supersaturations predicted assuming either limited or full solubility of *cis*-pinonic acid. In the mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate solution droplets, the slightly soluble compound gradually dissolves in the growing droplets due to the progressively increasing droplet water volume. The gradual dissolution of *cis*-pinonic acid produces two local maxima of the corresponding Köhler curves, separated by a cusp at the so-called transition diameter where *cis*-pinonic acid is eventually completely dissolved [14], [95]. For droplet sizes exceeding the transition diameter, all *cis*-pinonic acid resides in the droplet solution phase and the Köhler curve shape is analogous to that resulting from assuming full solubility of *cis*-pinonic acid. The relative position of the supersaturation values corresponding to the two local Köhler curve maxima thus determine the difference in activation predicted by the approaches assuming limited and full *cis*-pinonic acid solubility, respectively. When the first maxima constitutes the overall Köhler curve maximum, activation occurs before *cis*-pinonic acid is completely dissolved and there will be a discrepancy between the respective critical supersaturations calculated assuming limited and full solubility. However, if the second local Köhler curve maximum yields the critical supersaturation, *cis*-pinonic acid is fully dissolved upon droplet activation and the critical supersaturations calculated accounting for limited *cis*-pinonic acid solubility coincides with the results of the full solubility approach. The calculated Köhler curves are displayed in fig.s 5.13, 5.14, 5.15 and 5.16.

The critical supersaturations calculated from the approach "Kuopio model, full solubility" coincide with those of "Kuopio model, limited solubility" and thus agree equally well with the experimentally determined activation for the mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particles containing approximately 20% and 50% by mass of *cis*-pinonic acid. The corresponding Köhler curves in fig.s 5.13 and 5.14 show, that activation is given by the second curve maximum except for the 25 nm particles comprising 50% *cis*-pinonic acid, so the identical results of the limited and full solubility approaches are to be expected. The fact that no discrepancy is observed in predicted activation even for the 25 nm 50% *cis*-pinonic acid particles must rely on difference between the Kuopio model and the calculation approach used for producing the Köhler curves.

Figure 5.13: Köhler curves for 25 and 80 nm particles comprising 20.90% of *cis*-pinonic acid by mass, calculated with the approach "no partitioning, limited solubility", considering the limited *cis*-pinonic acid solubility in terms of parameterization 5.7 and disregarding effects of *cis*-pinonic acid partitioning. For the 80 nm particles, the second curve maximum is barely visible, whence the extended supersaturation range has been depicted. Activation occurs at the second Köhler curve maximum for both dry particle sizes and is therefore the same as for supersaturated solution droplets comprising identical amounts of solute. Note that the supersaturation is given in [%].

Figure 5.14: Köhler curves for 25 and 80 nm particles comprising 49.40% of *cis*-pinonic acid by mass, calculated with the approach "no partitioning, limited solubility", considering the limited *cis*-pinonic acid solubility in terms of parameterization 5.7 and disregarding effects of *cis*-pinonic acid partitioning. For the 25 nm particles, activation occurs at the first Köhler curve maximum and is therefore dominated by the limited solubility of *cis*-pinonic acid, whereas for the 80 nm particles, activation occurs at the second maximum and is the same as for supersaturated solution droplets comprising identical amounts of solute. Note that the supersaturation is given in [%].

Figure 5.15: Köhler curves for 25 and 80 nm particles comprising 80.18% of *cis*-pinonic acid by mass, calculated with the approach "no partitioning, limited solubility", considering the limited *cis*-pinonic acid solubility in terms of parameterization 5.7 and disregarding effects of *cis*-pinonic acid partitioning. Activation occurs at the first Köhler curve maximum for both dry particle sizes and is therefore dominated by the limited solubility of *cis*-pinonic acid. Note that the supersaturation is given in [%].

Figure 5.16: Köhler curves for 25 and 80 nm particles comprising 92.50% of *cis*-pinonic acid by mass, calculated with the approach "no partitioning, limited solubility", considering the limited *cis*-pinonic acid solubility in terms of parameterization 5.7 and disregarding effects of *cis*-pinonic acid partitioning. Activation occurs at the first Köhler curve maximum for both dry particle sizes and is therefore dominated by the limited solubility of *cis*-pinonic acid. Note that the supersaturation is given in [%].

Large differences result in the critical supersaturations calculated for the mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particles comprising 80% and 95% by mass of *cis*-pinonic acid, assuming limited ("Kuopio model, limited solubility") and full ("Kuopio model, full solubility") solubility of *cis*-pinonic acid, respectively. This is emphasized by the Köhler curves in fig.s 5.15 and 5.16, showing that activation for these particles is determined by the first curve maximum, where the limited solubility of *cis*-pinonic acid

is decisive. Nevertheless, presuming the particles investigated to be supersaturated solution droplets, by imposing the assumption of complete *cis*-pinonic acid dissolution in the activating droplets, is insufficient to describe the experimentally observed activation of the mixed particles with 80% and 95% *cis*-pinonic acid, which is still considerably overestimated.

Pursuing the notion of supersaturated solution droplets, activation of the mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particles has been calculated assuming full *cis*-pinonic acid solubility and a constant droplet solution surface tension corresponding to that of a saturated *cis*-pinonic acid solution at room temperature. Such conditions should yield the maximum Raoult effect and suppression of the Kelvin effect conceivable for the particles in question and consequently the lowest possible estimate of the corresponding critical supersaturations, whence the calculations are termed "minimum". Comparing the results of this approach to experiments show, that the activation of mixed particles with 80% and 95% *cis*-pinonic acid is still overestimated, however. It is therefore not possible to explain the discrepancy between experimental and modeled critical supersaturations for the mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particles containing 80% and 95% of *cis*-pinonic acid by mass solely in terms of the investigated particles being present in the experiments as supersaturated solution droplets. Furthermore, as the calculation approach "minimum" is believed to produce unrealistically low predictions within the given theoretical framework of the critical supersaturations for the *cis*-pinonic acid containing particles studied, the gap between experiments and modeled activation is likely larger than presented by the results of the "minimum" approach. Consequently, some significant mechanism must apply to the experiments performed, which is not properly accounted for, either upon interpreting the experimental results or in the theoretical description adopted for the model calculations.

These results and observations have been discussed with both Ari Laaksonen and Birgitta Svenningsson and two possible explanations for the nature of such a mechanism have been obtained, which will be described in the following.

In the atomizer, a beam of atomizer solution is produced, which subsequently undergoes spontaneous breakup due to the Rayleigh-Plateau instability [64, pp.100], [8, pp.10], hereby forming individual droplets. During the breakup process, *cis*-pinonic acid surface adsorption is enhanced in regions of the atomizer solution beam with smaller local radius of curvature, which may subsequently cause a preferential accumulation of *cis*-pinonic acid in the combined surface and bulk phase of such regions in the solution beam. Droplets emerging upon atomization from the regions of the atomizer solution beam with smaller curvature radius may thus contain relatively more *cis*-pinonic acid solute compared to droplets originating from regions of the atomizer solution beam with larger radius of curvature. Solution droplets formed from regions of the atomizer beam with smaller curvature radii are innately smaller themselves and will generally produce smaller dry particles. As a consequence of the described mechanism, the dry particles generated from the mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate atomizer solution will therefore be unevenly composed as function of size, in that the smaller

particles will comprise larger relative amounts of *cis*-pinonic acid and the larger particles will be accordingly depleted in *cis*-pinonic acid, compared to the composition of the atomizer solution prepared for particle generation. This entails, that the particles selected for activation measurements may contain larger fractions of ammonium sulfate than expected and thus activate for lower critical supersaturations than predicted from calculations using the relative *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate dry particle mass fractions given by the atomizer solution composition through equation 3.5. The effect is anticipated to become increasingly important for particles with larger *cis*-pinonic acid content, since partitioning of *cis*-pinonic acid in the atomizer solution beam and the resulting dry particle composition differentiation will be more pronounced, just as the relative role of *cis*-pinonic acid in determining cloud droplet activation properties will be accordingly greater. It would be interesting to investigate this effect further by applying a different atomizer type or varying the atomizer solution concentration.

A similar effect on particle composition may arise from a mechanism occurring upon drying of the wet aerosol droplets generated by atomization: When the droplets are dried, the dissolved solute crystallize and the corresponding Raoult effect consequently vanishes; the greatly enhanced Kelvin effect thus attained by the droplets causes water to evaporate, leaving the crystallized solute as a solid dry particle. Nevertheless, owing to the large increase in Kelvin effect upon crystallization of the solute, droplets initially remain as metastable supersaturated solutions when dried to relative humidities below the deliquescence point. Since the deliquescence relative humidity of *cis*-pinonic acid due to its low water solubility is at saturation or supersaturation conditions, $DRH_{CPA} \geq 100\%$, the *cis*-pinonic acid containing droplets very soon become supersaturated upon entering the diffusion driers during experiments. As the vapor pressure of *cis*-pinonic acid is expected to be much greater for the supersaturated solution droplets compared to the solid dry particles [15], [85], significant amounts of *cis*-pinonic acid may evaporate from the droplets during drying, before crystallization occurs. Again, this would entail the solid dry particles generated to comprise relatively less *cis*-pinonic acid compared to solute composition of the atomizer solution, and thus to activate for smaller critical supersaturations than predicted by calculations employing a particle composition derived from equation 3.5. Likewise, the effect of this mechanism is anticipated to be more pronounced for particles with larger expected *cis*-pinonic acid mass fractions, due to increased evaporation of *cis*-pinonic acid from the supersaturated solution droplets in the driers and the expected larger relative influence of *cis*-pinonic acid properties on calculated activation behavior.

Both mechanisms mentioned above affect the composition of the mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particles generated towards a larger relative ammonium sulfate content; since the change occurs before the dry particles are selected by size in the DMA, activation is not halted by a decreased amount of solute, as suspected due to evaporation in the flow system for the acid containing particles in chapter 4, but rather facilitated by the increased amount of ammonium sulfate in particles of a given selected size. Furthermore will neither mechanism affect the activation of pure *cis*-pinonic acid particles, which is consistent with the relative activation behavior observed

for the different particle compositions in fig. 5.8: Pure *cis*-pinonic acid particles activate for considerably larger critical supersaturations than any of the mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particles, which all show activation behavior similar to that of pure ammonium sulfate particles. This effect cannot be explained by insufficient drying of the particles, which must be expected to pertain to the pure as well as the mixed *cis*-pinonic acid containing particles. Regardless of the nature of the underlying mechanism, the resulting effect must therefore be large. It should be possible to make a quantitative estimate of the effect from either re-dissolving the generated particles and performing appropriate spectroscopic measurements on the resulting solution, or from measuring the vapor pressure of *cis*-pinonic acid in the supersaturated solution droplets and subsequently calculate the extent of evaporation from an estimate of the residence time in the diffusion driers, using the model of Bilde et al. [15].

Hartz et al. [41] find, that pure *cis*-pinonic acid particles activate almost as if completely water soluble and explain this observation with particles never being completely dry in the experimental system; the anticipated model results for pure *cis*-pinonic acid particles will show, if similar enhanced activation properties are displayed in the present experiments. Since the possibility of supersaturated solution droplets cannot be dismissed as part of the explanation for the discrepancy between observed and calculated activation behavior for the mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particles, this will be investigated further in future experiments. Measuring hygroscopic growth factors for the generated particles in the HTDMA will determine if they are indeed solid dry particles or supersaturated solution droplets, as the supersaturated solution droplets will not display the deliquescence expected for initially dry particles. Alternatively, re-performing the activation measurements at a controlled relative humidity with particles known to be incompletely dried will reveal if the same activation behavior is observed as in the present experiments and thus if the activating particles share similar properties in terms of the particle phase.

A value for the *cis*-pinonic acid dissociation constant has not been found, so no conclusions as to the possibility of acid dissociation enhancing droplet activation by increasing the Raoult effect can be made. Such an effect is however not expected to be large. On the other hand, experimental conditions regarding the CCNC may affect the observed activation of *cis*-pinonic acid containing particles; the surfactant nature of *cis*-pinonic acid causes "soap bubbles" to be generated inside the measurement chamber and a possible influence on the supersaturation profile in the chamber or the activation measurement results in general from these bubbles cannot be discounted. Lastly should be mentioned, that the effects of non-spherical particles and particle evaporation in the flow system before the activation measurements have not been considered here, as these conditions would suppress cloud droplet activation of the particles investigated and thus produce discrepancies between experiments and predicted activation in the sense opposite to what is observed in this study.

The results for mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particles presented in this section show, that the experimentally determined critical supersaturations do not

confirm the activation predicted by the Kuopio model or either of the other calculation approaches applied. Therefore, it is not possible to establish the significance of the *cis*-pinonic acid surfactant properties for cloud droplet activation of the investigated particles. Evidently, one or more mechanisms bring about additional experimental conditions, which are not properly accounted for in the subsequent analysis of the results. The nature and effects of such mechanism will be investigated in future experiments, including those mentioned in the discussion above.

5.3 Conclusions and Perspectives

The cloud droplet activation properties of particles containing the surfactants sodium dodecyl sulfate and *cis*-pinonic acid mixed in different ratios with sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate, respectively, have been investigated in laboratory experiments and modeled accounting for the surfactant and other properties of sodium dodecyl sulfate and *cis*-pinonic acid in various ways.

The results for mixed sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride particles show, that the activation of these particles is well described in terms of the account provided for the sodium dodecyl sulfate properties by the Kuopio model. It is evident, that if the surfactant nature of sodium dodecyl sulfate is considered for evaluating droplet solution surface tension upon prediction of cloud droplet activation of the sodium dodecyl sulfate containing particles, sodium dodecyl sulfate partitioning must necessarily be taken into account, and that the best agreement with observed activation behavior is obtained when partitioning is included in evaluation of both Kelvin and Raoult terms. Thus, partitioning of sodium dodecyl sulfate in the activating droplet solutions clearly constitutes an important property for cloud droplet activation of the mixed sodium dodecyl sulfate and sodium chloride particles investigated.

On the other hand, the experimentally determined activation of the investigated mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particles cannot be captured by the theoretical description applied in of any the calculations performed for this study. Besides the possibility of the particles generated for experiments being metastable supersaturated solution droplets instead of solid dry particles, the results strongly suggest, that the experiments are governed by some mechanism, which is not properly quantified in the interpretation or modeling of the observed activation, and which obscures the subsequent analysis. Due to this circumstance, it has not been possible to establish the significance of *cis*-pinonic acid surfactant properties, and in particular of *cis*-pinonic acid partitioning, for cloud droplet activation of the mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particles concerned.

A number of experiments are being contemplated to improve our understanding and control of the experimental conditions concerning activation measurements for *cis*-pinonic acid containing particles, as well as the quality of the theoretical parameterizations of *cis*-pinonic acid properties; this is necessary for obtaining experimental results and subsequent analyses that enable discerning the effects of *cis*-pinonic acid surfactant proper-

ties and partitioning on cloud droplet activation of particles containing *cis*-pinonic acid. In addition, activation properties of *cis*-pinonic acid will be investigated for particles containing additional compounds other than ammonium sulfate. An immediate extension of the present work is to measure the activation of particles comprising *cis*-pinonic acid and sodium chloride in various mixing ratios.

As *cis*-pinonic acid is an atmospherically relevant organic compound, quantifying its surfactant and other properties, like those concerning solubility and acid dissociation, is believed to be important for understanding the processes of cloud formation in the atmosphere. Of the two mechanisms suggested as explanation for the unexpected activation properties of the mixed *cis*-pinonic acid and ammonium sulfate particles studied, the one concerning *cis*-pinonic acid partitioning during the atomization process pertains strictly to laboratory experiments. However, evaporation of *cis*-pinonic acid from supersaturated solution droplets would potentially be important in respect to cloud processing of atmospheric aerosol particles, just as the activation properties of supersaturated *cis*-pinonic acid containing solution droplets may be equally relevant in the atmosphere as those of the corresponding solid dry particles.

Facchini et al. [27] find that many organic surfactants extracted from atmospheric samples belonged to the compound class HULIS, and the influence of surfactant properties on activation behavior for particles containing HULIS has been explored by both Dinar et al. [23] and Svenningsson et al. [100]. Kiss et al. [58] detect a 25-42% surface tension lowering compared to pure water for aqueous solutions of HULIS isolated from atmospheric aerosol samples with concentrations 1 g/L, but note that even if the magnitude of the Kelvin effect is decreased accordingly, effects of surfactant partitioning and the magnitude of the corresponding Raoult effect must be considered before making conclusions about the resulting activation properties of the sampled aerosol particles. Model calculations by Kokkola et al. [60] for particles containing different relative amounts of HULIS and ammonium sulfate show, that "the surface partitioning of HULIS has a significant effect on cloud droplet activation" and the predicted number of CCN, as "the surface tension reduction and the Raoult effect are strongly suppressed due to partitioning, which leads to higher critical supersaturations and decreased cloud droplet activation".

The properties of HULIS in atmospheric aerosol particles and of atmospheric samples in general are complex and not well-quantified on a single compound basis. Unfortunately, application of the Kuopio model requires specific parameterizations of properties for all individual system components in order to evaluate the effects of surfactant partitioning for cloud droplet activation. To develop an understanding of the overall significance of organic aerosol component surfactant properties and partitioning for cloud formation in the atmosphere, other more simple atmospherically relevant organic surfactants in addition to *cis*-pinonic acid will therefore need to be investigated first; of these, azelaic acid is a likely candidate, which has also displayed unexpected activation properties in laboratory experiments [18]. It will be very interesting to see, if improved compound property characterization and control of the experimental conditions will enable an ad-

equate description of activation behavior for particles containing *cis*-pinonic acid and other atmospherically relevant organic surfactants.

Chapter 6

Summary and Outlook

In this work, the cloud condensation nuclei properties of organic aerosol constituents have been investigated in terms of the effects of acid dissociation and surfactant partitioning on cloud droplet activation. This was accomplished by laboratory experiments involving CCNC measurements and theoretical predictions using model and other calculations based on Köhler theory of the activation properties for aerosol particles containing citric and malic acid, sodium dodecyl sulfate and *cis*-pinonic acid. Citric, malic and *cis*-pinonic acid are atmospherically relevant compounds, whereas sodium dodecyl sulfate has been invoked to test model predictions for a system with well-known properties.

Generally, results of the theoretical calculations agreed well with the experimentally observed activation for the citric and malic acid and sodium dodecyl sulfate containing particles investigated, implying that the different parameterizations applied were overall successful in describing the chemical properties concerned in the activating droplet solutions. On the other hand, the activation determined in experiments for the particles containing *cis*-pinonic acid could not be explained by any of the theoretical approaches applied, which is however most likely due to inexpedient conditions concerning the particle generation procedure that were not accounted for upon interpretation of the experimental results. Comparison of the experimental and theoretical results showed, that both the degree of acid dissociation in the droplet solutions and the effect of surfactant partitioning on the resulting droplet surface tension were important properties to consider in evaluating cloud droplet activation of the particles in question.

For the citric and malic acid particles investigated, it was found that both acids were indeed dissociated to some degree in the activating droplet solutions and that the degree of dissociation at the point of activation varied due to varying dilution state for droplets originating from dry particles of different sizes with a given composition. A parameterization of the droplet solution water activity in terms of a single constant van't Hoff factor was therefore inadequate to fully describe the droplet growth and activation properties for the collection of particle sizes investigated for each composition. Employing different empirically based water activity parameterizations further showed, that the choice of water activity parameterization was important for the value and especially the validity of the subsequently evaluated critical supersaturation; due to the

dilute droplet solution state at activation, water activity parameterizations based on techniques that allow measurements at very low concentrations, like osmolality or bulk water activity measurements, seem very promising for future application to predicting properties of activating droplets.

The results for sodium dodecyl sulfate containing particles showed, that accounting for surfactant partitioning upon evaluation of the droplet solution surface tension was essential to a proper description of cloud droplet activation properties for the particles concerned; furthermore, the best agreement with experimental observations was obtained when sodium dodecyl sulfate partitioning was considered in determining both Kelvin and Raoult effects on activation. Unfortunately, these findings could not be conveyed to the investigated particles containing *cis*-pinonic acid; as *cis*-pinonic acid is a compound of great atmospheric relevance, it is however important to understand the cloud condensation nuclei properties of *cis*-pinonic acid containing aerosol particles. Thus, a number of future investigations are contemplated to improve the control and interpretation of experimental conditions governing production and activation measurements of *cis*-pinonic acid containing particles in the laboratory and the parameterizations of specific chemical properties for *cis*-pinonic acid in aqueous solutions, in order to resolve the importance of *cis*-pinonic acid surfactant properties and partitioning for cloud droplet activation.

Both acid dissociation and surfactant partitioning is highly relevant in connection to humic like substances (HULIS), which comprise a significant fraction of atmospheric organic aerosol components and generally display both acidic and surfactant properties. Here, the water activity parameterisations employing either osmolality or bulk water activity measurements can readily be applied in predicting cloud condensation nuclei properties of collected atmospheric samples arising from the dissociation of carboxylic acid groups. For evaluation of the effects of surfactant partitioning, the Kuopio model however requires a specific knowledge of the nature and properties of all individual components, that will often not be obtainable for such atmospheric samples. This again poses great challenges on future development of the understanding of cloud condensation nuclei properties for organic atmospheric aerosol particles.

In a recently published paper, Dusek et al. [24] conclude from comparison of model calculations and size-resolved cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) spectra measured for different continental air masses that "CCN concentrations are mainly determined by the aerosol number size distribution" and "distinct variations of CCN activation with particle chemical composition were observed but played a secondary role". This is actually not surprising, considering that in laboratory experiments of cloud droplet activation, including those of the present study, a greater variation of critical supersaturation is usually found with particle diameter over the size ranges studied for a given composition, than with variation in chemical composition. Nevertheless, the recognition for atmospheric aerosols has important implications for modeling CCN concentrations in the atmosphere and thus for estimating the magnitude of the aerosol indirect climate effects, as atmospheric aerosol size distributions are more easily obtained than the cor-

responding chemical compositions. Furthermore, as was clearly seen in this study, characterization of aerosol component chemical properties and the effects on cloud droplet activation resulting from such combined properties and composite compositions can be very complex.

Whereas estimating atmospheric CCN concentrations from aerosol size distributions is an extremely useful approximation for climate modeling purposes, a full account for observed numbers of CCN is not given in this way [24] and aerosol size distributions therefore cannot replace a detailed understanding of the fundamental chemical processes governing cloud droplet formation. For instance, the results of the present study for sodium dodecyl sulfate containing particles show that it may be of great importance to determine if and how to deal with partitioning of surfactants in activating droplets when evaluating critical supersaturations for atmospheric aerosol particles. An understanding of the chemical properties and processes involved in cloud droplet activation must therefore be sought to obtain a comprehensive description of the cloud condensation nuclei properties of atmospheric organic aerosol components and for establishing the role of the aerosol indirect effect in determining global climate.

Appendix A

Parameterisations

A.1 The Osmolality Parameterization

In Weast and Astle [107, pp.D-272], the measured citric acid aqueous solution osmolalities b_{osm}^{CA} are listed for corresponding sets of citric acid molar concentration c_{CA} [mol/L] and concentration of water C_w [g/L]. The molal concentration of citric acid can then be calculated from

$$b_{CA} = \frac{1000}{C_w} c_{CA} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

The solution osmolality $b_{osm}^{CA} \in [0.028 - 2.285]$ Osm/kg is parameterized as a function of citric acid molal concentration $b_{CA} \in [0.0261 - 2.2312]$ mol/kg by fitting the data to polynomial functions of different order, first without constraints and then applying the restriction $b_{osm}^{CA}(b_{CA} = 0) = 0$. In both cases, good agreement with the data is achieved for several polynomial orders. The polynomials subordinate to the constraint have been chosen as physically most correct; fig. A.1 show that the 3rd, 4th and 5th order polynomials $f3$, $f4$ and $f5$ are difficult to distinguish when plotted over the whole data range, and are very close even for the most dilute solutions.

$$f5 : b_{osm}^{CA} = 0.070571b_{CA}^5 - 0.38425b_{CA}^4 + 0.69344b_{CA}^3 - 0.47257b_{CA}^2 + 1.1474b_{CA}, R = 0.99999 \quad (\text{A.2})$$

$$f4 : b_{osm}^{CA} = -0.0060105b_{CA}^4 - 0.0022520b_{CA}^3 + 0.029392b_{CA}^2 + 1.0352b_{CA}, R = 0.99999 \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$f3 : b_{osm}^{CA} = -0.027095b_{CA}^3 + 0.059873b_{CA}^2 + 1.0249b_{CA}, R = 0.99999 \quad (\text{A.4})$$

Figure A.1: Parameterization of aqueous citric acid solution osmolality b_{osm}^{CA} as function of citric acid molal concentration b_{CA} by fitting data from Weast and Astle [107, pp.D-272] to polynomial functions $f3$, $f4$ and $f5$ of 3rd, 4th and 5th order with the constraint $b_{osm}^{CA}(b_{CA} = 0) = 0$. The left plot shows the fits for the whole data range $b_{CA} \in [0.0261 - 2.2312]$ mol/kg and on the right the fits are plotted with the data for dilute solutions. The polynomials are difficult to distinguish, but a magnification of the right plot show that $f4$ gives the slightly better fit to the data in the dilute concentration end.

Inspection of a magnification of the righthand plot in fig. A.1 reveal that the polynomial $f4$ gives slightly better agreement with the dilute solution data than $f3$ and $f5$. Recalling from section 3.2.2 that the resulting water activity expression for the dilute solutions appear to be of greatest influence to the calculations, $f4$ is thus chosen for the parameterization given in equation 4.9.

A.2 The EDB Water Activity Parameterizations

The collected electrodynamic balance (EDB) and bulk measurements of water activity for citric and malic acid aqueous solutions [78], [77] are reported on the web page <http://ihome.ust.hk/~keckchan/hygroscopic.html> (last accessed 23-08-2006) for the respective ranges $a_w = RH/100\% \in [0.0500 - 0.9961]$ and $a_w = RH/100\% \in [0.0400 - 0.9860]$. The corresponding acid solution mass fractions are $x_{CA}^m \in [0.9167 - 0.0370]$ and $x_{MA}^m \in [0.9424 - 0.1189]$, which can be converted to acid molal concentrations by equation 4.11 to give $b_{CA} \in [57.2544 - 0.2000]$ and $b_{MA} \in [122.0721 - 1.0067]$.

Svenningson et al. [100] have derived a serial approximation of Raoult's law using a constant solute (s) van't Hoff factor i_s , which gives the water activity a_w as function of solute molality b_s by a polynomial with coefficients only depending on the constant values of the van't Hoff factor and the molar mass of water M_w and with alternating coefficient signs

$$a_w(b_s) = 1 - i_s M_w b_s + (i_s M_w)^2 b_s^2 - (i_s M_w)^3 b_s^3 + (i_s M_w)^4 b_s^4 - \dots \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Hereby inspired, the water activity for citric and malic acid aqueous solutions was attempted parameterized as function of the respective solution molal concentrations, first

without restrictions and then applying the constraint $a_w(b=0) = 1$ according to equation A.5. It was not possible to achieve a decent fit of this kind or any other polynomial form with the available fitting tools (Matlab package Ezyfit); various other functional expressions like exponentials also failed.

The water activity a_w was instead parameterized as function of citric and malic acid solution mass fractions x_{CA}^m and x_{MA}^m by fitting the data to polynomial functions of different orders. The constraint $a_w(x^m=0) = 1$ is believed to be physically representative and was applied in all cases. For citric acid, good agreement was obtained by the 8th, 7th and 5th order polynomials $f8$, $f7$ and $f5$ as seen on the left in fig. A.2.

$$f8 : a_w^{CA} = -6.7036x_{CA}^m{}^8 + 10.628x_{CA}^m{}^7 - 6.3673x_{CA}^m{}^6 + 4.7331x_{CA}^m{}^5 - 4.5308x_{CA}^m{}^4 + 1.0156x_{CA}^m{}^3 - 0.0055431x_{CA}^m{}^2 - 0.14145x_{CA}^m + 1, R = 0.99631 \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$f7 : a_w^{CA} = -3.7476x_{CA}^m{}^7 + 4.3851x_{CA}^m{}^6 - 1.6698x_{CA}^m{}^5 + 2.1447x_{CA}^m{}^4 - 3.3968x_{CA}^m{}^3 + 1.2131x_{CA}^m{}^2 - 0.24844x_{CA}^m + 1, R = 0.99618 \quad (\text{A.7})$$

$$f5 : a_w^{CA} = -3.7664x_{CA}^m{}^5 + 5.5603x_{CA}^m{}^4 - 3.4861x_{CA}^m{}^3 + 0.5844x_{CA}^m{}^2 - 0.13172x_{CA}^m + 1, R = 0.99601 \quad (\text{A.8})$$

Figure A.2: Measured water activities for citric acid bulk and droplet solutions from Peng et al. [78] fitted by 8th, 7th and 5th order polynomials $f8$, $f7$ and $f5$ with the constraint $a_w(x^m=0) = 1$. The polynomials are difficult to distinguish when depicted for the whole data range $x_{CA}^m \in [0.9167-0.0370]$ to the left, but show differences in the dilute limit $x_{CA}^m \in [0-0.3]$ plotted to the right. The polynomial $f5$ gives the better agreement with the data for the dilute solutions and is thus chosen for the water activity parameterization in equation 4.12.

For malic acid, the 8th, 7th and 6th order polynomials $f8$, $f7$ and $f6$ shown on the left in fig. A.3 fitted the data well. It was however necessary to omit the 6 data points for the most concentrated droplet solutions to improve the fit sufficiently in

the dilute end. The resulting fits are then based on 33 of the total 39 data points in the set and represent the water activity and malic acid solution mass fraction ranges $a_w = RH/100\% \in [0.2500 - 0.9860]$ and $x_{MA}^m \in [0.8498 - 0.1189]$. Since the dilute solutions are of principal concern to the activation studies in the present work, removing the data pertaining to the most concentrated and highly supersaturated solutions is believed to be justifiable.

$$f8 : a_w^{MA} = 6.2131x_{CA}^m{}^8 - 0.46271x_{CA}^m{}^7 - 8.3046x_{CA}^m{}^6 - 1.7894x_{CA}^m{}^5 + 7.0823x_{CA}^m{}^4 - 3.5412x_{CA}^m{}^3 + 0.26506x_{CA}^m{}^2 - 0.10561x_{CA}^m + 1, R = 0.99838 \quad (\text{A.9})$$

$$f7 : a_w^{MA} = 2.7466x_{CA}^m{}^7 + 0.6855x_{CA}^m{}^6 - 2.8433x_{CA}^m{}^5 - 5.9907x_{CA}^m{}^4 + 7.032x_{CA}^m{}^3 - 2.7349x_{CA}^m{}^2 + 0.17140x_{CA}^m + 1, R = 0.99833 \quad (\text{A.10})$$

$$f6 : a_w^{MA} = 2.9860x_{CA}^m{}^6 - 3.1210x_{CA}^m{}^5 - 1.8546x_{CA}^m{}^4 + 1.2627x_{CA}^m{}^3 - 0.25525x_{CA}^m{}^2 - 0.15411x_{CA}^m + 1, R = 0.99818 \quad (\text{A.11})$$

Figure A.3: Measured water activities for malic acid bulk and droplet solutions from Peng et al. [77] fitted for the restricted range $x_{MA}^m \in [0.8498 - 0.1189]$ by 8th, 7th and 6th order polynomials $f8$, $f7$ and $f6$ with the constraint $a_w(x^m = 0) = 1$. The polynomial graphs are close for the whole data range shown on the left, but for the dilute solutions $x_{MA}^m \in [0 - 0.3]$ seen on the right, $f8$ gives a better agreement with the data than $f7$ and $f6$ and is thus applied for the water activity parameterization in equation 4.13.

To the right in figs. A.2 and A.3 the fitting polynomials are plotted with the data for the dilute solutions (acid solute mass fractions $x^m \in [0 - 0.3]$). As it was seen in section 3.2.2 that the water activity expression for the most dilute solutions appears to be decisive for the outcome of the activation calculations, polynomials $f5$ in fig. A.2 and $f8$ in fig. A.3 which give the best agreement to the data in this limit were chosen for the parameterizations of water activity for citric and malic acid solutions, respectively, as given by equations 4.12 and 4.13.

A.3 The Bulk Water Activity Parameterization

Peng et al. [78] report measured bulk water activities for citric acid solutions from several different studies, covering the range $a_w = RH/100\% \in [0.779154 - 0.996120]$ with corresponding citric acid solution mass fractions $x_{CA}^m \in [0.619909 - 0.037012]$. Analogously to the parameterizations in appendix A.2, the water activity has been parameterized as a function of citric acid solution mass fraction x_{CA}^m by fitting the bulk measurements to polynomial functions of different order, under the constraint $a_w(x_{CA}^m = 0) = 1$. Good agreement with the data was achieved for the 6th, 5th and 4th order polynomials f_6 , f_5 and f_4 , as seen to the left in fig. A.4.

$$f_6 : a_w^{CA} = 1.0926x_{CA}^m{}^6 - 0.029218x_{CA}^m{}^5 - 3.8508x_{CA}^m{}^4 + 2.7819x_{CA}^m{}^3 - 0.91516x_{CA}^m{}^2 - 0.031288x_{CA}^m + 1, R = 0.99907 \quad (\text{A.12})$$

$$f_5 : a_w^{CA} = -1.6955x_{CA}^m{}^5 + 0.52010x_{CA}^m{}^4 + 0.064330x_{CA}^m{}^3 - 0.27781x_{CA}^m{}^2 - 0.078701x_{CA}^m + 1, R = 0.99914 \quad (\text{A.13})$$

$$f_4 : a_w^{CA} = -2.0342x_{CA}^m{}^4 + 1.3993x_{CA}^m{}^3 - 0.55618x_{CA}^m{}^2 - 0.060117x_{CA}^m + 1, R = 0.99911 \quad (\text{A.14})$$

Figure A.4: Measured citric acid bulk solution water activities for the range $x_{CA}^m \in [0.619909 - 0.037012]$ from Peng et al. [78] fitted by 6th, 5th and 4th order polynomials f_6 , f_5 and f_4 with the constraint $a_w(x_{CA}^m = 0) = 1$. The polynomials are almost indistinguishable when viewed over the whole data range, as seen to the left, but for the dilute solutions $x_{CA}^m \in [0 - 0.3]$ to the right, f_5 gives a slightly better agreement with the data and is therefore used for the water activity parameterization 4.14.

To the right in fig. A.4, the polynomials are plotted with the data for dilute solutions $x_{CA}^m \in [0 - 0.3]$; f_5 gives the better agreement with the measured bulk water activities in the dilute solutions and is thus chosen for the water activity parameterization 4.14 by the same argument as applied in appendix A.2.

A.4 The Ammonium Sulfate Solution Water Activity Parameterization

The ammonium sulfate solution water activity parameterization 3.13 obtained in this work by fitting water activity data for different ammonium sulfate molal concentrations b_{AS} reported by Low [71]

$$a_w^{AS} = 1 - 0.039767b_{AS} + 0.0079808b_{AS}^2 - 0.0022641b_{AS}^3, \quad (A.15)$$

$$b_{AS} \in [0 - 5.5] \text{ mol/kg}$$

is compared to the corresponding water activity and ammonium sulfate van't Hoff factor i_{AS} parameterizations developed by Young and Warren [109], Tang and Munkelwitz [102] and Merete Bilde using data from Low [71].

The ammonium sulfate solution water activity parameterization of Tang and Munkelwitz [102]

$$a_{wAS} = 1.0 - 2.715 \cdot 10^{-3} X_{AS}^m + 3.113 \cdot 10^{-5} X_{AS}^{m^2} - 2.336 \cdot 10^{-6} X_{AS}^{m^3} + 1.412 \cdot 10^{-8} X_{AS}^{m^4},$$

$$X_{AS}^m \in [0 - 78] \% \quad (A.16)$$

is given as function of ammonium sulfate mass percent in solution, which can be written in terms of ammonium sulfate solution molality by

$$X_{AS}^m \equiv \frac{m_{AS}}{m_w} \cdot 100\% = M_{AS} b_{AS} \cdot 100\% \quad (A.17)$$

The ammonium sulfate van't Hoff factor parameterizations derived by Young and Warren [109] in the form

$$i_{AS} = 1.9242 - 0.1844 \ln b_{AS} - 0.007931(\ln b_{AS})^2, \quad (A.18)$$

$$b_{AS} \leq 1.0 \text{ mol/kg}$$

and fitted to the data from Low [71] by Merete Bilde

$$i_{AS} = -0.002b_{AS}^5 + 0.032b_{AS}^4 - 0.197b_{AS}^3 + 0.5997b_{AS}^2 - 0.8431b_{AS} + 2.3552, \quad (A.19)$$

$$b_{AS} \in [0 - 5.5] \text{ mol/kg}$$

are substituted into the water activity expression defined by McDonald [72], which is then reformulated as function of ammonium sulfate solution molality b_{AS}

$$a_{wAS} \equiv \frac{n_w}{n_w + i_{AS}n_{AS}} = \frac{M_w^{-1}}{M_w^{-1} + i_{AS}b_{AS}} = \frac{55.5084 \text{ mol/kg}}{55.5084 \text{ mol/kg} + i_{AS}b_{AS}} \quad (A.20)$$

The resulting ammonium sulfate solution water activity from the four expressions A.16, A.18, A.19 and A.15 are plotted as function of ammonium sulfate solution molality b_{AS} in fig. A.5, for the concentration ranges $b_{AS} \in [0 - 1.0] \text{ mol/kg}$ (right) and $b_{AS} \in [0 - 0.1] \text{ mol/kg}$ (left). A close mutual agreement of the predicted water activities is seen, likely due to the dilute solution states involved. The greatest deviation is displayed by the parameterization A.16 of Tang and Munkelwitz [102], which is based on solutions considerable more concentrated than the remaining three parameterizations.

Figure A.5: Ammonium sulfate solution water activity $a_{w_{AS}}$ calculated with the parameterizations A.16, A.18, A.19 and A.15 for the ammonium sulfate solution molal concentration ranges $b_{AS} \in [0 - 1.0]$ mol/kg (right) and $b_{AS} \in [0 - 0.1]$ mol/kg (left). The mutual agreement is rather close, despite the different parameterization approaches used.

Appendix B

Sensitivity Tests

B.1 Effect of Different Doubly Charged Particle Corrections

The sensitivity of the fitted activation curves described in section 3.2.1 to the correction for doubly charged particles has been tested in two ways, for the value of parameter y_0 and for the choice of approach to the correction.

B.1.1 Sensitivity to the Value of y_0

Two examples of activation measurements showing distinct levels of doubly charged particle activation f_{act}^D have been fitted to the 4-parameter sigmoidal function 3.6 with different fixed values of y_0 , and with y_0 as a free fitting parameter (see fig B.1).

Figure B.1: Activation curves for two different measurements (raw data) with clear levels of doubly charged particle activation f_{act}^D , fitted by the 4-parameter sigmoidal function 3.6 with different fixed values of y_0 and with y_0 as a free fitting parameter. The matching values of x_0 obtained are listed in table B.1.

The values of the activation curve midpoint positions x_0 , corresponding to the single charged particle critical supersaturations SS_c , obtained from the different fits are shown for both measurements in table B.1. In addition, the standard deviations σ_{x_0} deriving from the fitting have been listed. No physical significance should be attributed to the number of digits depicting the values of x_0 and the corresponding standard deviations σ_{x_0} , which are included only for comparison of the performance of the fits. It is seen that the value of x_0 is not very sensitive to the choice of y_0 in either case; the maximum difference between x_0 values for a given measurement amounts to about 2% of the smallest value obtained for that measurement.

measurement	45 nm	malic acid	48 nm	malic acid
constraint	x_0	σ_{x_0}	x_0	σ_{x_0}
y_0 free	1.2463	0.0068	1.2231	0.0073
$y_0 = 0.01$	1.2383	0.0070	1.2144	0.0081
$y_0 = 0.10$	1.2476	0.0063	1.2272	0.0072
$y_0 = 0.19$	1.2561	0.0068	1.2393	0.0083

Table B.1: Activation curve midpoint positions x_0 with corresponding standard deviations σ_{x_0} , determined from fits by function 3.6 employing different constraints in terms of fitting parameter y_0 .

B.1.2 Sensitivity to the Correction Approach

The same activation measurements used above have each been fitted using two different approaches to correcting for the activation of doubly charged particles: The first is the one used in this work, as described in section 3.2.1, where the level of doubly charged particles f_{act}^D is determined by inspection of the measured activation ratios f_{act} and then employed as the fixed value of fitting parameter y_0 in the 4-parameter sigmoidal fitting function 3.6. Another correction method has however been proposed by Frank et al. [32], where the level of doubly charged particles f_{act}^D is equivalently determined by inspection of the measured activation ratios f_{act} , which are then corrected accordingly as

$$f_{act}^{corr} = \frac{N(CCN) - N(CN)f_{act}^D}{N(CN) - N(CN)f_{act}^D} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

$N(CCN)$ and $N(CN)$ are the number of activated and total number of particles measured, respectively, as defined in sections 3.1.1 and 3.1.1. In case the correction returns a negative value, the f_{act}^{corr} concerned is assigned the value 0. The corrected activation ratios f_{act}^{corr} are subsequently fitted as function of the supersaturation SS by 3.6 with no further constraints.

Fits have been made using the same determined level of doubly charged particles f_{act}^D in each measurement for fixing y_0 and for obtaining f_{act}^{corr} . The two different fits for one of the measurements are shown in fig.s B.2 and B.3.

Figure B.2: Activation curve obtained by fitting the measured activation ratios f_{act} (raw data) to the 4-parameter sigmoidal function 3.6 with y_0 fixed at the level of doubly charged particles f_{act}^D . The value of the curve midpoint position x_0 is listed in table B.2.

Figure B.3: Activation curve obtained by fitting the activation ratios f_{act}^{corr} , the raw data corrected by the level of doubly charged particles f_{act}^D , with the 4-parameter sigmoidal function 3.6. The value of the curve midpoint position x_0 is listed in table B.2.

The activation curve midpoint positions x_0 and standard deviations σ_{x_0} from fitting obtained by the two approaches, corresponding to the single charged particle critical supersaturations SS_c , are shown in table B.2; again, the number of digits depicted is only for the sake of comparison. The difference between the values of x_0 from the two approaches is insignificant in both cases investigated.

measurement	x_0 , fixed y_0	σ_{x_0}	x_0 , subtract f_{act}^D	σ_{x_0}
45 nm malic acid	1.2524	0.0064	1.2529	0.0059
48 nm malic acid	1.2340	0.0077	1.2339	0.0067

Table B.2: Activation curve midpoint positions x_0 and corresponding standard deviations σ_{x_0} obtained from fitting function 3.6 with two approaches to correcting for doubly charged particles.

B.2 Sensitivity of Activation Calculations Used in the CCNC Calibration

The sensitivity of the critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{calc})$ calculated in section 3.2.2 to the functional forms of the solution water activity a_w and surface tension σ parameterizations, as well as to the values for parameters affected by experimental conditions, the temperature T , dry particle size D_p and water density $\rho_w(T)$, have been tested using 35 nm sodium chloride and 40 nm ammonium sulfate particles as examples. These particle sizes have been selected, because the particles activate for supersaturations

SS_c high enough that possible sensitivity effects are believed to be discernible, and because they activate well within the supersaturation range $SS \in [0.1-2.5]$ % available for measurement in the CCNC, thus being representative of the calibration data set.

B.2.1 Water Activity Parameterizations

The respective sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate solution water activity a_w parameterizations in solution molality were attained by fitting water activity data from Low [71] for a number of concentrations b_{SC} and b_{AS} , covering the full sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate water solubility ranges given in 3.10 and 3.11, to a 3rd order polynomial with the constraint $y(x = 0) = 1$. This was the highest order polynomial that enabled a good fit to the data with the available fitting tools (Matlab package Ezyfit and SigmaPlot). The constraint was employed, since, as will be seen, the calculated critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{calc})$ are most sensitive to the water activity values for dilute solutions and the condition $a_w(b = 0) = 1$ should therefore hold.

For sodium chloride solutions, it was possible to attain a fit that agrees well with the water activity data for the whole sodium chloride water solubility range $b_{SC} \in [0-6.153]$ mol/kg and with the data for the most dilute solutions in particular (see fig. B.4).

$$a_w^{SC} = 1 - 0.031715b_{SC} - 0.0012582b_{SC}^2 - 2.2921 \cdot 10^{-5}b_{SC}^3, \quad b_{SC}/[\text{mol/kg}] \in [0.01 - 6.0] \quad (\text{B.2})$$

This is the parameterization given in equation 3.12.

Figure B.4: Parameterization curve for solution water activity a_w^{SC} as function of sodium chloride concentration b_{SC} , made by fitting water activity data from Low [71] to a 3rd order polynomial with the constraint $y(x = 0) = 1$. The agreement of the parameterization curve with the data is shown for dilute solutions to the left and for the full sodium chloride water solubility range $b_{SC} \in [0-6.153]$ mol/kg to the right.

For ammonium sulfate solutions, however, it was not possible to attain a fit that agreed well with the water activity data for both the most dilute and the most concentrated

solutions over the ammonium sulfate water solubility range $b_{AS} \in [0-5.790]$ mol/kg. Better agreement with the most dilute solution water activity data could only be achieved at the expense of the most concentrated solution water activity data (see fig. B.5).

Figure B.5: Parameterization curves for solution water activity a_w^{AS} as function of ammonium sulfate concentration b_{AS} . The parameterizations are made by fitting different subsets of the water activity data from Low [71] to a 3rd order polynomial with the constraint $y(x = 0) = 1$. The agreement of the parameterization curves with the data is shown for dilute solutions to the left and for the full ammonium sulfate water solubility range $b_{AS} \in [0-5.790]$ mol/kg to the right.

The sensitivity of the calculated critical supersaturation $SS_c(\text{calc})$ for 40 nm ammonium sulfate particles to the choice of water activity parameterization have been tested for five parameterizations fitted to different subsets of the ammonium sulfate solution water activity data from Low [71]:

$$a_w^{AS1} = 1 - 0.039767b_{AS} + 0.0079808b_{AS}^2 - 0.0022641b_{AS}^3, \quad b_{AS}/[\text{mol/kg}] \in [0.01 - 1.8]$$

$$a_w^{AS2} = 1 - 0.034954b_{AS} + 0.0014418b_{AS}^2 - 0.00024001b_{AS}^3, \quad b_{AS}/[\text{mol/kg}] \in [0.01 - 5.5]$$

$$a_w^{AS3} = 1 - 0.036878b_{AS} + 0.0033252b_{AS}^2 - 0.00061242b_{AS}^3, \quad b_{AS}/[\text{mol/kg}] \in [0.01 - 4.0]$$

$$a_w^{AS4} = 1 - 0.038073b_{AS} + 0.0048602b_{AS}^2 - 0.0010219b_{AS}^3, \quad b_{AS}/[\text{mol/kg}] \in [0.01 - 3.0]$$

$$a_w^{AS5} = 1 - 0.038612b_{AS} + 0.0057116b_{AS}^2 - 0.0013058b_{AS}^3, \quad b_{AS}/[\text{mol/kg}] \in [0.01 - 2.5]$$

The respective Köhler curves calculated with the different parameterizations $a_w^{AS1} - a_w^{AS5}$ are shown in fig. B.6 and the corresponding critical supersaturation $SS_c(\text{calc})$ are listed in table B.3. It is seen, that the calculated values of the critical supersaturation $SS_c(\text{calc})$ for 40 nm ammonium sulfate particles are most affected by the parameterized water activity values for the most dilute solutions, whereas the effects of the parameterization differences for more concentrated solutions nearly even out before activation is reached. This is not unexpected, as the ammonium sulfate droplet solution water activities at activation are calculated to be in the range $a_{w_c}^{calc} < 0.15$ (see table 3.3).

On this grounding, the critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{calc})$ for ammonium sulfate particles are calculated with the water activity parameterization given in equation 3.13, corresponding to a_w^{AS1} , which gives the best fit to the ammonium sulfate solution water activity data from Low [71] for the smallest ammonium sulfate molalities. This parameterization is based on 14 of the 22 available data points and is thus believed still to be of some validity. The largest variation in the calculated critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{calc})$ for 40 nm ammonium sulfate particles with the different parameterizations is -6% of the value calculated with the parameterization equation 3.13.

It is reassuring, that both the calculated sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate molalities at activation $b_c^{calc}_{SC}$ and $b_c^{calc}_{AS}$ given in table 3.3 are within the concentration ranges $b_{SC} \in [0.01 - 6.0]$ mol/kg and $b_{AS} \in [0.01 - 1.8]$ mol/kg spanned by the data points used for the respective selected water activity parameterizations for all particles studied.

Figure B.6: Critical (left) and earliest (right) points of the Köhler curves for a 40 nm ammonium sulfate particle calculated with different parameterizations of the droplet solution water activity a_w^{AS} . The legends denote the section of water activity data from Low [71] used for each parameterization.

parameterization	range	$SS_c(\text{calc})[\%]$
a_w^{AS1}	$b_{AS}/[\text{mol}/\text{kg}] \in [0.01 - 1.8]$	0.6503
a_w^{AS2}	$b_{AS}/[\text{mol}/\text{kg}] \in [0.01 - 6.0]$	0.6895
a_w^{AS3}	$b_{AS}/[\text{mol}/\text{kg}] \in [0.01 - 4.0]$	0.6726
a_w^{AS4}	$b_{AS}/[\text{mol}/\text{kg}] \in [0.01 - 3.0]$	0.6629
a_w^{AS5}	$b_{AS}/[\text{mol}/\text{kg}] \in [0.01 - 2.5]$	0.6588

Table B.3: Different solution water activity parameterizations $a_w^{AS1} - a_w^{AS5}$ and the calculated critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{calc})$ for 40 nm ammonium sulfate particles, corresponding to the Köhler curves in fig. B.6. The difference between the smallest and largest values of $SS_c(\text{calc})$ constitute a variation of -6.0% in the smallest value. This value is calculated with parameterization a_w^{AS1} , which is the one used for the calculations in section 3.2.2.

B.2.2 Other Calculation Parameters

The sensitivity of calculated critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{calc})$ for 35 nm sodium chloride and 40 nm ammonium sulfate particles have been tested for a substitution of the linear expressions for the sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate solution surface tensions σ^{SC} and σ^{AS} in equations 3.14 and 3.15 with the constant value of the surface tension of pure water $\sigma_w = 0.07275 \text{ N/m}$ (20°C). The resulting calculated critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{calc})$ are not very sensitive to this substitution, as the variations in $SS_c(\text{calc})$ are numerically less than 1% in both cases (see table B.4). This is not unexpected, since equations 3.14 and 3.15 yield solution surface tensions at activation in the ranges $\sigma_c^{SC^{calc}} \in [72.80-72.95] \text{ mN/m}$ and $\sigma_c^{AS^{calc}} \in [72.80-73.10] \text{ mN/m}$ (see table 3.3) and consequently very close to the pure water value. The linear relations 3.14 and 3.15 are retained in the calculations in section 3.2.2, since they are believed to be more correct by principle.

The critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{calc})$ have been calculated in section 3.2.2 assuming a temperature of $25^\circ\text{C} = 298.15 \text{ K}$; however, the temperature in the laboratory has varied over the course of the measurements leading to the corresponding experimental values $SS_c(\text{meas})$, so the sensitivity of the calculations to a variation in temperature of $\pm 5 \text{ K}$ has been tested. Since the water density is a function of temperature, a test of the calculation sensitivity to the corresponding variation in $\rho_w = 997.0480 \text{ kg/m}^3(25^\circ\text{C})$, to $995.6511 \text{ kg/m}^3(30^\circ\text{C})$ and $998.2063 \text{ kg/m}^3(20^\circ\text{C})$, respectively, is also made. The calculated critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{calc})$ are somewhat sensitive to the given variations in temperature, but not to the corresponding variations in the water density on itself, as the perturbations give rise to numerical variations in $SS_c(\text{calc})$ of about 2.5% in the first case and $<1\%$ in the second (see table B.4).

Finally, considering the quasi-monodisperse quality of the dry particle size D_p selected by the DMA, the sensitivity of the calculations is tested for a variation in the dry particle diameter of $\pm 1 \text{ nm}$ in accordance with Bilde et al. [15]. The calculated critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{calc})$ are somewhat sensitive to this perturbation, which causes a

numerical variation in $SS_c(\text{calc})$ of about 4% (see table B.4). Again, this is not unexpected, since such a variation in dry particle size for the relatively low molecular weight salts sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate constitutes a considerable variation in the amount in moles of dissolved compound, affecting the water activity of the droplet solutions.

In conclusion should be noted, that the choice of water activity parameterization is the factor causing the strongest variation in the calculated critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{calc})$ of the different parameters tested here, at least for 40 nm ammonium sulfate particles. The water activity parameterization selected for the activation calculations of sodium chloride and ammonium sulfate particles is therefore believed to be of some importance to the quality of these calculations.

parameter	value used	$SS_c(\text{calc})$ [%]	perturbation	$SS_c(\text{pert})$ [%]	$\frac{\Delta SS_c}{SS_c(\text{calc})}$ [%]
D_p^{AS}	40 nm	0.6503	+1 nm	0.6264	-3.7
D_p^{AS}	40 nm	0.6503	-1 nm	0.6758	3.9
D_p^{SC}	35 nm	0.5295	+1 nm	0.5075	-4.2
D_p^{SC}	35 nm	0.5295	-1 nm	0.5530	4.4
T, AS	298.15 K	0.6503	+5 K	0.6341	-2.5
T, AS	298.15 K	0.6503	-5 K	0.6673	2.6
T, SC	298.15 K	0.5295	+5 K	0.5164	-2.5
T, SC	298.15 K	0.5295	-5 K	0.5431	2.6
ρ_w, AS	997.0480 kg/m ³	0.6503	995.6511 kg/m ³	0.6513	0.2
ρ_w, AS	997.0480 kg/m ³	0.6503	998.2063 kg/m ³	0.6496	-0.1
ρ_w, SC	997.0480 kg/m ³	0.5295	995.6511 kg/m ³	0.5302	0.1
ρ_w, SC	997.0480 kg/m ³	0.5295	998.2063 kg/m ³	0.5288	-0.1
σ^{AS}	eq. 3.15	0.6503	$\sigma_w = 0.07275$ N/m	0.6479	-0.4
σ^{SC}	eq. 3.14	0.5295	$\sigma_w = 0.07275$ N/m	0.5260	-0.7

Table B.4: Sensitivity of the calculated critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{calc})$ for 40 nm ammonium sulfate (AS) and 35 nm sodium chloride (SC) particles to variation in dry particle size D_p , temperature T , water density ρ_w and solution surface tension σ .

B.3 Sensitivity of Dissociation Calculations

The equilibrium concentrations of undissociated acid have been calculated for both citric and malic acid considering both the full stepwise dissociation as outlined in section 2.2.6 and only the first dissociation step as employed in section 4.1.3. Calculations are made at activation for droplets formed from the selected sizes of 30 and 100 nm pure citric and malic acid dry particles, respectively.

Citric acid has 3 carboxylic groups; considering all 3 dissociation steps according to

equation 2.64 for triprotic acid H_3A gives the equilibrium conditions

$$\begin{aligned}
 [H_3A]_{eq} &= [H_3A]_{in} - X_1 \\
 [H_2A^-]_{eq} &= X_1 - X_2 \\
 [HA^{2-}]_{eq} &= X_2 - X_3 \\
 [A^{3-}]_{eq} &= X_3 \\
 [H_3O^+]_{eq} &= X_1 + X_2 + X_3
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{B.3}$$

For the 2 dissociation steps of a diprotic acid H_2A as malic acid, which has 2 carboxylic groups, the equilibrium conditions are similarly

$$\begin{aligned}
 [H_2A]_{eq} &= [H_2A]_{in} - X_1 \\
 [HA^-]_{eq} &= X_1 - X_2 \\
 [A^{2-}]_{eq} &= X_2 \\
 [H_3O^+]_{eq} &= X_1 + X_2
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{B.4}$$

These equation sets are solved numerically using the bisection method together with the defining equations 2.65 and given values in table 4.2 for the stepwise acid constants, to obtain the equilibrium concentrations of undissociated acid $[H_nA]_{eq}$ (all steps).

The same calculations are then performed considering only the first dissociation step for citric and malic acid, respectively, by employing equations 4.20 and 4.21 given in section 4.1.3 to give the equilibrium concentrations of undissociated acid $[H_nA]_{eq}$ (first step).

In both cases, the total acid molar concentration $[H_nA]_{in}$ is obtained from the activation calculations as described in section 4.1.3. The results of the two dissociation calculation procedures are shown in table B.5.

(all in mol/L)		$[H_nA]_{in}$	$[H_nA]_{eq}$ (all steps)	$[H_nA]_{eq}$ (first step)
citric acid	30 nm	0.5329905	0.5136995	0.5136995
	100 nm	0.07984382	0.07259204	0.07259204
malic acid	30 nm	0.5846785	0.5696196	0.5696196
	100 nm	0.1114074	0.1049438	0.1049438

Table B.5: Equilibrium concentrations of undissociated acid at activation in droplets formed from 30 and 100 nm pure citric and malic acid particles, calculated considering the full stepwise acid dissociation and only the first dissociation step, respectively. The two calculation methods give the same results.

For the cases investigated, both calculation procedures give the same results for the equilibrium concentration of undissociated acid $[H_nA]_{eq}$ within the number of decimals included here. Therefore, the more usable calculation approach considering only the first acid dissociation step is employed in section 4.1.3.

Appendix C

Corrections

- Unless otherwise stated, temperature refers to the Kelvin temperature.
- Unless otherwise stated, parameterizations employ values of the quantities concerned as given by the standard units presented when the respective quantities are introduced.
- section 1.2, pp.8-9 (4 occurrences) and section 4.2.3, pp.111: "water" should be "water vapor"
- section 2.2.3, pp.20: "[86]" should be "Robinson and Stokes [86]"
- section 2.2.4, pp.21: "where y_v is the mole fraction of water vapor in the gas mixture, defined in equation 2.8" is missing after equation 2.34
- section 2.2.5, pp.26: "molar weight" after equation 2.54 should be "molar mass"
- section 2.2.6, pp.30: "relation 2.69 is valid" should be "relation 2.69 is derived"
- section 2.3.2, pp.34: equation 2.79 should be

$$\begin{aligned} p_w^{0,drop} &= p_w^0(T, p) \exp\left(\frac{v_w^0 \Delta p}{RT}\right) \\ &= p_w^0(T, p) \exp\left(\frac{v_w^0 2\sigma_w}{RT r}\right) \\ &= p_w^0(T, p) \exp\left(\frac{2M_w \sigma_w}{RT \rho_w r}\right) \end{aligned} \tag{C.1}$$

- section 3.1.1, pp.46: equation 3.3 should be

$$D_p^e = \frac{D_p^{EM}}{\chi} \tag{C.2}$$

- sections 3.1.1, pp.47 and 3.1.2, pp.50: size distribution designation " dCN/dD_p " should be " $dN(CN)/d\log D_p$ "

- section 3.1.3, pp.53: "the supersaturation SS for which half the particles in the aerosol flow have activated, given by $f_{act} = 0.5(f_{act}^{max} - f_{act}^{min})$ [88, pp.25]" should be "the supersaturation SS for which half the particles in the aerosol flow have activated [88, pp.25], given by $f_{act} = f_{act}^{min} + 0.5(f_{act}^{max} - f_{act}^{min})$ "
- section 3.2.2, pp.58; section 4.1.3, pp.72 and pp.73, section 4.1.3, pp.83 (3 occurrences), section B.2.1, pp.164 and section B.2.2, pp.168-169 (2 occurrences): "density" should be "mass density"
- section 3.2.2, pp.61: in table 3.3, the dimension [%] of $\sigma_{SS_c(\text{meas})}$ is missing
- section 4.1.3, pp.78: "within seconds" should be "within half to whole minutes"
- section 4.1.3, pp.83: equation 4.25 should be

$$x_{MA}^n \equiv \frac{n_{MA}}{n_w + n_{MA}} \quad (\text{C.3})$$

and the following remark "where x_{MA}^m is the corresponding malic acid mass fraction" should be omitted

- section 4.1.3, pp.84: according to the correction of equation 4.25, the entries in table C.1 should be

D_p^{MA}	σ	$SS_c(\text{theo})$	$\frac{\Delta SS_c}{SS_c(\text{theo})}$	d_c	b_{MAc}	a_{wc}	σ_c
	[mN/m]	[%]	[%]	[nm]	[mol/kg]		[mN/m]
40 nm	σ_w	1.1679		121.6	0.4420	0.9944	71.98
	σ_{MA}	1.1214	-4.0	124.9	0.4067	0.9948	70.07
80 nm	σ_w	0.4070		338.6	0.1601	0.9979	71.98
	σ_{MA}	0.3977	-2.3	347.1	0.1484	0.9980	70.92

Table C.1: Critical supersaturations $SS_c(\text{theo})$, as well as droplet diameters d_c , malic acid molalities b_{MAc} and solution water activity a_{wc} and surface tension σ_c at activation, calculated with the EDB water activity parameterization approach for 40 and 80 nm pure malic acid particles, using a constant surface tension equal to the value for pure water σ_w and the malic acid aqueous solution surface tension σ_{MA} from equation 4.26 given by Hyvärinen et al. [48].

- section 4.2.1, pp.88: in text to figures 4.5 and 4.6, remarks "Again, note the different axis scales used for the left and right figure" and "Note the different axis scales used in the two figures" should be omitted
- section 4.2.1, pp.89: "This may then contribute to rationalize the very close activation behavior of the pure and mixed malic acid containing particles in fig. 4.6 (right)" is incorrect
- section 4.2.3, pp.111-112 and section 5.1.1, pp.119: Malonic, Glutaric and Oxalic acid, α -Pinene compound names should not be capitalized

- section 5.1.2, pp.121: "This results in fewer particles in the wet aerosol" should be "This results in fewer droplets in the wet aerosol"
- section 5.1.2, pp.122: in table 5.2, entry "0.05737" for " m_{CPA}^w " should be "0.0537"
- section 5.1.3, pp.124: " $c_{CPA}^{sol,w}$ is the solubility of *cis*-pinonic acid in pure water" should be " $c_{CPA}^{sol,w}$ is the solubility of *cis*-pinonic acid in pure water, given as the molar concentration of a saturated aqueous *cis*-pinonic acid solution"
- section 5.1.3, pp.124: "where c_{CPA}^B and c_{AS}^B are the respective bulk concentrations" should be "where c_{CPA}^B and c_{AS}^B are the respective molar bulk concentrations"
- section 5.1.4, pp.126: "largest attainable Kelvin and Raoult effects" should be "smallest Kelvin and largest Raoult effects attainable"
- section 5.2.1, pp.129: "though only within the depicted experimental error" should be "though only within the depicted experimental uncertainty"
- section A.4, pp.160: equation A.17 should be

$$X_{AS}^m \equiv \frac{m_{AS}}{m_w + m_{AS}} \cdot 100\% = \frac{b_{AS}M_{AS}}{1 + b_{AS}M_{AS}} \cdot 100\% \quad (\text{C.4})$$

- section A.4, pp.161: according to the correction of equation A.17, fig. A.5 should be

Figure C.1: Ammonium sulfate solution water activity a_{wAS} calculated with the parameterizations A.16, A.18, A.19 and A.15 for the ammonium sulfate solution molal concentration ranges $b_{AS} \in [0 - 1.0]$ mol/kg (right) and $b_{AS} \in [0 - 0.1]$ mol/kg (left). The mutual agreement is rather close, despite the different parameterization approaches used.

- section B.1.2, pp.163 (2 occurrences): "number" should be "number concentration"
- section B.2.1, pp.165-166 (3 occurrences): "constraint $y(x = 0) = 1$ " should be "constraint $a_w(b = 0) = 1$ "

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